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PhD Thesis in Emerging Digital Technologies

Advances in Airborne Wind Energy and Wind Drones

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Preface and Acknowledgements

When I first started my PhD program at Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna in Pisa I never imagined the vibrant, educational, constructive and inspiring environment that I found. I still don't know what makes this place so good for research, it might be the balance between sunny summers and rainy winters, or the left-wing, dirty and warm city, or the amount of artists and philosophers outside the laboratory, or simply a strong tradition of science and engineering. After all, this is where Galileo was from. In Pisa it is easy to meet new people and share your thoughts with them, I will always remember some of the best conversations of my life during random nights with people whose name I can hardly remember. It seems that good brainstorming, creative thinking, games and art are rooted deep inside this place.

Scuola Sant'Anna is a tiny and beautiful university in Pisa, born 30 years ago, and now in the top ten world ranking of the young universities. Few people outside Italy know it, but whoever has known Sant'Anna has good words for it. I am glad and proud to have been part of it and I hope that this thesis and my publications will be a small piece of the big puzzle of innovation that mankind needs in a world where resources are always less and demand is always more.

The list of people that I should thank is fairly long and it goes more or less like this. First, I wish to thank my supervisor, Prof. Marco Fontana, the kindest of all bosses and a really really bright mind. Thank you Marco, you are a master to me. Special thanks to my colleagues Giacomo and Gastone for their deep daily conversations in our tasty and lovely canteen and their constructive attitude. Thanks also to: Prof. Roland Schmehl for trusting me, Pietro Fag-

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Hoping that the reader of this thesis will find this work useful, I wish to add that the footer of this thesis contains a flipbook animation where the reader can already see a dual drone system taking off!

Abstract

Among novel technologies for producing electricity from renewable resources, a new class of wind energy converters has been conceived under the name of Airborne Wind Energy Systems (AWESs) or Wind Drones (WDs). This new generation of systems employs flying tethered wings or aircraft in order to reach winds blowing at atmosphere layers that are inaccessible by traditional wind turbines.

The economics of AWESs is very promising for mainly two reasons. First, winds high above ground level are steadier and typically much more powerful, persistent and globally available than those closer to the ground, and second, the structure of AWESs is expected to be orders of magnitude lighter than conventional wind turbines. These plants are therefore interesting for their potential high power density, i.e. ratio between nominal power and weight of required constructions, that makes it possible to forecast a low Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) for the produced electricity.

Despite this interesting potential, two important issues might be a major limitation to AWESs development. First, the large requirement in terms of airspace and the related safety issues, and second, the power dissipation through the aerodynamic cable drag. In a scenario where AWESs beat conventional wind turbines in terms of LCOE, the large airspace requirement is a logistic constraint that might slow down the economic development of AWESs, but the relatively small size/weight of AWESs foundations might be a key factor that enables the development of inexpensive floating offshore platforms thus solving the airspace limitations thanks to practically unlimited sea area. A significant part of this thesis investigates the performance of floating offshore AWESs by means of dynamic models, first with a single Degree of Freedom (D.o.F.) of the floating platform, then with a more complex multi D.o.F. model.

The second issue, the aerodynamic cable drag, is a physical constraint that is already limiting the potential of AWESs. In short, in order to reach higher altitudes, current AWESs must increase the cable length, but the power that would be dissipated by sweeping a longer cable through the air exceeds the power that would be gained from stronger winds at higher altitudes. This prevents current AWESs from working at very high altitudes where the jet streams carry up to 15.5 kW/m^2 of wind power density.

A possible solution to this second problem is represented by a

dual Wind Drone architecture in which two aircrafts, with on-board generators, are connected to the ground with a ‘Y’ shaped tethering; a concept that was first envisioned in 1976. At that time it was hard to envision a real operation of this system but recent studies are starting to investigate this concept in more detail. The last two chapters contain an attempt to estimate the power output of a large scale dual Wind Drone system and a proposal for a novel take-off method that might enable a first implementation of the dual Wind Drone system. It is first introduced a power model that captures the most significant real-world issues such as the effect of the weight of airborne components, the limits of structural/electrical elements, and considers take-off constraints. A numerical case study is analyzed considering a large scale system in Saudi Arabia. For such a device, the power curve is computed and, using real wind data, a nominal power output of approximately 15 MW with 30% capacity factor is estimated. Finally an experimental campaign that was carried out in TU Delft is described. In that campaign a take-off system for dual drones inspired to the so called ‘control line flight’ was investigated. The passive flight stability of a single wind drone in axi-symmetric configuration is a positive experimental evidence that encourages further research in dual drone systems.

Contents

Introduction	13
1 Airborne Wind Energy: state of the art and literature review	17
1.1 Availability of Airborne Wind Energy	18
1.2 Classifications of Airborne Wind Energy Systems . . .	19
1.3 Ground-Gen Airborne Wind Energy Systems	20
1.3.1 Ground-Gen systems architectures and aircraft	23
1.3.2 Fixed-ground-station systems under development	26
1.3.3 Moving-ground-station systems under develop- ment	34
1.4 Fly-Gen Airborne Wind Energy Systems	35
1.4.1 Aircraft in Fly-Gen systems	35
1.4.2 Fly-Gen systems under development	38
1.5 Crosswind flight: the key to large scale deployment . .	40
1.5.1 Crosswind GG-AWESs	42
1.5.2 Crosswind FG-AWESs	44
1.6 Discussion	46
1.6.1 Effect of flying mass	46
1.6.2 Rigid vs Soft Wings	46
1.6.3 Take-off and landing challenge	46
1.6.4 Optimal altitude	47
1.6.5 Angle of attack control	47
1.6.6 Cables	48
1.6.7 Business opportunities	50
1.7 Conclusions	50

2	Simplified model of offshore airborne wind energy converters	53
2.1	Offshore AWES	54
2.2	Model	56
2.2.1	Hydrodynamic model	57
2.2.2	Aerodynamic model	59
2.2.3	Integrated model	61
2.2.4	Control	62
2.2.5	Combined wind-wave power output	63
2.3	Case study	65
2.3.1	Geometry	65
2.3.2	Computation of the hydrodynamic coefficients	67
2.3.3	Results	67
2.3.4	Small aircraft - Small platform	69
2.3.5	Small aircraft - Medium platform	69
2.3.6	Small aircraft - Big platform	69
2.3.7	Big aircraft	69
2.3.8	Discussion	70
2.3.9	Transient behaviour	70
2.3.10	Applicability of the results	73
2.4	Conclusions	73
3	Dynamic model of floating offshore airborne wind energy systems	75
3.1	Model	76
3.1.1	Floating platform dynamic model	78
3.1.2	Mooring lines model	81
3.1.3	Kite model	83
3.2	Case study	86
3.2.1	Simulator	87
3.2.2	Platform and mooring	89
3.2.3	Kite and controller	91
3.2.4	Simulation results	93
3.3	Discussion	97
3.4	Conclusions	102
4	Assessment of high altitude dual wind energy drone generators	103
4.1	Jet stream altitude wind drone system	104
4.2	Model	108

4.2.1	Model hypotheses	108
4.2.2	Geometrical relations	109
4.2.3	Distributed drag on fixed cable	109
4.2.4	Crosswind Fly-Gen flight and drone mass	110
4.2.5	Structural equations of dancing cables	113
4.2.6	Electrical equations	113
4.2.7	Fixed cable mass and shape	114
4.2.8	Power output	115
4.3	Power curves of a dual wind drone system	115
4.3.1	Power coefficient of the high altitude wind drone system	120
4.4	Future works	120
4.5	Conclusions	125
5	Automatic ‘control-line flight’ for high altitude wind energy drones	127
5.1	Dynamic model of take off and landing of a single drone	129
5.1.1	Position	130
5.1.2	Attitude	131
5.1.3	Kinematics	131
5.1.4	Force balance	133
5.1.5	Relative wind velocity and angles of attack	133
5.1.6	Aerodynamic coefficients and forces	134
5.1.7	Pitch motion dynamics	135
5.1.8	Horizontal steady-state flight	136
5.1.9	Pitch stability	136
5.1.10	Altitude stability	137
5.1.11	Faster than real time integration	137
5.2	Test setup	137
5.3	Automatic flight results	139
5.4	Conclusions	144
A	How to use the open source multi d.o.f floating off-shore AWE simulator	149
A.1	Step by step guide	149
A.2	Hydrodynamic preprocessing	151
A.3	Input simulation options	151
A.4	Input platform and mooring data	153
A.5	Input kite data	154
A.6	Simulation results	155

- B Cables for Airborne Wind Energy 159**
 - B.1 Cable sag 2D steady state model 159
 - B.1.1 Differential steady state model at constant tension 160
 - B.1.2 Without gravity, constant ρ 161
 - B.1.3 Without gravity, variable ρ 162
 - B.1.4 With gravity, constant ρ 163
 - B.1.5 Numerical results 163
 - B.2 Partitioned tether fairing 165
 - B.2.1 Concept 165
 - B.2.2 Experimental procedure 167

- C Fast solver based on non-linear iterative nested loops 171**
 - C.1 Pre-processing wind data analysis 171
 - C.2 Solver processing 172
 - C.3 Post-processing and hovering constraint 173

- D Technical drawings of the wind drone experimental setup 177**

- Bibliography 217**

List of Acronyms

AWE	Airborne Wind Energy
AWES	Airborne Wind Energy System
AWT	Airborne Wind Turbine
BEM	Boundary Element Method
CF	Capacity Factor
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamic
DoF	Degree of Freedom
EU	European Union
FEG	Flying Electric Generator
FG	Fly-Gen
FG-AWES	Fly-Gen Airborne Wind Energy System
GG	Ground-Gen
GG-AWES	Ground-Gen Airborne Wind Energy System
ISA	International Standard Atmosphere
LEI	Leading Edge Inflatable
KGR	KiteGen Research
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
NIMBY	Not In My Back-Yard

PTO	Power Take Off
PPM	Pulse Position Modulation
TLP	Tension Leg Platform
UHMWPE	Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene
VIV	Vortex-Induced Vibration
WEC	Wave Energy Converter
WED	Wind Energy Drone
WD	Wind Drone

Introduction

Advancement of societies, and in particular in their ability to sustain larger populations, are closely related to changes in the amount and type of energy available to satisfy human needs for nourishment and to perform work [1]. Low access to energy is an aspect of poverty. Energy, and in particular electrical energy, is indeed crucial to provide adequate services such as water, food, healthcare, education, employment and communication. To date, the majority of energy consumed by our societies has come from fossil and nuclear fuels, which are now facing severe issues such as security of supply, economic affordability, environmental sustainability and disaster risks.

To address these problems, major countries are enacting energy policies focused on the increase in the deployment of renewable energy technologies. In particular:

- since 1992, to prevent the most severe impacts of climate change, the United Nations member states are committed to a drastic reduction in greenhouse gas emissions below the 1990 levels;
- in September 2009, both European Union and G8 leaders agreed that carbon dioxide emissions should be cut by 80% before 2050 [2].

In the European Union (EU), compulsory implementation of such a commitment is occurring via the Kyoto Protocol, which bounded 15 EU members to reduce their collective emissions by 8% in the 2008-2012 period, and the ‘Climate Energy Package (the 20-20-20 targets)’, which obliges EU to cut its own emissions by at least 20% by 2020.

In this context, in the last decades there has been a fast growth and spread of renewable energy plants. Among them, wind generators are the most widespread type of intermittent renewable energy

harvesters with their 318 GW of cumulative installed power at the end of 2013 [3]. Wind capacity, i.e. total installed power, is keeping a positive trend with an increment of 35.47 GW in 2013, however the growth rate slightly decreased due to saturation of in-land windy areas that are suitable for installations. For this reason, current research programs are oriented to the improvement of power capacity per unit of land area. This translates to the global industrial trend of developing single wind turbines with increased nominal power (up to 5 MW) that feature high-length blades (to increase the swept area) and high-height turbine axis (to reach stronger winds at higher altitudes) [4].

More recently, because of market reasons, capacity factors are increasing, reaching values up to 50% [5].

In parallel, since the beginning of 2000s, industrial research is investing on offshore installations. In locations that are far enough from the coast, wind resources are generally greater than those on land, with the winds being stronger and more regular, allowing a more constant usage rate and accurate production planning, and providing more power available for conversions. The foreseen growth rate of offshore installations is promising; if this exponential growth rate is continued [6], the worldwide installed offshore power is envisaged in the order of 45 GW in 2020.

In this framework, a completely new renewable energy sector, Airborne Wind Energy (AWE), emerged in the scientific community. AWE aims at capturing wind energy at significantly increased altitudes. Machines that harvest this kind of energy can be referred to as AWESs. The high level and the persistence of the energy carried by high-altitude winds, that blow in the range of 200 m - 10 km from the ground surface, has attracted the attention of several research communities since the beginning of the eighties. The basic principle was introduced by the seminal work of Loyd [7] in which he analyzed the maximum energy that can be theoretically extracted with AWESs based on tethered wings. During the nineties, the research on AWESs was practically abandoned; but in the last decade, the sector has experienced an extremely rapid acceleration. Several companies have entered the business of high-altitude wind energy, registering hundreds of patents and developing a number of prototypes and demonstrators. More and more research teams all over the world are currently working on different aspects of the technology including control, electronics and mechanical design. Figs. 1 and 2

show the current trends in published knowledge in AWE for the case of industrial patents and academic publications, respectively.

Figure 1: AWE patent application trend Number of patents as a function of year of first application. Non-cumulative results searching for: (airborne wind energy) OR (high altitude wind energy) OR (kite power). Orbit-Questel database, Apr 2017.

Figure 2: AWE academic publication trend Google Scholar search results. Non-cumulative number of items searching for: ‘airborne wind energy’ OR ‘high altitude wind energy’ OR ‘kite power’ -patent.

This thesis is divided into five chapters, Chapter 1 is very useful to the first-time reader and to those who want to know more about AWE and Wind Drones in general. The content is mainly taken from a review paper that we published after the Airborne Wind Energy Conference of 2015 in TU Delft [8]. It is now on the top 20 of the most downloaded papers of all times of the journal ‘Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews’.

Marine applications of AWE are envisaged to be particularly promising thanks to the potential ability to overcome important constraints such as airspace, safety and Not In My Back-Yard (NIMBY) effect. The most interesting case is represented by floating platforms in deep

water locations, that are the most abundantly available and where the airspace is practically unlimited. In order to properly address the problem of design and verification of such a kind of system, models that are able to describe the dynamic response of floating platforms to combined kite forces and wave loads have to be developed. For this reason, two dynamic models for Offshore Airborne Wind Energy Systems are presented in this thesis in two chapters. Chapter 2 introduces a basic model for floating offshore AWESs. Some of its content is taken from one of our publications in ‘Renewable Energy’ [9]. Chapter 3 explains a more advanced model for floating offshore AWESs. Its contents were published in the book ‘Airborne Wind Energy’ [10]. An open source simulator for offshore AWESs was released [11] and its first user-manual is also included in Appendix A.

Together with offshore AWESs, this thesis also deals with another important topic for the long term development of AWE, the reduction of the cable aerodynamic drag by means of multiple wind drone systems. Reaching higher altitudes is desirable because of the higher wind power density, however In order to reach higher altitudes, a longer cable is of course needed. However this means sweeping a longer cable through the air and the gain in power provided by the strength of winds at higher altitude is not enough to compensate the loss in power, through cables drag, that increases with the cable’s length. Chapter 4 is about a theoretical assessment of a system of two drones that is potentially able to overcome the problem of the cable aerodynamic drag and finally unleash the tremendous power of jet-streams. Chapter 5 provides an insight about the experimental flight dynamics of a single tethered wind drone in axi-symmetric configuration in laboratory conditions that provides an understanding of the flight dynamics of a low-drag multiple wind drone system. Appendix B provides further important details about cables for AWE. Being the cable arguably one of the most important subsystems and also a major physical limitation of AWE generators, I decided to include this appendix. Finally, Appendix C describes the architecture of a fast iterative solver for the model proposed in Chapter 4 and Appendix D contains the technical drawing of the experimental setup described in Chapter 5.

Chapter 1

Airborne Wind Energy: state of the art and literature review

This chapter provides an overview of the different AWES concepts focusing on devices that have been practically demonstrated with prototypes. The chapter is structured as follows. Section 1.1 provides a brief description of the energy resource of high altitude winds. Section 1.2 provides a unified and comprehensive classification of different AWES concepts, which tries to merge previously proposed taxonomies. In sections 1.3 and 1.4, an up to date overview of different devices and concepts is provided. Section 1.5 explains why AWE is so attractive thanks to some simple and well-known models. Finally, section 1.6 presents some key techno-economic issues basing on the state of the art and trends of academic and private research. Differently from other previously published reviews, this chapter deals with aspects that concern architectural choices and mechanical design of AWESs. We made our best in collecting comprehensive information from literature, patents and also by direct contacts with some of the major industrial and academic actors.

1.1 Availability of Airborne Wind Energy

High-altitude winds have been studied since decades by meteorologists, climatologists and by researchers in the field of environmental science even though many questions are still unsolved [12]. The first work aimed at evaluating the potential of AWE as a renewable energy resource has been presented by Archer and Caldeira [13]. Their paper introduces a study that assesses a huge worldwide availability of kinetic energy of wind at altitudes, between 0.5 km and 12 km above the ground, providing clear geographical distribution and persistency maps of wind power density at different ranges of altitude. This preliminary analysis does not take into account the consequences on wind and climate of a possible extraction of kinetic energy from winds. However, the conclusions of these researchers already raised the attention of many researchers and engineers suggesting great promises for technologies able to harvest energy from high altitude winds.

More in depth studies have been conducted employing complex climate models, which predict consequences associated with the introduction of wind energy harvesters (near surface and at high altitude), that exerts distributed drag forces against wind flows. Marvel et al. [14] estimate a maximum of 400 TW and 1800 TW of kinetic power that could be extracted from winds that blows respectively near-surface (harvested with traditional wind turbines) and through the whole atmospheric layer (harvested with both traditional turbines and high altitude wind energy converters). Even if in the case of such a massive extraction severe/undesirable changes could affect the global climate, the authors show that the extraction of ‘only’ 18 TW (i.e. a quantity comparable with the actual world power demand) does not produce significant effects at global scale. This means that, from the geophysical point of view, very large quantity of power can be extracted from wind at different altitudes.

A more skeptical view on high altitude winds is provided in Miller et al. [15] who evaluated in 7.5 TW the maximum sustainable global power extraction. But their analysis is solely focused on jet stream winds (i.e. only at very high altitude between 6 km - 15 km above the ground).

Despite the large variability and the level of uncertainty of these results and forecasts, it is possible to conclude that an important share of the worldwide primary energy could be potentially extracted from high altitude winds. This makes it possible to envisage great

business and research opportunities for the next years in the field of Airborne Wind Energy.

1.2 Classifications of Airborne Wind Energy Systems

In this chapter, the term AWES is used to identify the whole electro-mechanical machine that transforms the kinetic energy of wind into electrical energy. AWESs are generally made of two main components, a ground system and at least one aircraft that are mechanically connected (in some cases also electrically connected) by ropes (often referred to as tethers). Among the different AWES concepts, we can distinguish *Ground-Gen* systems in which the conversion of mechanical energy into electrical energy takes place on the ground and *Fly-Gen* systems in which such conversion is done on the aircraft [16] (Fig. 1.1).

Figure 1.1: AWESs. Example of Ground-Gen (a) and Fly-Gen (b) AWESs.

In a Ground-Gen Airborne Wind Energy System (GG-AWES), electrical energy is produced on the ground by mechanical work done by traction force, transmitted from the aircraft to the ground system through one or more ropes, which produce the motion of an electrical generator. Among GG-AWESs we can distinguish between *fixed-ground-station* devices, where the ground station is fixed to the ground and *moving-ground-station* systems, where the ground station is a moving vehicle.

In a Fly-Gen Airborne Wind Energy System (FG-AWES), electrical energy is produced on the aircraft and it is transmitted to the ground via a special rope which carries electrical cables. In this case, electrical energy conversion is generally achieved using wind turbines. FG-AWESs produce electric power continuously while in operation except during take-off and landing maneuvers in which energy is consumed. Among FG-AWESs it is possible to find crosswind systems and non-crosswind systems depending on how they generate energy.

1.3 Ground-Gen Airborne Wind Energy Systems

In GG-AWESs electrical energy is produced exploiting aerodynamic forces that are transmitted from the aircraft to the ground through ropes. As previously anticipated, GG-AWESs can be distinguished in devices with fixed or moving-ground-station.

Fixed-ground-station GG-AWESs (or Pumping Kite Generators) are among the most exhaustively studied by private companies and academic research laboratories. Energy conversion is achieved with a two-phase cycle composed by a generation phase, in which electrical energy is produced, and a recovery phase, in which a smaller amount of energy is consumed (Fig. 1.2). In these systems, the ropes, which are subjected to traction forces, are wound on winches that, in turn, are connected to motor-generators axes. During the generation phase, aircraft are driven in a way to produce a lift force and consequently a traction (unwinding) force on the ropes that induces the rotation of the electrical generators. For the generation phase, the most used mode of flight is the crosswind flight (Fig. 1.2.a) with circular or so called eight-shaped paths. As compared to a non-crosswind flight (with the aircraft in a static angular position in the sky), this mode induces a stronger apparent wind on the aircraft that increases the pulling force acting on the rope. In the recovery phase (Fig. 1.2.b) motors rewind the ropes bringing the aircraft back to its original position from the ground. In order to have a positive balance, the net energy produced in the generation phase has to be larger than the energy spent in the recovery phase. This is guaranteed by a control system that adjusts the aerodynamic characteristics of the aircraft [17] and/or controls its flight path [18] in a way to maximize the energy produced in the generation phase and to minimize the

energy consumed in the recovery phase.

Figure 1.2: Scheme of the two-phase discontinuous energy production for GG-AWESs. a) The energy generation phase occurs during the unwinding of the ropes as the aircraft performs a crosswind flight. b) The recovery phase is performed in order to minimize the energy consumed for the recovery.

Pumping kite generators present a highly discontinuous power output, with long alternating time-periods (in the order of tens of seconds) of energy generation and consumption. Such an unattractive feature makes it necessary to resort to electrical rectification means like batteries or large capacitors. The deployment of multiple AWESs in large high-altitude wind energy farms could significantly reduce the size of electrical storage needed.

Moving-ground-station GG-AWESs are generally more complex systems that aim at providing an always positive power flow which makes it possible to simplify their connection to the grid. There are different concepts of moving-ground-station GG-AWESs (Fig. 1.3) but no working prototype has been developed up to date and only one prototype is currently under development (see paragraph 1.3.3). Differently from the pumping generator, for moving-ground-station systems, the rope winding and unwinding is not producing/consuming significant power but is eventually used only to control the aircraft trajectory. The generation takes place thanks to the traction force of ropes that induces the rotation (or linear motion) of a generator that exploits the ground station movement rather than the rope winding mechanism.

Basically, there are two kinds of moving-ground-station GG-AWES:

- ‘Vertical axis generator’ (Fig. 1.3.a) where ground stations are

Figure 1.3: Scheme of three different concepts of moving-ground-station GG-AWES. a) Vertical axis generator: ground stations are fixed on the periphery of the rotor of a vertical axis generator; b) Closed loop rail: ground stations are fixed on trolleys that move along a closed loop rail; c) Open loop rail: ground stations are fixed on trolleys that move along an open loop rail.

fixed on the periphery of the rotor of a large electric generator with vertical axis. In this case, the aircraft forces make the ground stations rotate together with the rotor, which in turn transmits torque to the generator.

- ‘Rail generators’ (closed loop rail (Fig. 1.3.b) or open loop rail (Fig. 1.3.c)) where ground stations are integrated on rail vehicles and electric energy is generated from vehicle motion. In these systems, energy generation looks like a reverse operation of an electric train.

The following subsections provide an overview of the most relevant prototypes of GG-AWESs under development in the industry and the academy.

1.3.1 Ground-Gen systems architectures and aircraft

In Ground-Gen (GG) systems the aircraft transmits mechanical power to the ground by converting wind aerodynamic forces into rope tensile forces. The different concepts that were prototyped are listed in Fig. 1.4; examples of aircraft of GG systems that are currently under development are presented in Fig. 1.5. They exploit aerodynamic lift forces generated by the wind on their surfaces/wings.

The aircraft is connected to the ground by at least one power-rope that is responsible for transmitting the lift force (and the harvested power) to the ground station. The flight trajectory can be controlled by means of on-board actuators (Fig. 1.4.a), or with a control pod (Fig. 1.4.b), or by regulating the tension of the same power-ropes (Fig. 1.4.c), or with thinner control-ropes (Fig. 1.4.d).

There are also two GG concepts that are worth mentioning: one uses parachutes which exploit aerodynamics drag forces [19, 20], the other uses rotating aerostats which exploit the Magnus effect [21, 22].

The most important aircraft used for GG systems are here listed:

1. *LEI kites* [23] are single layer kites whose flexural stiffness is enhanced by inflatable structures on the leading edge (Figs. 1.5.a). The stiffened tube-like structure of LEI kites is especially useful for take-off and landing maneuvers when the wing is not yet supported by wind pressure. The ease of handling is very

Figure 1.4: Control layout of crosswind GG-AWESs. (a) with on-board control actuators; (b) with flying control pod; (c) control through power ropes; (d) with additional control rope.

Figure 1.5: Different types of aircraft in Ground-Gen systems. a) LEI Kite; c) Foil Kite, design from Skysails; (d) Glider, design from Ampyx Power; e) Swept rigid wing, design from Enerkite; f) Semi-rigid wing, design from Kitegen.

appreciated also during small-scale prototyping and subsystem testing. However LEI kites have severe scalability issues as the tube diameter needs to be oversized in case of large wings.

2. *Foil kites* (also called *ram-air kites*) are derived from parafoils [24]. These double-layer kites are made of canopy cells which run from the leading edge to the trailing edge (Figs. 1.5.c and 1.6.b). Cells (some or all) are open on the leading edge in a way that the air inflates all cells during the flight and gives the kite the necessary stiffness. Bridles are grouped in different lines, frequently three: one central and two laterals. With respect to LEI kites, foil wings have a better aerodynamic efficiency despite the higher number of bridles and can be one order of magnitude larger in size.

Figure 1.6: Control of bridles tension. a) Control bridles are attached to the leading and trailing edges of a LEI kite; b) a control pod can be used to control the flight trajectory and angle of attack.

3. *Delta kites* are similar to hang glider wings. They are made by a single layer of fabric material reinforced by a rigid frame. Compared with LEI or foil kites, this kind of aircraft has a better aerodynamic efficiency which in turn results in a higher efficiency of wind power extraction (as discussed in section 1.6). On the other hand, their rigid frame has to resist to mechanical bending stresses which, in case of high aerodynamic forces, make it necessary to use thick and strong spars which increase the aircraft weight, cost and minimum take-off wind speed.

Durability for fabric wings such as LEI, foil and delta kites, is an issue. Performance is compromised soon and lifetime is usually around several hundred hours [25].

4. *Gliders* (Fig 1.5.d) can also be used as GG aircraft. Like delta kites, their wings are subject to bending moment during the tethered flight. Gliders, and more generally rigid wings, have excellent aerodynamic performance, although they are heavier and more expensive. Lifetime with regular maintenance is several decades.
5. *Swept rigid wings* are gliders without fuselage and tail control surfaces (Fig 1.5.e). Flight stability is most likely achieved thanks to the bridle system and the sweep angle.
6. *Semi-rigid wings* are also under investigation by the Italian company Kitegen Research. They are composed of multiple short rigid modules that are hinged to each other (Fig 1.5.f). The resulting structure is lighter than straight rigid wings and more aerodynamically efficient and durable than fabric kites.
7. *Special design kites*. Kiteplanes [26] and Tensairity Kites [27] are projects developed by TUDelft (The Netherlands) and EMPA (Research Center for Synergetic Structures, ETH Zurich), that aim at increasing the aerodynamic efficiency of arch kites without using rigid spars.

1.3.2 Fixed-ground-station systems under development

This subsection provides a list of fixed-ground-station GG-AWESs which are summarized in Figs. 1.7 and 1.10.

TU Delft

At Delft University of Technology, the first research in Airborne Wind Energy was started by the former astronaut, Prof. Ockels, in 1996 [28]. A dedicated research group was initiated by Ockels in 2004 with the aim to advance the technology to the prototype stage.

Delft University of Technology and Karlsruhe University of Applied Sciences have initiated a joint project to continue the development and testing of a mobile 20 kW experimental pumping kite generator [29]. A main objective of this project is to improve the reliability and robustness of the technology and to demonstrate in the next months a continuous operation of 24 hours. At present, they

use the third version of a special design LEI kite, co-developed with Genetrix / Martial Camblong, of 25 m² wing surface area. Together with an automatic launch setup [30], the wing demonstrated fully automatic operation of their 20 kW system in 2012 [29]. The Tu Delft Spin-Off company ‘Kite Power’ (also known as Enevate B.V.) is now developing a 100 kW system in the framework of the REACH project [31]. This prototype is based on a single tether and an airborne control pod (Fig. 1.4.b) but they also control the angle of attack for powering and depowering the wing during production and recovery phase, respectively. An automatic launch and retrieval system for 100 m² LEI kites is also under development [32].

In the past, the research group tested several kinds of wings such as foil kites and kiteplanes. TU Delft also tested an alternative device for controlling the kite: a cart-and-rail system attached to the tips of a ram-air wing and used to shift the attachment point of the two bridle lines. By that system, the wing could be steered and depowered with a minimal investment of energy. Ultimately, the concept was too complex and too sensitive to deviations from nominal operation [33].

TU Delft is also the main reference point of the AWE academic community by means of several publications and projects, the last of which, the doctoral training network AWESCO, is now home to 14 PhD students in Airborne Wind Energy [34].

Ampyx Power

The first company that developed a pumping glider generator is the Dutch Ampyx Power [35, 36]. After several prototypes, they are currently developing and testing two 5.5 m ‘PowerPlanes’ the AP-2A1 and the AP-2A2 [37]. They are two officially registered aircraft that are automatically controlled with state of the art avionics. They are constructed with a carbon fiber body and a carbon backbone truss which houses onboard electronics with sensors and actuators. Onboard actuators can drive a rudder, an elevator and four flaperons. One rope connects the glider to a single winch in the ground station on the ground (Fig. 1.4.a). Ampyx Power is actually one of the few companies which has already developed an AWES [38] that is able to automatically perform the sequence of glider take-off, pumping cycles and landing. Take-off maneuver sees the glider lying on the ground facing the ground station at some meters of distance. As the winch starts exerting traction force on the rope, the glider moves on the

ground and, as soon as the lift forces exceed the weight forces, the glider takes off. They also installed a catapult for take-off and they have a propulsion system to climb up. The glider flight is fully autonomous during normal operations even though, for safety reasons, it can be occasionally controlled wirelessly from the ground thanks to a backup autopilot. The pumping cycles are similar to those of a kite. Glider landing is similar to that of an airplane and is being equipped with an arresting line so as to stop the glider in a right position for a new take-off. During a test campaign in November 2012, the system demonstrated an average power production of 6 kW with peaks of over 15 kW (earlier tests showed peak in power production of 30 kW). Ampyx has started the design of its first commercial product: a 35 m wingspan AP-4 PowerPlane with a ‘wind turbine equivalent’ power of 2 MW. The company now employs 45 people [38].

Kite Power Solutions

The UK company KPS was founded in 2011 and is now developing a ground-gen pumping kite generator. Similarly to TU Delft’s concept, their prototype uses a soft kite and a control pod. Their kite also features embedded robotic actuation. The company recently received a joint 5 million GBP investment from three energy firms, E.on, Schlumberger and Shell. The start-up’s plan is to build one of the world’s first kite power stations using technology it believes could generate hundreds of megawatts of energy by 2030 [39].

EnerKite

The German company EnerKite [40] developed a portable pumping kite generator with rated continuous power of 30 kW. The ground station is installed on a truck through a pivotal joint which allows azimuthal rotations. EnerKite demonstrator uses mainly a foil kite, but a delta kite and a swept rigid wing are also under investigation and testing. The aircraft does not have on-board sensors and is controlled from the ground with three ropes according to the scheme of Fig. 1.4.d. EnerKite is now developing an autonomous launch and landing system for semi-rigid wings [41]. The company plans to produce a 100 kW and a 500 kW system [42].

KiteGen Research

The company KiteGen Research (KGR) was one of the first to test a prototype of Ground-Gen AWES [43]. KGR technology is based on a C-Kite integrating on board electronics with sensor and is controlled by two power-ropes [44] from a control station on the ground [45] (Fig. 1.4.c). The first prototype, named KSU1 (acronym for Kite Steering Unit) [44, 46] was successfully demonstrated in 2006. After a few years of tests, the company focused on the development of a new generator, named ‘KiteGen Stem’ [47]. In this system, the ropes are wound on special winches [48] and are driven by a pulley system through a 20 m flexible rod called ‘stem’ to an arch-kite or a semi-rigid wing. The stem is linked to the top of the control station through a pivot joint with horizontal axis. The most important functions of the stem are: (1) supporting and holding the kite and (2) damping peak forces in the rope that arise during wind-gusts. The entire control station can make azimuthal rotations so the stem has two degrees of freedom relative to the ground. The ‘Stem’ concept was first patented in 2008 [49] and is now used by more and more companies and universities.

At the beginning of the take-off maneuvers, the kite is hanged upside down at the end of the stem. Once the kite has taken off, the production phase starts: the automatic control drives the kite acting on the two ropes, the kite makes a crosswind flight with ‘eight shape’ paths; at the same time ropes are unwound causing the winches to rotate; the motor-generators transform mechanical power into electric power. The company aims at retracting the cables with minimum energy consumption thanks to a special maneuver called ‘side-slip’ or ‘flagging’ [25]. Side-slip is a different flight mode where the kite aerodynamic lift force is cleared by rewinding at first one rope before the other, which makes the kite lose lift and ‘stall’ and then, once fully stalled, both ropes are rewound at the same speed and the kite precipitates flying sideways. This maneuver can be done with flexible foil kites or semi-rigid wings. In this phase, the power absorbed by motor-generators is given by rope rewind speed multiplied by the resulting aerodynamic drag force of the side-slip flying mode. This power consumption would be a small percentage of the power produced in the production phase. After rewinding a certain length of the ropes (less than the total rope length in order to exploit only the highest winds) another special maneuver restores the gliding

flight and the aerodynamic lift force on the kite. At this point one pumping cycle ends and a new production phase starts.

KGR patented and plans to develop special aerodynamic ropes [50] in order to increase their endurance and to increase system performances. KGR also plans to use the Kitegen Stem technology to produce an offshore AWES [51] since offshore AWESs are very promising [52, 9, 10].

Kitenergy

Another Italian company, Kitenergy, was founded by a former KiteGen partner and is also developing a similar concept by controlling a foil kite with two ropes [53, 54]. The prototype of the company features 60 kW of rated power [55]. Kitenergy submitted also a different GG-AWES patent [56] that consists in a system based on a single motor-generator which controls winding and unwinding of two (or more) cables and another actuator that introduce a differential control action of the employed cables. Another prototype developed by its co-founder, Lorenzo Fagiano, achieved four hours of consecutive autonomous flight with no power production at University of California at Santa Barbara in 2012 [57].

SkySails

The German company SkySails GmbH developed a wind propulsion system for cargo vessels based on kites [58]. A few years ago a new division of the company ‘SkySails Power’ has been created to develop GG-AWES [59] based on the technology used in SkySails vessel propulsion system. Two products are under development: a mobile AWES having a capacity between 250 kW and 1 MW, and an offshore AWES with a capacity from 1 to 3.5 MW. SkySails’ AWES is based on a foil kite controlled with one rope and a control pod (Fig. 1.4.b) which controls the lengths of kite bridles for steering the kite and changes its angle of attack [60]. Control pod power and communication with the ground station is provided via electric cables embedded in the rope. SkySails also has a patented launch and recovery system [61] designed for packing the kite in a storage compartment. It is composed by a telescopic mast with a special device on its top that is able to grab, keep and release the central point of the kite leading edge. When the system is off, the mast is compacted in the storage compartment with the kite deflated. At the beginning

of the launching operation, the mast extends out vertically bringing the deflated kite some meters above the ground (or the sea level). The kite is then inflated to have appropriate shape and stiffness for the production phase. Kite take-off exploits only the natural wind lift force on the kite: the system at the top of the mast releases the kite leading edge, the pod starts to control the flight and the winch releases the rope letting the kite reach the operating altitude. While the energy production phase is similar to that of the KGR generator, SkySails has a different recovery phase. Specifically, SkySails uses high speed winching during reel-in while the kite is kept at the edge of the wind window. The kite is then winched directly against the wind without changing the kite angle of attack. Though it might seem counter-intuitive at first, this kind of recovery phase has proven to be competitive [62].

Unfortunately, in March 2016 SkySails GmbH had to file for insolvency and it has now closed [63].

TwingTec

The Swiss company Twingtec is developing a 100 kW GG-AWES. After having tried several concepts including soft wings and rigid wings, the team is now tackling the problem of automating take-off and landing with the following concept: a glider with embedded rotors having rotational axis perpendicular to the wing plane. The rotors are used during take-off and landing. The company plans to have the generator and power conversion hardware inside a standard 20-foot shipping container in order to easily target off-grid and remote markets. The AWES will supply continuous and reliable electrical power thanks to the integration with conventional diesel generators [64, 65].

Kitemill

Based in Norway, Kitemill started the development of a GG-AWES. The company already switched early on to a 1-cable rigid wing system with on-board actuators (Fig. 1.4.a) after having faced controllability and durability issues with soft materials [66], and most recently the company switched to a 1-cable rigid drone with vertical take-off capabilities, similar to TwingTec's concept. The company was recently funded with 6.5 million Norwegian crowns.

e-Kite

e-Kite was founded in 2013 in the Netherlands and developed a 50 kW GG-AWES (Fig. 1.4.c) based on a direct drive generator. After having investigated several layouts, the company is now focusing on a 1-rope rigid wing with vertical take-off capabilities that will fly at low altitude [67, 68].

Windlift

The US Company Windlift [69] has shifted from a concept similar to that of Enerkite (Fig. 1.4.d) i.e. a 12 kW prototype with LEI kites, to a rigid wing with vertical take-off capabilities. They aim at selling their product to the military and to off-grid locations.

eWind

eWind solutions is a US company that is developing an unconventional, low altitude, rigid wing GG-AWES [70]. The company was recently awarded a 600 k\$ research grant from the US Department of Agriculture.

Skypull

SkyPull is a Swiss startup that is developing a ground-gen double-decker drone with vertical take-off capabilities, in between Joby's and KiteMill's concept [71]. SkyPull won the IMD startup competition in 2016.

KU Leuven

KU Leuven has been actively doing research in AWESs since 2006. After significant theoretical contributions, the team developed a test bench to launch a tethered glider with a novel procedure [72]. Before take-off, the glider is held at the end of a rotating arm. When the arm starts rotating, the glider is brought to flying speed and the tether is released allowing the glider to gain altitude. They are currently developing a larger experimental test set-up, 2 m long with a 10 kW winch. The KU Leuven AWE team, lead by Prof. Moritz Diehl, has recently moved to University of Friburg [73].

SwissKitePower

SwissKitePower is a collaborative research and development project started in Switzerland in 2009. It involves four laboratories of different Swiss universities: FHNW, EMPA (Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology), ETH (Federal Polytechnique of Zurich) and EPFL (École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne). The first prototypes, tested between 2009 and 2011, were based on a C-kite controlled by one rope and a control pod. The initial system worked according to the scheme of Fig. 1.4.b, similarly to KitePower and SkySails prototypes. In 2012, SwissKitePower developed a new ground station with three winches that can be used to test kites with 1, 2 or 3 lines [74]. They also test LEI kites and tensairity kites. The project ended in 2013 and since then FHNW is working in collaboration with the company TwingTec.

NASA Langley

At Langley Research Center, the US space agency NASA conducted a study about wind energy harvesting from airborne platforms after which they developed an AWES demonstrator based on a kite controlled by two ropes and having a vision-based system and sensors located on the ground [75].

Others

In addition to the main prototypes listed above, there are several other systems that have been built.

- Wind tunnel tests of small scale non-crosswind generation, and outdoor crosswind generation tests with a LEI kite [76, 77] of GIPSA-lab/CNRS, University of Grenoble.
- Kite control project [78] of CCNR at Sussex University, UK,
- Electricity from High Altitude Wind with Kites (EHAWK) project [79] of dept. of Mechanical Engineering of Rowan University,
- Kite powered water pump [80] of Worcester Polytechnic Institute.

1.3.3 Moving-ground-station systems under development

In addition to pumping systems, a number of AWES concepts with moving-ground-station have been proposed. Their main advantage is the ability to produce energy continuously or nearly continuously. However, only a few companies are working on AWESs with moving-ground-station and there are more patents and studies than prototypes under development. This subsection provides a list of moving-ground-station GG-AWESs which are summarized in Figs. 1.7 and 1.10

KiteGen Research

The first moving-ground-station architecture which is based on a vertical axis generator has been proposed back in 2004 by Sequoia Automation and acquired by KGR [81]. This AWES concept is based on the architecture described in Fig. 1.3.a. During operations, lift forces are transmitted to a rotating frame inducing a torque around the main vertical axis. Torque and rotation are converted into electricity by the electric generator. This system can be seen as a vertical axis wind turbine driven by forces which come from tethered aircraft. There is no prototype under development, but the concept has been studied in a simulation [18] showing that 100 kites with 500 m² area could generate 1000 MW of average power in a wind with speed of 12 m/s. The considered generator would have a 1500 m radius, occupying a territory about 50 times smaller and costing about 30 times less than a farm of wind turbines with the same nominal power.

NTS Energie

An alternative system based on ground stations that moves on closed track circuits is proposed by KGR [82] and by the German company NTS Energie und Transportsysteme [83, 84]. Starting from September 2011, NTS tested a prototype where 4-rope kites are controlled by a vehicle which moves on a 400 m flat-bed straight railway track. They are able to produce up to 1 kW per m² of wing area and they tested kites up to 40 m² [85]. The final product should have a closed loop railway where more vehicles run independently.

Kitenergy

Another rail concept is proposed by Kitenergy [86] and it is based on ideas published in 2004 in Drachen Foundation journal [87]. The concept is based on a straight linear rail fixed on the ground with a pivotal joint. The rail direction is then adjusted perpendicular to the main direction of the wind. The ground station of the system is mounted on a wheeled vehicle which moves along the straight rail, under the kite traction forces, back and forth from one side to the other. The power is extracted from electromagnetic rotational generators on the wheels of the vehicle or from linear electromagnetic generators on the rail. The power production is not fully continuous because during the inversion of vehicle direction the power production will not only decrease to zero, but it could also be slightly negative. Nevertheless the kite inversion maneuver could be theoretically performed without the need of power consumption.

Laddermill

Although it cannot be considered a moving-ground-station device, it is important to mention that the first concept of continuous energy production AWES was the Laddermill concept envisaged by the former astronaut, Prof. Ockels in 1996 [28].

1.4 Fly-Gen Airborne Wind Energy Systems

In Fly-Gen AWESs, electric energy is produced onboard of the aircraft during its flight and it is transmitted to the ground through one special rope which integrates electric cables. Electrical energy conversion in FG-AWESs is achieved using one or more specially designed wind turbines.

A general classification of these systems is provided in this section.

1.4.1 Aircraft in Fly-Gen systems

Besides the general classification between crosswind and non-crosswind mode proposed in Fig. 1.10, FG-AWESs can also be distinguished basing on their flying principles that are:

CHAPTER 1. AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY: STATE OF THE
ART AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Fixed/Moving	Airborne System	Company/ University	Main force	Actuators		N. Ropes
				On ground	Airborne	
Fixed ground station - Pumping System	Drone	Kitemill	Lift		x	1
		Skypull	Lift		x	1
		TwingTec	Lift		x	1
		eKite	Lift		x	1
	Leading edge inflatable kite	KiteGen Stem	Lift	x		2
		WindLift	Lift	x		3
		Kitenergy	Lift	x		2
		Swiss Kite Power 2	Lift	x		3
		KitePower - TU Delft	Lift		x	1
		Swiss Kite Power 1	Lift		x	1
	Foil kite	SkySails Power	Lift		x	1
		EnerKite	Lift	x		3
	Delta Kite	EnerKite	Lift	x		3
	Swept Rigid Wing	EnerKite	Lift	x		3
	Glider	Ampyx Power	Lift		x	1
		eWind	Lift		x	1
	Semi-rigid Wing	KiteGen Stem	Lift	x		2
Parachute	GuangdongTech	Drag		x	2	
Aerostat	Omnidea	Magnus effect		x	2	
Moving ground station	- Rail	Leading edge inflatable kite	KiteGen Rail Carousel	Lift	x	2
		Kitenergy	Lift	x	2	
	Foil kite	NTS	Lift	x	4	
	-Axial	Leading edge inflatable kite	KiteGen Carousel	Lift	x	2

Figure 1.7: Groud-Gen AWESs. Summary of GG-AWESs.

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CHAPTER 1. AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY: STATE OF THE ART AND LITERATURE REVIEW

- Wings lift: achieved with a tethered flight of special gliders (Fig. 1.8.a) or frames with multiple wings (Fig. 1.8.b).
- Buoyancy and static lift: achieved with aerodynamically shaped aerostats filled with lighter-than-air gas (Fig. 1.8.c).
- Rotor thrust: achieved with the same turbines used for electrical power generation (Fig. 1.8.d).

Aircraft in Figs. 1.8.a and 1.8.b fly crosswind and harvest the relative wind, while those in Figs. 1.8.c and 1.8.d fly non-crosswind and harvest the absolute wind.

There is also one Fly-Gen (FG) concept that aims at exploiting high altitude wind energy not by using aerodynamic lift. It uses instead a rotating aerostat which exploits the Magnus effect [88, 89].

Figure 1.8: Different types of aircraft in Fly-Gen systems. (a) Plane with four turbines, design by Makani Power; (b) Aircraft composed by a frame of wings and turbines, design by Joby Energy; (c) Toroidal lifting aerostat with a wind turbine in the center, design by Altaeros Energies; (d) Static suspension quadrotor in autorotation, design by Sky WindPower.

1.4.2 Fly-Gen systems under development

This subsection provides a list of FG-AWESs which are summarized in Figs. 1.9 and 1.10.

Loyd's first mechanical concept

One of the most famous and old idea of exploiting wind energy using turbines on a kite, belongs to Loyd [7] who calculated that wind turbines installed on a crosswind flying kite could be able to generate up to 5 times the power produced by equivalent turbines installed on the ground. He also patented his idea in 1978 [90]. Loyd's concept foresees a reciprocating wind driven apparatus, similar to a multi propeller plane, with a plurality of ropes linking the aircraft to a ground station.

Makani Power

After about twenty-five years from Loyd's work, Makani Power Inc. [91] has started the development of its Airborne Wind Turbine (AWT) prototypes (as in Fig. 1.8.a). In nine years, Makani tested several AWESs concepts including Ground-Gen, single rope, multiple rope, movable ground station on rails, soft wings and rigid wings [92]. During these years, the company filed several patents where an electric and modern version of Loyd's idea has been enriched with a tether tension sensor [93], an aerodynamic cable [94], a bimodal flight [95], a radiator to cool the motors [96], an electromechanical joint [97] that has been invented to solve take-off and energy production issues. In the bimodal flight the AWT takes off with the wing plane in a vertical position, driven by propellers thrust. This flight mode is similar to a quadcopter flight and rotors on AWT are used as engines. Once all the rope length has been unwound, the AWT changes flight mode becoming a tethered flight airplane. In this second flight mode a circular flight path is powered by the wind itself and rotors on AWT are used as generators [98] to convert power from the wind. During this phase the cable length is fixed. In order to land, a new change of flight mode is performed, and the AWT lands as a quadcopter. Makani has developed and tested its 8 m, 20 kW demonstrator, called 'Wing 7' that showed the capability of fully automatic operations and power production. After these results, in early 2013 Makani was acquired by Google. Makani is currently developing a 600 kW prototype, 'the

M600'. The M600 AWT has eight turbines, each with five propeller blades, and has a wingspan of 28 m. The prototype is now undergoing testing [99]. After M600, Makani plans to produce an offshore commercial version of AWT with a nominal power of 5 MW featuring 6 turbines and a wingspan of 65 m.

Sant'Anna University

A novel fly-gen concept has recently been proposed by Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna of Pisa and University of Trento [100]. In this concept two fly-gen drones are tethered to each other at the wing-tip and follow each other in a circular path. This concept will be thoroughly explained in Chapters 4 and 5 of this thesis.

Joby Energy

Founded in 2008, Joby Energy Inc. [101] is another US company which is developing a FG-AWES similar to Makani. The main difference between Joby and Makani is that the tethered airborne vehicle is a multi-frame structure with embedded airfoils. Turbines are installed in the joints of the frame (as in Fig. 1.8.b). In Joby's concept, the system could be adapted to be assembled with modular components, constructed from multiple similar frames with turbines. The power generation method and the take-off and landing maneuvers are similar to those of Makani concept [102, 103]. Joby also patented an aerodynamic rope for its system [104]. Joby tested different small scale prototypes.

Altaeros Energies

Another project based on flying wind turbines in a stationary position has been developed by Altaeros Energies, a Massachusetts-based business led by MIT and Harvard alumni [105, 106, 107]. In this case, instead of using wings lift to fly, they use a ring shaped aerostat with a wind turbine installed in its interior (as in Fig. 1.8.c). The whole generator is lighter than the air, so the take-off and landing maneuvers are simplified, and the only remaining issue is the stabilization of the generator in the right position relative to the wind [108]. The aerostat is aerodynamically shaped so that the absolute wind generates lift that helps keeping a high angle of altitude together with the buoyancy force. After their energy production tests in 2012, Altaeros

is additionally working on multiple rotor generators with different lighter-than-air craft configurations.

Sky Windpower

Sky Windpower Inc. [109] proposed a different kind of tethered craft called Flying Electric Generator (FEG) (as in Fig. 1.8.d) which is similar to a large quadrotor with at least three identical rotors mounted on an airframe that is linked to a ground station with a rope having inner electrical cables [110, 111, 112, 113]. Their concept was the first AWES to be tested in 1986 at University of Sidney [16, 114]. Take-off and landing maneuvers are similar to those of Makani's and Joby's generators, but FEG operation as generator is different. Once it reaches the operational altitude, the frame is inclined at an adjustable controllable angle relative to the wind (up to 50 deg) and the rotors switch the functioning mode from motor to generator. At this inclined position, the rotors receive from their lower side a projection of the natural wind parallel to their axes. This projection of wind allows autorotation, thus generating both electricity and thrust. Electricity flows to and from the FEG through the cable. Sky Windpower tested two FEG prototypes. They claimed that a typical minimum wind speed for autorotation and energy generation is around 10 m/s at an operational altitude of 4600 m [115]. Unfortunately the company went out of business.

1.5 Crosswind flight: the key to large scale deployment

One of the most important reasons why AWESs are so attractive is their theoretical capability of achieving the megawatt scale with a single plant. For example in [16] a 34 MW plant is envisaged with a tethered Airbus A380, and many other publications present theoretical analyses with MW scale AWESs [116, 7, 52, 117]. This scalability feature is rare in renewable energies and is the key to successful commercial development.

With reference to the extraction principles explained in sections 1.3 and 1.4, this section gives an introduction to the modelling of crosswind flight, the most used flight mode in AWE. Modelling the principle of crosswind flight is a first necessary step towards the

CHAPTER 1. AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY: STATE OF THE ART AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Fly-Gen HAWECs				
General system description	Company/ University	Flying principle	Type	Energy generation system
Turbines on a tethered aircraft	Makani Power	Wings lift	Crosswind	6/8 turbines
	Joby Energy	Wings lift	Crosswind	Several turbines
Rotary drone system	Uni Sant'Anna	Wings lift	Crosswind	Several turbines
Tethered quadcopter	Sky Windpower	Rotors thrust	Non-crosswind	4 turbines
Turbine on a lighter than the air balloon	Altaeros Energies	Buoyancy	Non-crosswind	1 turbine
Magnus Effect turbine	Magenn Power	Buoyancy	Non-crosswind	Buoyant wind turbine

Figure 1.9: Fly-Gen AWESs. Summary of FG-AWESs.

Figure 1.10: Classification of AWESs. The different AWESs concepts are listed here as explained in section 1.2.

understanding of AWESs and their potential. A well known basic model is explained for the case of Ground-Gen and Fly-Gen crosswind AWESs.

Only crosswind generation is analyzed because it was demonstrated that it can provide a power one or two orders of magnitude higher than non-crosswind generation [7]. AWESs concepts that exploit crosswind power have therefore a strong competitive advantage over non-crosswind concepts in terms of available power and, therefore, in the economics of the whole system.

1.5.1 Crosswind GG-AWESs

This section explains how to compute the power output of a fixed-ground-station crosswind GG-AWES (Fig. 1.1.a) during the reel-out phase (Fig. 1.2.a). As already introduced in section 1.3, in GG-AWESs, the recovery phase (Fig. 1.2.b) represents an important factor in the computation of the average power output but, for simplicity, it is not considered in the following model. The expression of the maximum power, P , for crosswind Ground-Gen AWESs can be derived following the analytical optimization on the reel-out speed from [7] with the integrations from [118] and [119]. The hypotheses are: high equivalent aerodynamic efficiency, steady-state crosswind flight at zero azimuth angle from the wind direction, negligible inertia and gravity loads with respect to the aerodynamic forces.

With reference to Fig. 1.11, the velocities are sketched in blue and the forces are sketched in red. The velocity triangle at the kite is composed by the three components V_k , V_a and V_w^* : the aircraft speed, the apparent wind speed at the aircraft and the wind speed felt by the aircraft, respectively. V_r is the reel-out velocity (i.e. the velocity of the cable in the direction of its own axis) and V_w is the actual wind speed. V_w^* is defined as $V_w^* = V_w \cos \theta - V_r$ where θ is the angle between tether and wind direction (that corresponds to the angle of altitude in case of horizontal wind speed and aircraft at zero azimuth). T_k is the tether tension, L is the wing lifting force, D is the drag force (i.e. the drag force of the aircraft D_w plus the equivalent cable drag force D_{ce}). Notice that the velocity triangle and the force triangle are similar because of the force equilibrium at the aircraft, and therefore $V_k = V_w^* G$, where G is the equivalent aerodynamic efficiency [118], $G = L/D$ that is further explained in Eq. 1.2. Assuming $V_a \cong V_k$ (valid thanks to the hypothesis of high aerodynamic efficiency) and

CHAPTER 1. AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY: STATE OF THE ART AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Figure 1.11: Basic crosswind model. A simple and well known model for assessing the power output of a crosswind Ground-Gen AWES [7, 118, 119].

imposing the equilibrium at the aircraft, the tether tension is $T_k = \frac{1}{2}\rho V_w^{*2} G^2 C_L A$, where ρ is the air density. The power output can then be computed as $P_k = T_k V_r = \frac{1}{2}\rho (V_w \cos \theta - V_r)^2 V_r G^2 C_L A$. This expression can be optimized [7] in order to choose the reel-out speed that maximizes the power output, by setting $dP_k/dV_r = 0$. This simple optimization leads to the choice of optimal reel-out speed $V_{r,o} = 1/3 V_w \cos \theta$, and to the optimal power output, P

$$P = \frac{1}{2}\rho (V_w \cos \theta)^3 \frac{4}{27} G^2 C_L A \quad (1.1)$$

where A is the area of the kite and G is the equivalent aerodynamic efficiency, that is:

$$G = \frac{L}{D} = \frac{C_L}{C_{D_w} + C_{D_{ce}}} \quad (1.2)$$

where C_L and C_{D_w} are the wing lift and drag coefficients and $C_{D_{ce}}$ is equivalent cable drag coefficient. The expression of $C_{D_{ce}}$ can be computed by equating the energy dissipated by the distributed cable drag force to the energy that would be dissipated by a concentrated equivalent drag force located at the top end of the cable. This leads to $\int_0^r n D_c(x) V_c(x) dx = D_{ce} V_k$ where n is the number of cables, r is the length of each cable, $V_c(x)$ is the velocity in every point of the cable, $V_c = V_k x/r$, and D_c is the distributed cable drag, $D_c = \frac{1}{2}\rho V_c^2 d C_\perp$ where d is the cable diameter and C_\perp is the perpendicular cable drag coefficient. The expression for the equivalent cable drag coefficient is therefore:

$$C_{D_{ce}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}\rho V_k^2 \frac{1}{4} C_\perp n r d}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V_k^2 A} = \frac{C_\perp n r d}{4A} \quad (1.3)$$

1.5.2 Crosswind FG-AWESs

This section explains how to compute the power output of a crosswind FG-AWES (Fig. 1.1.b) during the generation phase. As already introduced in section 1.4, unlike crosswind GG-AWESs, crosswind FG-AWESs have the advantage of being able to produce power without the need of a duty cycle for the recovery phase.

Similarly to what has already been done in section 1.5.1, the expression of the available crosswind power, P , for Fly-Gen AWESs can be derived following the analytical optimization on the flying generator drag from [7] with the integrations from [118] and [119].

Figure 1.12: Basic crosswind model. A simple and well known model for assessing the power output of a crosswind Fly-Gen AWES [7, 118, 119].

With reference to Fig. 1.12, using the assumptions and the symbols defined in section 1.5.1, it is possible to compute the maximum power, P , for crosswind Fly-Gen AWESs by combining three expressions: the drag force from the flying generators $D_g = \frac{1}{2}\rho V_a^2 C_{D_g} A$, the apparent wind velocity $V_a = (V_w \cos \theta) C_L / (C_D + C_{D_g})$ where $C_D = C_{D_w} + C_{D_{ce}}$, and the generators power $P_g = D_g V_a$. Therefore $P_g = \frac{1}{2}\rho V_w^3 A (C_L^3 C_{D_g}) / (C_D + C_{D_g})^3$. A simple optimization $dP_g/dC_{D_g} = 0$ leads to the maximum value of power:

$$P = \frac{1}{2}\rho (V_w \cos \theta)^3 \frac{4}{27} G^2 C_L A \quad (1.4)$$

that is the same of the Ground-Gen case and occurs when the drag of the flying generators is chosen to be $C_{D_g} = C_D/2$. It is worth noticing that the maximum power expressed in Eq. 1.4 does not take into account the conservation of momentum and a more rigorous procedure would yield a slightly lower value of P [120]. However, Eq. 1.4 correctly defines the upper bound for the maximum power and is useful for first assessments.

1.6 Discussion

This section provides a brief discussion on some techno-economic issues and topics that are considered relevant with respect to the current development, trends, and future roadmap of AWESs.

1.6.1 Effect of flying mass

In all AWESs, increasing the flying mass decreases the tension of the cables. Since Ground-Gen systems rely on cable tension to generate electricity, a higher mass of the aircraft and/or cables decreases the energy production [119] and should not be neglected when modelling [121]. On the contrary, increasing the flying mass in Fly-Gen systems does not affect the energy production even though it still reduces the tension of the cable. Indeed, as a first approximation, the basic equations of Fly-Gen power production do not change if the aircraft/cable mass is included and this is also supported by experimental data [120].

1.6.2 Rigid vs Soft Wings

A question faced by many companies and research groups is whether rigid wings are better or worse than soft wings. On the plus side for soft wings there are: crash-free tests and lower weight (therefore higher power) because of the inherent tensile structure. Conversely, rigid wings have better aerodynamic efficiency (therefore higher power) and they do not share the durability issues of soft wings mentioned in section 1.3. It is unclear whether one of the two solutions will win over the other, but a trend is clearly visible in the AWE community: even though a lot of academic research is still being carried out on soft wings [34], more and more companies are switching from soft to rigid wings [122] (see Fig. 1.10).

1.6.3 Take-off and landing challenge

Starting and stopping energy production requires special take-off and landing maneuvers as explained in sections 1.3 and 1.4. These are the most difficult to automate and are requiring a lot of research in private companies and academic laboratories [32, 40, 72].

1.6.4 Optimal altitude

Another interesting question is how much is the optimal flight altitude, i.e. how much are the optimal cable length and elevation angle that maximize the power output. Increasing the altitude allows to reach more powerful winds, but, at the same time, increasing the cable length or the elevation angle reduces the power output according to Eqs. 1.1-1.4. Considering a standard wind shear profile, the optimal flight altitude is found to be the minimum that is practically achievable [120, 123]. However, results greatly change depending on the hypotheses and, for example, a reduction in cables drag might lead to optimal flight altitudes around 1000 meters [123]. More detailed and location-specific analyses could be therefore useful to define an optimal flight altitude. Nowadays, many AWE companies are aiming at exploiting low altitude winds with the minimum flight altitude set by safety concerns. Only a few companies and academic institutions are still trying to reach high altitudes.

1.6.5 Angle of attack control

As shown in Eq. 1.1, the aerodynamics of the system is very important to the power production. A first aerodynamic design should maximize the value $G^2 C_L$.

A bridle system might be used to fix an incidence angle so that $G^2 C_L$ is fixed at an optimal angle of attack. But it is easy to show that an active control of the angle of attack is essential during the production phase of Ground-Gen or Fly-Gen devices.

A variation of the angle of attack can be induced by a change in the tether sag or in the velocity triangle. As for the tether sag, it is possible to compute the variation of the nominal angle of attack thanks to the model provided in [124]. Depending on the value of the design parameters, the model would give a numerical value between 7 deg and 11 deg for a large scale AWES. As regards the velocity triangle, assuming controlled constant tether force (a common constraint in a real power curve [120, 33]) and computing the effect of a different absolute wind speed on the angle of attack with a simple velocity triangle, a variation of about 3.5 deg or 4 deg can be reasonably obtained.

Such variations of the angle of attack can decrease substantially the power output or even make the flight impossible. For example, using the values of the aerodynamic coefficients for an airfoil specifi-

cally optimized for AWESs [125], a steady state variation in the angle of attack of just ± 2 deg can lead to a decrease in power output between 5% and 42% with respect to the optimal angle of attack. Real time control of the angle of attack in current AWESs prototypes from Ampyx and Makani [36, 120] limits the angle of attack variation to ± 2 deg in a real flight time history.

1.6.6 Cables

Cables for AWESs are usually made of Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene (UHMWPE), a relatively low-cost material with excellent mechanical properties [126] even though many different materials are being used and studied [127]. The cables can be 1, 2 or 3 and in some concepts they carry electricity for power generation or just for on-board actuation. Each of these choices has advantages and disadvantages, and, at the present time, any prediction about the best tethering system would be highly speculative. The tethers also represent a known issue in the AWE community [128] because of wear, maintenance and aerodynamic drag.

Polynomial curvature

It is worth noticing that section 1.5 describes a steady state flight with straight cables under known tension, but for very long cables this model is not accurate. For example, removing the straight cable hypothesis gives a fourth order polynomial shape function [124] for cables in steady state flight. The curvature is acceptable for short round cables ($C_{\perp} = 1$ and r up to 1 km), while it is highly undesirable with extremely long round cables (e.g. $r = 10$ km). Reducing the cable aerodynamic drag to 0.2 allows reasonable curvatures with lengths of several kilometers (e.g. $r = 5$ km).

Unsteady analysis

Very long cables should be studied removing also the steady state hypothesis in order to consider the fact that, in unsteady flight, the lower part of the cables could reasonably move less than in steady state flight, thus dissipating less energy.

Tethers electrostatic behavior

Some concerns have been raised regarding the behavior of tethers in atmospheric environment [129]. An analysis performed on dry and wet polyethylene ropes without inner conductors [19] shows that non-conductive tethers will not trigger a flashover in typical static electric fields of thunder clouds, however non-conductive tethers are very likely to trigger a flashover when subjected to impulsive electric fields produced by lightnings. It is reasonable to say that AWESs will not work during thunderstorms and that lightnings should not be an issue. However, an analysis regarding the electrical atmospheric behavior of tethers with inner conductors could be useful to understand the worst atmospheric conditions to which conductive tethers might be exposed.

Aerodynamic drag opportunities

A reduction in the cable drag coefficient would likely lead to an increase in power output by two or three times thanks to better aerodynamic efficiency, increased flight speed and higher operational altitude [123]. Several patents have been filed to address this issue [94, 104, 50] even though the reduction of cable drag by means of e.g. fairing or streamlined cross-sections has not been experimentally demonstrated yet. Because of the potential advantages, funding opportunities might be available for concepts in aerodynamic drag reduction [130].

Nearly zero cable drag

As regards the aerodynamic cable drag, two patented concepts might provide an important improvement in the long term by setting to zero the aerodynamic drag for the majority of the length. They are worth being mentioned even though no prototype already exists for both of them. The first appeared in the very first patent about high altitude wind energy in 1976 [131] and described the so called ‘dancing planes’ concepts. Two Fly-Gen turbines are held by a single cable, the top part of which splits into two. Each turbine is tethered to one of these ends and follows a circular trajectory so that only the two top parts of the cable fly crosswind through the air and the main single cable stands still under balanced tensions. Several studies already exist for this promising concept [132, 133]. The second [134]

describes a ‘multi-tether’ AWES where three cables are deployed from three different ground stations and are eventually connected to each other in their top end. A single tether connects the top end of the three cables to one kite that is then geometrically free to fly crosswind within a certain solid angle without moving the three lower cables but only changing their inner tension. The further the ground stations are spaced apart, the larger is the allowable solid angle. For both of these concepts the result is the same: high altitude crosswind flight is achieved with the longest part of the cables completely fixed in space, thus allowing to reach winds at very high altitude with a relatively short dissipative cable length.

1.6.7 Business opportunities

To date, several tens of millions dollars have been spent for the development of AWESs, which is a relatively low amount of money, especially if one considers the scale of the potential market and the physical fundamentals of AWE technology. The major financial contributions came, so far, by big companies usually involved in the energy market [130]. The community is growing both in terms of patents and in terms of scientific research [135]. But still, there is no product to sell and the majority of the companies that are trying to find a market fit are now focusing on off-grid markets and remote locations where satisfying a market need can be easier at first [122].

1.7 Conclusions

High altitude wind energy is currently a very promising resource for the sustainable production of electrical energy. The amount of power and the large availability of winds that blow between 300 and 10000 meters from the ground suggest that AWESs represent an important emerging renewable energy technology. In the last decade, several companies entered in the business of AWESs, patenting diverse principles and technical solutions for their implementation. In this extremely various scenario, this chapter attempts to give a picture of the current status of the developed technologies in terms of different concepts, systems and trends. In particular, all existing AWESs have been briefly presented and classified. The basic generation principles have been explained, together with very basic theoretical estimations of power production that could provide the reader

CHAPTER 1. AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY: STATE OF THE ART AND LITERATURE REVIEW

with a perception on which and how crucial parameters influence the performance of an AWES. In the next years, a rapid acceleration of research and development is expected in the airborne wind energy sector. Several prototypes that are currently under investigation will be completed and tested.

*CHAPTER 1. AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY: STATE OF THE
ART AND LITERATURE REVIEW*

Chapter 2

Simplified model of offshore airborne wind energy converters

As introduced in Chapter 1, at several thousand meters above sea level, jet streams currents can reach power densities as high as 15 kW/m^2 (i. e. from 50 to 100 times more powerful than at 100 m altitude) with typical availability of more than 30%.

AWESs appear exceptionally promising from the point of view of: 1) increased power production, because of the high power density and high capacity factors and 2) reduced structural mass (10 to 50 times lighter than conventional wind turbines), thanks to the tensile loading conditions.

On the downside, current AWESs require large airspace, they can raise safety issues, and might face NIMBY effect. For these reasons, deep-offshore floating AWESs may take advantage of both the lightweight design of AWESs and the huge availability of low-cost sites for the installation of floating structures. This chapter presents a preliminary investigation on the feasibility and on fundamental design issues of offshore AWESs. The dynamics of an offshore floating AWES has been investigated with a model that couples the aircraft steady state crosswind model with 1 degree of freedom hydrodynamics of a floating platform held in place by a catenary mooring line. The possibility of extracting combined wind-wave power has been

investigated.

Section 2.1 is an introduction to modelling of offshore AWESs. Section 2.2 introduces a simple dynamic model for an offshore pumping AWES with catenary mooring. In Section 2.3, a case study is analysed in order to address first design issues and to estimate the advantage that an offshore AWES could obtain by exploiting the available wave energy in addition to that of wind.

2.1 Offshore AWES

The study and development of offshore AWESs combine different fields of engineering. They are composed of a flying wing (or kite) linked with a tether to a floating platform, which in turn is anchored to the seabed by a mooring system as shown in Fig. 2.1. All these subsystems involve complex dynamics and can be studied with different degrees of accuracy.

Figure 2.1: Schematic layout of an offshore Airborne Wind Energy Converter. The four subsystems composing an offshore AWES are shown, i.e. wing, tether, floating platform and mooring system. The forces transmitted among the chain of components are indicated in the block diagram.

Depending on where the generators are placed, two types of AWESs can be envisioned:

- ‘Float-gen’ (floating equivalent of ground-gen) in case the generators are placed on the floating platform.
- ‘Fly-gen’ in case the generators are placed on board the wing.

In float-gen systems, the generation type is traction based and the aircraft performs the pumping cycle. Electricity is generated during the reel-out phase of the cycle when the aircraft generates significant pull and the cables are reeled out from the drums on which they are wound. Then comes the reel-in phase in which the aircraft is controlled in order to generate less tension and the cables are reeled back in. Reeling-in of cables is achieved with the aircraft in a depowered configuration. For current experimental systems, the reel-in phase requires nearly one third of the power produced during the reel-out phase [62, 136] but there are several concepts that aim at reducing substantially this power requirement [137].

On the other hand, fly-gen systems extract electricity from on board wind turbines which rotate fast and continuously. With respect to float-gen systems, they can have higher global electrical efficiencies and 100% duty-cycle efficiency (they are not subjected to reel-out reel-in cycles). However, the transmission of electricity from the wing to the floating platform adds a lot more complexity and requires larger-sized cables, thus increasing the aerodynamic drag, which has a detrimental effect on crosswind power output [16]. In this work float-gen systems are analysed.

The aerodynamics of the AWES can be investigated through different models; for example it can be described by a simple algebraic formula for quick power assessment [119], or can be modelled with a first order non linear dynamic system for controller design [138], or can be thoroughly simulated to investigate how a kite deforms during flight manoeuvres [139]. Also the cable dynamics can be taken into account when modelling the aircraft forces [140, 124].

In order to model the displacement of the floating platform and to estimate its effect on the energy production, it is necessary to investigate the hydrodynamics of the system. The hydrodynamics of floating bodies involve highly non-linear phenomena and turbulent flows. Reasonable predictions and simulations can be obtained by means of computationally intensive Computational Fluid Dynamic

(CFD) analyses. However, several simplified methods are commonly employed in marine engineering to efficiently perform preliminary design iterations [141, 142, 143].

The mooring system cannot be neglected when modelling an offshore AWES, even though it is only needed to hold the generator in place. Several kinds of mooring systems are available and extensive literature, patents and regulations exist for oil drilling platforms and naval engineering [144, 145]. Mooring systems are known to be difficult to model due to their inherent non-linearity and sophisticated fluid structure interaction. For example, simple slack mooring systems have a non linear stiffness that changes significantly with the applied load and other design criteria [146]. In offshore oil platforms, their dynamics are usually deemed to be negligible for non-extreme events. However, it is important to notice that mooring equipment could be the most costly subsystem of a floating platform and could affect substantially the global business plan [147].

In this chapter, a preliminary study of offshore AWESs is performed thanks to a simplified model with minimum complexity that allows analysis of the coupling of two main systems, namely a moored floating platform and an airborne device. This model has the important advantage of being computationally fast and easy to use. It is therefore suitable for qualitative analyses and first design iterations. In particular, the next section proposes a model of a 1 Degree of Freedom (DoF) heaving platform coupled with a steady state aerodynamic model of a generic wing flying in the crosswind direction.

The study only focuses on an AWES in operational conditions, during energy production phase. Although relevant, other aspects and operating modes, such as launching/landing/emergency manoeuvres, optimal control, etc. are not discussed [8].

2.2 Model

This section describes the simple model shown in Fig. 2.1 that has been taken as reference for the numerical study provided in the following section.

2.2.1 Hydrodynamic model

The offshore floating platform is modelled as a heaving rigid body having only 1 DoF. This approximation, often assumed in the preliminary design phases of buoy-like Wave Energy Converters (WECs) [148], limits the capability and accuracy of the model. However, this approach is very useful to provide a first (quick) insight into the global behaviour of the floating dynamic system.

Figure 2.2: Model of the floating platform. The offshore platform is modelled as a heaving floating rigid body having only 1 DoF. The horizontal components of the mooring force T_m and the aircraft force T_k are equal.

The forces acting on the system are shown in Fig. 2.2. Under these assumptions, the vertical equilibrium of the platform yields

$$M\ddot{z}(t) = f_h(t) + f_g + f_m(t) + f_k(t) \quad (2.1)$$

where z is the heaving coordinate and M is the nominal mass, i.e. the actual mass of the floating platform. On the right-hand side of the equation, there are the time-varying forces acting on the platform: f_h are the hydrodynamic forces on the hull, f_g is the gravity force, f_m and f_k are respectively the contributions of the traction forces of the mooring system and of the tethered aircraft.

Platform

The hydrodynamic force f_h represents the vertical component of the resultant of pressure and shear forces on the wet surface of the hull. It is generally calculated through an integral equation which is not

easy to compute and several methods exist for its evaluation, such as CFD, analytical models or experimental measures. However, assuming inviscid and irrotational fluids subjected to small amplitude wave fields, linear wave theory can be applied to provide a reasonable estimate that is valid in non-extreme events. In particular, the hydrodynamic force on the hull can be described as the sum of three terms [149, 150]:

$$f_h(t) = f_b(t) + f_r(t) + f_e(t) \quad (2.2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f_b(t) &= -k_b z(t) - f_{b0} \\ f_r(t) &= -M_\infty \ddot{z} - \int_0^t k_r(t-\tau) \dot{z}(\tau) d\tau \\ f_e(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^n F_{wi} \sin(\omega_i t + \phi_i). \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

In Eq. 2.2, f_b is the buoyancy force and it is composed by a constant term f_{b0} plus an elastic contribution with stiffness k_b . f_r is the radiation force that takes into account the the kinetic and dissipative contributions of the motion of the water particles induced by the platform oscillations. It comprises an inertial contribution with constant mass, M_∞ , plus a convolution integral term which depends on the past oscillations of the platform. The function $k_r(t-\tau)$ is called the ‘memory kernel’, or radiation impulse response function. In particular, k_r is zero when its argument is lower than zero in such a way so as to weight only the present and past values of the heave velocity in the convolution operation. f_e is the excitation force and models the forces that are exerted on a fixed body by the waves. In the most general case of irregular sea, f_e is expressed as a Fourier series where ω_i are the frequencies of the waves, while F_{wi} and ϕ_i are the amplitudes and phases of the wave forces. As shown by Eqs. 2.1 and 2.2, the constant terms f_{b0} and f_g can be balanced if a proper choice of the heave coordinate z is made.

Mooring

The mooring system is difficult to model and its effect on the dynamics of the floating platform significantly depends on the design criteria. The mooring system chosen in this analysis is composed by

a single catenary line with a gravity anchor because of its simplicity and suitability for WECs [145]. Assuming, as above, linear wave theory, the catenary line dynamics are reduced to an equivalent mass, damping and stiffness, which are then added to the platform equation of motion as described in [151].

The expression for the mooring force is

$$f_m = -M_m \ddot{z} - B_m \dot{z} - k_m z \quad (2.4)$$

where M_m , B_m , k_m are the mooring linearised coefficients: equivalent mass, damping and stiffness respectively. M_m is not simply the nominal mooring mass, but includes also the added mass of water displaced by the mooring line and takes into account the fact that the mooring line does not move uniformly along its length.

2.2.2 Aerodynamic model

The aircraft model that is assumed in this chapter is based on the work done in [7]. In addition, we have also taken into account the angle of altitude θ (see Fig. 2.3) and the effects of the cables aerodynamic drag as in [119] and [118], respectively. In short, the basic assumptions are:

- flight at constant altitude θ and zero azimuth angle with respect to the wind direction¹;
- negligible inertia and gravity forces of the aircraft with respect to the aerodynamic loads;
- high equivalent aerodynamic efficiency;
- therefore, steady state flight in crosswind direction is assumed.

These approximations are typically adopted in the literature of AWESs and are commonly used for first design iterations, even though experimental validations are challenging and the results are scattered [120]. This first model allows fast analytical computations and is therefore very useful for our preliminary assessment of offshore AWESs.

¹Notice that this last hypothesis defines a theoretical horizontal flight which describes only the instant of time when the aircraft crosses the zero azimuth. In order to imagine an equivalent more realistic flight path that satisfies this requirement, one should think to a semi-circular flight path around the wind direction such that the angular distance of the aircraft from the wind direction is kept constant. A good definition of such distance is given in [138].

Figure 2.3: AWES aerodynamic model The balloon shows the aerodynamic equilibrium at the kite in the tether reference system.

With reference to Fig. 2.3, it is possible to derive the equations that govern the aircraft dynamics.

In particular, assuming the following notation: V_k is the absolute aircraft speed, V_a is the apparent wind speed, V_w is the actual wind speed, V_c is the velocity of the cable in the direction its own axis, T_k is the tether traction force, L is the aircraft lift force, D_{eq} is the equivalent drag force (i.e the drag force of the aircraft plus the equivalent cable drag force acting on the aircraft), and V_w^* is the wind speed felt by the aircraft defined as

$$V_w^* = V_w \cos \theta - V_c. \quad (2.5)$$

Notice that, with reference to Fig. 2.3, the force equilibrium at the aircraft makes the velocity triangle and the force triangle similar, thus yielding

$$V_k = E_{eq} V_w^*. \quad (2.6)$$

The equivalent aerodynamic efficiency takes account of the cables aerodynamic drag and can be derived by computing the energy dissipated by the distributed cable drag and reads as

$$E_{eq} = \frac{C_L}{C_D + \frac{C_{\perp} n_c r_c d_c}{4A}} = \frac{L}{D_{eq}} \quad (2.7)$$

where C_L and C_D are the lift and drag coefficients of the aircraft, C_\perp is the drag coefficient of the cable with respect to a flow perpendicular to its axis, n_c is the number of cables, r_c is the length of each cable, d_c is the cable diameter, A is the area of the aircraft, the same area to which C_L and C_D are referred.

Assuming $V_a \cong V_k$ (valid for a wing with high aerodynamic efficiency) and imposing the equilibrium of the aircraft, it is then possible to calculate the traction force as

$$T_k = \frac{1}{2} \rho_a V_w^{*2} E_{eq}^2 C_L A. \quad (2.8)$$

2.2.3 Integrated model

In an offshore AWES, the platform and the aircraft model are coupled. More specifically, the cable speed V_c is given by the sum of two velocities

$$V_c = V_r + \dot{z} \sin \theta \quad (2.9)$$

where V_r , is the cables reel-out velocity as seen by the floating platform. Notice that it is assumed that the motion of the platform will have an impact on the aircraft traction force only if the altitude θ is greater than zero. Moreover, since the cables length is much larger than the platform oscillations, the motion of the platform is always assumed to have no impact on the altitude θ .

Under this hypothesis, the equations that describe the behaviour the 1 DoF offshore AWES read as

$$\begin{aligned} (M + M_\infty + M_m) \ddot{z} + \int_0^t k_r(t - \tau) \dot{z}(\tau) d\tau + B_m \dot{z} + (k_b + k_m) z \\ = \sum_{i=1}^n F_{wi} \sin(\omega_i t + \phi_i) + T_k \sin \theta \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

$$V_r = V_w \cos \theta - \dot{z} \sin \theta - \sqrt{\frac{T_k}{\frac{1}{2} \rho_a E_{eq}^2 C_L A}} \quad (2.11)$$

$$P = T_k V_r \quad (2.12)$$

Eq. 2.10 is the platform equation that defines the vertical motion of the floating structure. Eq. 2.11 is the winch equation that couples

the platform dynamics with the kite model and defines the cables reel out velocity as seen by the winches. It is given by the combination of equations 2.5, 2.8 and 2.9. Eq. 2.12 is the power equation that defines the instantaneous available power to the alternators, P as the product between the tether tension, T_k , and the cables reel-out velocity as seen by a reference system that is fixed on the platform, V_r .

2.2.4 Control

The tether force, T_k , can be controlled thanks to the drums reeling velocity V_r . For example, if the cables are reeling-in, the wind speed felt by the aircraft V_w^* increases, thus increasing the flight speed and the aerodynamic lift. It is easy to understand that a controller can decouple the buoy from the aircraft by imposing an appropriate velocity to the drums in order to cancel the effect of the buoy motion on the cable speed V_c .

However, it also is possible to envisage a more complex controller that makes it possible to harvest energy, not only from wind, but also from waves without any changes in system architecture. Specifically, a suitable control on the force T_k can be conceived in order to exert an oscillating force on the platform and to extract energy from waves by damping its heaving motion. In order to assess this potential improvement in the power output, the average combined wind-wave power output of the floating AWES has to be computed. In the following, before analysing the case of combined wind-wave power, the formulations for estimating the maximum wind-only and wave-only power extraction are provided.

Wind-only optimal power output

For the well known case of a ground based pumping AWES, Eqs. 2.11 and 2.12 can be simplified by fixing the heave coordinate, $z(t)=0$.

The optimal reel out speed is known to be $V_{r0} = 1/3 V_w \cos \theta$ [7]. In such a case, the optimal aircraft tether force of Eq. 2.8 is constant:

$$T_k = T_{k0}$$

where $T_{k0} = 1/2 \rho_a V_w^2 4/9 E_{eq}^2 C_L A \cos^2 \theta$ and generates the *nominal aircraft power*, $P_0 = 1/2 \rho_a V_w^3 4/27 E_{eq}^2 C_L A \cos^3 \theta$.

Wave-only optimal power output

Eq. 2.10 is the equation of motion of a generic moored WEC, where $T_k \sin \theta$ corresponds to a general force of an external Power Take Off (PTO) unit, that can be externally controlled to introduce an additional mechanical impedance on the platform heaving motion and thereby extracting power from the waves.

Assuming regular waves, as typically made in preliminary analyses of WEC concepts [152], the wave force on the platform reads as $f_e = F_w \sin(\omega t)$ and then the integral term of Eq. 2.10 can be simplified in

$$\int_0^t k_r(t - \tau) \dot{z}(\tau) d\tau = (M_{\text{add}}(\omega) - M_\infty) \ddot{z}(t) + B_r(\omega) \dot{z}(t) \quad (2.13)$$

where $B_r(\omega)$ is the radiation damping coefficient, $M_{\text{add}}(\omega)$ is the added mass due to the water motion around the platform, both depending on the oscillation frequency ω . M_∞ is the limit of the added mass $M_{\text{add}}(\omega)$ as ω approaches infinity. Equation 2.13 also allows a fast computation of an analytical steady state solution of Eq. 2.10.

It is possible to demonstrate that the optimal wave-only power output is achieved by regulating the traction force according to the following linear relation:

$$T_k = -r_g \dot{z}(t) - s_g z(t)$$

where the values of r_g and s_g need to be properly selected according to the AWES hydrodynamic parameters [153].

2.2.5 Combined wind-wave power output

In order to investigate the possibility of extracting combined wind-wave power output, the tether force is then assumed to be a combination of a constant force plus a second component proportional to z and a third proportional to \dot{z} . The controller equation assumes the following form

$$T_k = cT_{k0} - r_g \dot{z}(t) - s_g z(t). \quad (2.14)$$

This control strategy introduces a superimposed alternate motion of the cables, due to the intrinsic relation between traction force and kite velocity (given by Eq. 2.8). This means that the aerodynamically-optimal reel out speed (given in [7]) cannot be followed. Therefore, the introduction of such a controller is reducing

the amount of extracted wind power with respect to the ideal maximum. In order to evaluate if the global balance is positive, having the benefit from the additional power from waves overcoming the losses from wind, the global wind-wave power output of the floating AWES has to be computed. Using Eqs. 2.10, 2.11, 2.12 and 2.14, simplifying the convolution integral with Eq. 2.13 and integrating on the wave period T_w , it is possible to derive the analytical expression for the steady state average power output of the combined wind-wave generation, P_{ww} .

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{ww} = & cT_{k0}V_w \cos \theta - \frac{1}{T_w} \int_0^{T_w} cT_{k0}C(t) dt + \frac{1}{2}z_1^2\omega^2r_g \sin \theta \\
 & + \frac{1}{T_w} \int_0^{T_w} \dot{z}(t)r_gC(t) dt + \frac{1}{T_w} \int_0^{T_w} z(t)s_gC(t) dt
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

with

$$C(t) = \sqrt{\frac{cT_{k0} - r_g\dot{z}(t) - s_gz(t)}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_a E_{eq}^2 C_L A}} \tag{2.16}$$

The solution for the dynamics of the platform reads as

$$\begin{aligned}
 z(t) &= z_1 \sin(\omega t + \phi_z) \\
 \dot{z}(t) &= \omega z_1 \cos(\omega t + \phi_z)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.17}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
 z_1 &= \frac{F_w}{\sqrt{(k - \omega^2 m)^2 + \omega^2 r^2}} \\
 \phi_z &= -\arctan\left(\frac{\omega r}{k - \omega^2 m}\right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.18}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 m &= M + M_{add}(\omega) + M_m \\
 r &= B_r + B_m + r_g \sin \theta \\
 k &= k_b + k_m + s_g \sin \theta
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.19}$$

If r_g and s_g are zero, then the maximum P_{ww} is achieved with $c = 1$ and corresponds to the maximum wind-only power, P_0 . This means, as we could easily guess, that an AWES placed on a floating platform is capable of generating at least the same power as if it were fixed on the ground exposed to the same absolute wind. However, Eq. 2.15 can be numerically maximised in order to find the optimal values of the controller parameters and verify if it is possible to achieve a power output P_{ww} higher than P_0 .

2.3 Case study

In this section, the model provided in section 2.2 is implemented in a numerical case study.

2.3.1 Geometry

The geometry of the platform is assumed to be of cylindrical shape and to be moored with a single line catenary mooring. A wide range of geometries and sea states have been investigated, but we report only the few most significant results whose details are provided in Fig. 2.4 and Tables 2.1, 2.2, 2.3.

Figure 2.4: Platform and aircraft dimensions The picture shows the dimensions of platforms and aircraft properly scaled. The draft is the submerged height and is chosen to be equal to 1.88 times the radius.

*CHAPTER 2. SIMPLIFIED MODEL OF OFFSHORE
AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY CONVERTERS*

Aircraft Data	Unit		
Aerodynamic efficiency E_{eq}	10		
Lift coefficient C_L	0.65		
Air density ρ_a	1.225		kg/m ³
Flight elevation angle θ	45		deg
Wind speed V_w	12		m/s
	Small	Big	
Area A	150	600	m ²
Nominal tension T_{k0}	191	764	kN
Nominal power P_0	0.54	2.16	MW

Table 2.1: Aircraft data.

Platform Data	Small	Medium	Big	Unit
Diameter D_b	5	10	15	m
Draft	4.7	9.4	14.1	m
Nominal displacement	95	760	2566	ton
Added mass M_∞	31	249	842	ton
Buoyancy stiffness k_b	198	793	1784	kN/m
Natural period (ca.)	5.2	7.1	8.6	sec

Table 2.2: Platform data.

Mooring Data	Unit		
Water depth	50		m
Length	350		m
Chain diameter	64		mm
Linear mass in air	90		kg/m
	Small	Big	
	air- craft	air- craft	
Equivalent mass M_m	33.1	53.2	ton
Equivalent damping B_m	17954	35084	N/(m/s)
Equivalent stiffness k_m	5940	11331	N/m

Table 2.3: Single line inelastic catenary mooring data. The equivalent mechanical properties change significantly with the loading condition.

2.3.2 Computation of the hydrodynamic coefficients

For all the considered cases, the hydrodynamic coefficients M_∞ , M_{add} , B_r , F_w , M_m , B_m , k_m were computed for the chosen geometries with a standard linear radiation-diffraction software (WAMIT). The mooring coefficients were taken from [151] and dimensioned in such a way to balance the horizontal forces of the kite cable.

The convolution integral found in Eq. 2.10 can be solved in a computationally efficient manner by approximating it with a system of differential equations. Sufficient accuracy can be achieved with a system of the third order or higher [154]. In this case, a fourth order linear system is used and its coefficients were computed by using M_∞ , $M_{\text{add}}(\omega)$ and $B_r(\omega)$.

The static buoyancy stiffness k_b can be easily computed as the product of water density, gravity acceleration, and waterplane area $\rho_w g \pi D_b^2 / 4$, where D_b is the platform diameter.

2.3.3 Results

A numerical parametric study of Eq. 2.15 in eight different sea states was performed for each geometry. The goal was to maximize the power output P_{ww} and the results are shown in Fig. 2.5.

In Fig. 2.5 each coloured square has two numbers. The first number (without brackets) is the wave power potential improvement and is the ratio P_w/P_0 where P_w is the nominal wave power that reaches the floating platform computed by multiplying the linear wave power density², P_{w1} , by the platform diameter D_b .

The second number (within brackets) is the wind-wave power actual improvement and is computed as $(P_{\text{ww}} - P_0)/P_0$. Finally the colormap of the cells represents how much of the wave potential is exploited (in addition to the wind potential); it is given by the ratio between the second and the first number and is then $(P_{\text{ww}} - P_0)/P_w$.

The picture also shows the values of the buoy resonance period $T_b = \frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{k/m}}$ and the lift safety η . The lift safety is the nominal mass of the platform plus the mooring line, divided by the maximum steady state aircraft tension. If an offshore wind-only AWES is to be built, it is reasonable to expect $\eta > 1.5$.

²The linear wave power density (W/m) in deep water can be computed with the formula $P_{w1} = \frac{\rho_w g^2 T_w H_w^2}{32\pi}$ where H_w is the wave peak-to-peak amplitude.

CHAPTER 2. SIMPLIFIED MODEL OF OFFSHORE
AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY CONVERTERS

Figure 2.5: Potential wave power advantage on different offshore geometries Each coloured square shows two numbers: the first (without brackets) is the incident wave power on the hull of the AWES as a percentage of the nominal wind-only power, the second (within brackets) is the actual improvement on the power output that is obtained with wind-wave generation instead of wind-only generation. The background colour of the cell represents the ratio between the second and the first number thus giving a visual representation of the ability to exploit the potential advantage. The cells with actual improvement higher than 5 % are marked in red. Resonant sea states are marked in green. An 'x' or a check mark indicates whether the platform is oversized or not with respect to a wind-only generator. Systems with not oversized platforms experience the lowest performance improvements.

2.3.4 Small aircraft - Small platform

In Fig. 2.5A, the platform is well dimensioned (η around 5 or 6), meaning that more than 5 times the nominal aircraft pull is needed to lift the whole system out of the water. The potential wave power advantage ranges anywhere between 2.6 % and 99.7 % However, the improvement that is actually achieved by configuration A is at most 2.0 % even in the resonant sea states (inside the green box) where T_w is roughly equal to T_b .

2.3.5 Small aircraft - Medium platform

If the buoy size is increased, Fig. 2.5B, η increases, meaning that the buoy is heavy when compared to the aircraft force. If compared to case A, the platform resonates with sea states that carry a larger amount of wave power (potential advantage up to 80 % in B5), however the best power output is achieved in B4 (aircraft-buoy combination B, sea state n. 4) where the improvement is only 10.8 % with respect to wind-only generation. Sea state data for case A2 and B4 are shown in Table 2.4.

Sea state B5 is marked by a * and is white. It has a * because the platform oscillations are large comparing to its own dimensions thus reducing the reliability of results. When such oscillations are considered too large, the cell is also white-filled and the advantage is set to zero ($s_g = r_g = 0$). In this case the aircraft can be controlled at constant nominal tension yielding the wind-only power $P_{ww} = P_0$.

2.3.6 Small aircraft - Big platform

If the buoy is enlarged even more, Fig. 2.5C, the advantage increases to 17.3 % at the cost of having a huge platform with respect to the wind-only needs ($\eta > 110$).

2.3.7 Big aircraft

Increasing the aircraft size does not change the results discussed for the small aircraft. Since the aircraft area increased by a factor 4, the potential advantages are much smaller (1/4) than for the small aircraft. Moreover, in case D the platform could be lifted out of water by peak forces.

2.3.8 Discussion

The fact that WECs performance are optimal only when they resonate with the sea state explains why all the cells outside the green boxes (i.e. non resonating working conditions) are coloured in blue (i.e. the obtained improvement is low). However, Fig. 2.5 clearly shows that the potential advantage of having a combined wind-wave system instead of a wind-only generator does not provide major benefits in most of the circumstances, even inside the green boxes. This can be explained as follows. It is possible to see from Eqs. 2.5, 2.9, 2.10, 2.11 and 2.14 that in order to extract energy from the wave, r_g must be greater than zero, thus requiring T_k to be different from the nominal T_{k0} . The wind speed at the aircraft, V_w^* , is therefore different from the optimal ($2/3 V_w \cos \theta$) violating the aerodynamic optimum. This can be seen in Fig. 2.6 where case B4 is analysed. The average power output, P_{ww} , (top) as a function of r_g is obtained from Eq. 2.15 by fixing the numerically optimal s_g and c . It is worth noticing that the optimal value of c is very close to one for all the considered cases. The average power contribution due to the wave (bottom) is computed as $\frac{1}{T_w} \int_0^{T_w} \dot{z}(t)^2 r_g \sin \theta dt = \frac{1}{2} (\omega z_1)^2 r_g \sin \theta$. The average wind power (middle) is computed as the difference between the other two.

Sea Data			Unit
Water density ρ_w	1030		kg/m^3
Sea State	n. 2	n. 4	
Frequency ω	1.21	0.89	rad/s
Period T_w	5.16	7.06	sec
Peak-to-peak height H_w	1.5	2.5	m
Power density P_{wl}	11.4	43.6	kW/m

Table 2.4: Wave data used to simulate cases A2 (n. 2) and B4 (n. 4).

2.3.9 Transient behaviour

So far, only the steady state values that occur during a continuous reel-out phase have been considered. Fig. 2.7 shows the transient behaviour of the floating platform (case A2 of fig. 2.5) in case the pumping cycle is performed. The equations of motion are the same

CHAPTER 2. SIMPLIFIED MODEL OF OFFSHORE
AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY CONVERTERS

Figure 2.6: Combined wind-wave power output, case B4 of fig. 2.5 Power output (top), wind power (middle) and wave power (bottom) as a function of r_g . The top graph is the sum of the other two. The dashed lines represent the nominal wind-only and wave-only power, P_0 and P_w respectively.

of section 2.2.3 with the only difference that the tether force is multiplied by a square wave $q(t)$ having unit amplitude and 60% reel-out time. T_k is then substituted with $T_{kd} = q(t)T_k$. According to this hypothesis the transient motion has a negligible impact on the average power output that results equal to 61.4% of P_0 (2.4% higher than the nominal 60% of P_0).

Figure 2.7: Offshore AWES transient behaviour. Typical simulated heave motion of the platform (top), aircraft tether force (middle) and mechanical power output (bottom). Three pumping cycles are shown. Even though the platform reaches steady state conditions in about 30 sec, the three cycles are different because the duty cycle period is not a multiple of the wave period.

2.3.10 Applicability of the results

The results shown in section 2.3 represent the first parametric analysis of the design parameters of a floating offshore AWES. In this study, the assumptions and models that have been adopted were partly taken from the literature of other engineering fields such as ocean wave and Airborne Wind Energy. As for the hydrodynamics, the buoy was modelled as a heaving rigid body with only one DoF whereas other translations and all the rotations have been completely neglected. Among them, the surge and pitch motions could be also relevant since traction force of the aircraft may have relevant components along these two directions, depending on the structural layout. Moreover, as discussed in section 2.2.1, the structural forces are computed thanks to linear wave theory and potential flow hydrodynamics, thus limiting the applicability of the results only to non-extreme operational conditions. As for the aerodynamics, the simple steady state model introduced in section 2.2.2 aims at representing the aircraft behaviour without considering several aspects of the dynamics of a real airborne system such as the effects of gravity (weight of the aircraft), wind gusts, deformation of the wing, changes in lift or drag coefficients, cable vibration/galloping or other aeroelastic fluttering etc. However, the approximations used in this study are very helpful for an initial analysis, allowing to introduce for the first time the offshore floating AWES concept and to provide a preliminary assessment of its performance.

2.4 Conclusions

In this chapter the dynamics of an offshore Airborne Wind Energy Converter (AWES) has been investigated by coupling the aircraft steady state crosswind model with the 1 degree of freedom hydrodynamics of a floating platform held in place by a catenary mooring line. A simple analytical model to compute the power production and the platform heaving motion was derived. The model shows clearly that offshore AWESs are viable and also that there is a mild potential improvement due to combined wind-wave energy exploitation that can be achieved without changing the generator design. The model was numerically optimized and simulated with six different combinations of aircraft-platform sizes in eight different sea states. Despite this simple and fast model allows first design iterations, further re-

*CHAPTER 2. SIMPLIFIED MODEL OF OFFSHORE
AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY CONVERTERS*

search is required in modelling the system hydrodynamics in order to take account of other important factors such as heave-pitch-surge motion and response in irregular sea. As regards the shape of the platform, other geometries could be considered in future works with the aim of improving the performances of the combined wind-wave power extraction.

Moreover, the proposed analytical tools should be extended to the modeling of AWES farms which are expected to be much more efficient from the techno-economic point of view.

Chapter 3

Dynamic model of floating offshore airborne wind energy systems

With respect to Chapter 2 where deep offshore AWESs were modeled with 1 D.o.F., this chapter introduces a more general modeling approach, considering generic multi-DoF models for the different subsystems (mooring, platform, tethered AWES). Integrated models are obtained by coupling simplified models for the various subsystems. Attention is focused on AWESs with generators on the lower end of the cable (Ground-Gen [8]) mounted on slack-moored platforms, although the presented models can be easily extended to the case of AWESs with flying generators (Fly-Gen) and to any kind of moored floating platform. The assumed methodology provides a computationally-inexpensive tool that is useful for the preliminary evaluation and conceptual design of floating AWESs. Moreover, the proposed aero-hydrodynamic models allow to assess the influence of the platform motion on the performance of the wind generator, thus providing strategic information for the design of offshore AWESs controllers. An open source simulator based on the model presented in this chapter has been released and it is described in Appendix A. It is worth mentioning that the proposed model is only theoretical and

that an experimental validation has not been implemented yet.

The chapter is organized as follows. Section 3.1 describes the models employed for the different subsystems, i.e. platform, moorings and AWES. On the basis of such formulations, in Section 3.2 a case study is presented in which a dynamic simulator is implemented in a Matlab/Simulink environment. Such a simulator has been conceived as a numerical tool for preliminary assessment of different layouts of floating AWESs and it may serve as a platform to test control strategies and perform feasibility studies.

Discussions on practical layouts for the platform and mooring lines and other relevant engineering issues are finally reported in Section 3.3. A possible roadmap toward full-scale development of offshore AWES systems is also proposed on the basis of well-known methodologies imported from other sectors of offshore renewables.

3.1 Model

Accurate mathematical description of the dynamic response of a floating offshore AWES is an extremely complex problem. The governing physics of the system are characterized by coupled non-linear unsteady hydrodynamic and aerodynamic equations that should be simultaneously solved in order to calculate loads on the platform and predict its time response. CFD techniques, such as commonly used Reynolds-Averaged-Navier-Stokes Finite Volume solvers, could be employed for this purpose to accurately find solutions but they would result in heavy computational loads and time consuming procedures for setting up simulations.

In this section, a different approach is proposed, that is based on simplified models that are able to grasp the complex multi-DoF dynamic of a floating offshore AWES with an extremely reduced computational complexity. These models make it possible to run preliminary studies and iterative optimizations with very reduced time-to-solution. On the downside, the proposed models are based on assumptions and approximations that are only valid in operative conditions, i.e. in moderate sea states and wind intensity, far from extreme levels of stress.

A simplified scheme of floating offshore AWES is shown in Fig.2.1 where the plant is represented in its main sub-components: a floating platform, a mooring system, a traction tether and a wing.

CHAPTER 3. DYNAMIC MODEL OF FLOATING OFFSHORE AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY SYSTEMS

In this section, a simplified mathematical model that is able to predict the response of each of the sub-components is provided. The approach that is assumed for modeling the airborne components is based on state of the art models from the AWE sector while models for floating elements and mooring are borrowed from the naval/ocean engineering sector [155, 156, 157] and ocean renewable energy [158, 159].

Figure 3.1: Sketch of offshore AWES plant sub-components (mooring, platform, tether and kite) and definition of the reference systems.

In order to provide a clear description of the models it is important to set appropriate reference frames and coordinates. With reference to Fig. 3.1, the following frames are defined:

- $x - y - z$ is a fixed frame with z axis perpendicular to the water plane pointing upwards and having the origin in the position of the center of gravity of the platform in absence of loads from waves and/or tether traction.
- $x_p - y_p - z_p$ is platform-fixed frame having the origin in the center of mass of the platform and whose axes coincide with $x - y - z$ when the platform is not loaded;
- $x_k - y_k - z_k$ is the reference system employed to define kite trajectories and has the origin on the center of mass of the plat-

form. The orientation of the axes does not follow the platform-fixed frame of reference, but the x_k axis is along the absolute wind direction and the z_k axis points upwards against gravity.

3.1.1 Floating platform dynamic model

This sub-section presents a 6 DoF hydrodynamic model of the AWES floating platforms based on the assumptions of potential flow, linear wave theory [160] and small displacements, which make it possible to adopt linear equations [155] for the description of floater dynamics.

The coordinate system assumed to describe the (small) displacements of the floating platform is provided by a six-dimension vector $\boldsymbol{\xi} = [\mathbf{x}^T \ \Theta^T]^T = [x \ y \ z \ \theta_x \ \theta_y \ \theta_z]^T$, where the first three elements are the linear displacement components of \mathbf{x} and the last three components, Θ , are rotations about the indexed fixed axes (all expressed in the inertial frame of reference). The motion equation can be written in the time-domain according to [161, 150]:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}(t) = \mathbf{F}_H(t) + \mathbf{F}_R(t) + \mathbf{F}_D(t) + \mathbf{F}_E(t) + \mathbf{F}_M(t) + \mathbf{F}_K(t). \quad (3.1)$$

which represents the balance of the inertia forces, on the right-hand side of the equation and the applied (six-dimension) force-moment, on the left hand-side. The different terms are detailed in the following.

Inertia Matrix. \mathbf{M} is the platform inertia matrix that in the $x - y - z$ frame of reference reads as

$$\begin{aligned} M_{ii} &= m \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3 \\ M_{ij} &= \mathbf{I}_{i-3, j-3} \quad \text{for } i \geq 4, j \geq 4 \\ M_{ij} &= 0 \quad \text{elsewhere,} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

being m the platform mass and $\mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3}$ the platform moment of inertia tensor.

Hydrostatic Loads. \mathbf{F}_H represent the forces and moments due to gravity and buoyancy loads. They are a function of the displacement, $\boldsymbol{\xi}$, and, under the hypothesis of small motion amplitude, they read as

$$\mathbf{F}_H(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \approx \mathbf{F}_{H,0} - \mathbf{G}\boldsymbol{\xi}, \quad (3.3)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{H,0}$ is the resultant of gravity and buoyancy loads in the equilibrium configuration, $\boldsymbol{\xi} = \mathbf{0}$, and \mathbf{G} is the so-called buoyancy stiffness matrix, and it is responsible for an elastic-like restoring effect.

Radiation Loads. \mathbf{F}_R represent the force and moments induced by radiated waves that are generated by the platform oscillation, and read as

$$\mathbf{F}_R = -\mathbf{M}_\infty \ddot{\boldsymbol{\xi}} - \int_0^t \mathbf{K}(t - \tau) \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}(\tau) d\tau, \quad (3.4)$$

where \mathbf{M}_∞ is the added inertia matrix at infinite oscillation frequency, and the convolution integral is a memory term, whose kernel, \mathbf{K} , can be expressed in Fourier frequency domain as

$$\widehat{\mathbf{K}}(\omega) = i\omega \left(\widehat{\mathbf{M}}_A(\omega) - \mathbf{M}_\infty \right) + \widehat{\mathbf{B}}_r(\omega). \quad (3.5)$$

\mathbf{M}_A and \mathbf{B}_r are the frequency-dependent added mass and radiation damping matrices respectively, ω is the frequency expressed in rad/s, and the superscript $\widehat{}$ indicates the Fourier transform of the labeled quantities. Eq. (3.5) shows that waves radiated by the body influence the total inertia of the system (because of the displaced water volume) and generate a damping effect (i.e., radiated waves propagate at the expense of the platform mechanical energy). The hydrodynamic parameters, i.e., \mathbf{M}_∞ , $\widehat{\mathbf{M}}_A(\omega)$, $\widehat{\mathbf{B}}_r(\omega)$, $\widehat{\mathbf{F}}(\omega)$ and $\widehat{\psi}_i(\omega)$ can be computed using potential flow solvers, based on the Boundary Element Method (BEM) [162], with respect to the reference position of the platform, $\boldsymbol{\xi} = \mathbf{0}$. Examples of commercial BEM codes employed for this purpose are WAMIT, ANSYS AQWA, and NEMOH. The convolution term in Eq. (3.4) is computationally inconvenient, and it can be replaced by a state-space approximation, by introducing a state vector, $\boldsymbol{\eta}$, of appropriate length:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}} = \mathbf{A}_c \boldsymbol{\eta} + \mathbf{B}_c \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}} \\ \int_0^t \mathbf{K}(t - \tau) \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}(\tau) d\tau \approx \mathbf{C}_c \boldsymbol{\eta} \end{cases} \quad (3.6)$$

Matrices \mathbf{A}_c , \mathbf{B}_c and \mathbf{C}_c can be chosen using an identification procedure in the frequency domain [154].

Viscous Loads. \mathbf{F}_D are force and moments produced by drag of viscous friction of the fluid. Although Eq. (3.1) comes from an assumption of inviscid fluid and potential flow, the time-domain formulation

allows to include the effects of hydrodynamic drag dissipation. Such contribution is useful to model reasonable drift velocities for example in case of sudden changes in the tether force and it can be expressed in a general form as

$$\mathbf{F}_{D,i} = -\frac{1}{2}\rho_w C_i A_i l_i^k |\dot{\xi}_i| \dot{\xi}_i, \quad \text{with } k = 0 \text{ for } i \leq 3, k = 1 \text{ for } i > 3, \quad (3.7)$$

where ρ_w is the sea water density, A_i and l_i are a characteristic cross sections and lengths respectively, and C_i are dimensionless drag coefficients.

Wave Excitation Loads. \mathbf{F}_E represent the loads on the floating structure due to sea waves. Thanks to the hypothesis of linear waves, real waves are described as a superimposition of monochromatic waves with different frequencies. With this assumption, wave excitation forces can be approximated by a finite sum of N components as follows [163]:

$$\mathbf{F}_{E,i} = \sum_{j=1}^N a_{w,j} \hat{\Gamma}_i(\omega_j) \cos(\omega_j t + \hat{\psi}_i + \vartheta_j), \quad (3.8)$$

where ω_j are N different angular frequencies, $\hat{\Gamma}$ is a vector of wave excitation loads (per unit wave amplitude) depending on the wave frequency and direction of propagation, $\hat{\psi}_i(\omega)$ are angles expressing the phase shift among the different components of the excitation load at each frequency, ϑ_j are random numbers in the interval $[0; 2\pi]$; finally, $a_{w,j}$ are the amplitudes of the different harmonics, given by:

$$a_{w,j} = \sqrt{2 \Delta\omega_j S_w(\omega_j)}. \quad (3.9)$$

In Eq. (3.9), $\Delta\omega_j$ are the differences between consecutive frequencies, and $S_w(\omega)$ is the wave spectrum expressed in $\text{m}^2/(\text{rad/s})$, which quantifies the distribution of wave energy over pulsation [164]. Besides the action of sea waves, other excitation terms can be kept into account, e.g., the loads induced by sea currents. The latter can be eventually included in the model by means of a term in the same fashion of \mathbf{F}_D in Eq. (3.7).

External Loads. $\mathbf{F}_M = \sum_i \mathbf{F}_{M,i}$ is the total load due to the mooring

system, and it is the sum of contributions from the single mooring lines (in case of multi-line layout), $\mathbf{F}_{M,i}$; \mathbf{F}_K represents kite loads. Both these contributions will be detailed later on in this section.

3.1.2 Mooring lines model

In this section, modeling of platform mooring lines will be discussed, with reference to two traditional classes of computation methods (quasi-static and dynamic).

Offshore renewable energy platforms are moored according to a variety of architectures; a review of the different mooring layouts is presented in [165]. Mooring lines are primarily designed to exert static forces and keep the platform in place and guarantee its stability. However, due to the relevant pulling loads imposed by the wind generator, the dynamic effects of the mooring lines on the platform are non-negligible [161]. The dynamic model of the platform (see Eq. (3.1)) has therefore to be coupled with a model of the mooring system. To this aim, two fundamental approaches exist to model moorings [166]: quasi-static approach and fully-coupled dynamic methods.

Quasi-static methods originate from analytic solutions for the load and shape of continuous homogeneous cables (inextensible or deformable). These methods are only able to account for the gravity/buoyancy forces and, eventually, elastic forces on the cables, thus neglecting any other effect related to inertia and viscous loads. According to these approaches, mooring tensions in any intermediate configuration are a function of the mooring line ends position only. Assuming a quasi-static formulation, the mooring loads on a platform are, in general, a non-linear function of the displacement; nonetheless, it is a common practice to linearize them:

$$\mathbf{F}_M \approx \mathbf{F}_{M0} - \mathbf{G}_M \boldsymbol{\xi}, \quad (3.10)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{M0} = \sum_i \mathbf{F}_{M0,i}$ is the total mooring load in the static equilibrium position (including the contributions of the single lines), and \mathbf{G}_M is the overall stiffness matrix of the mooring system [167].

Dynamic approaches, on the other hand, account for inertial and dissipative effects. As pointed out in [168], the dynamics of mooring lines is non-negligible when water depth is large or if the line has large-drag elements (e.g., chain moorings). Besides the intrinsic inertia of the mooring line, hydrodynamic parameters (such as added mass, or drag) are crucial in the dynamics of a mooring lines. Such parameters

are usually found by means of specialized codes (e.g., ANSYS AQWA or ORCAFLEX). As for the quasi-static case, the load exerted by the mooring on the platform is often expressed in an approximated linear form [151]:

$$\mathbf{F}_M \approx \mathbf{F}_{M0} - \mathbf{G}_M \boldsymbol{\xi} - \mathbf{B}_M \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}} - \mathbf{M}_M \ddot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}, \quad (3.11)$$

where \mathbf{B}_M and \mathbf{M}_M are overall damping and inertia due to the mooring system.

In this work and in the case study presented in the following, reference is made to a quasi-static non linear model described in [146], which applies for catenary moorings [165] and is based on the assumption of inextensible mooring lines and on the catenary equations.

Figure 3.2: Sketch of a single catenary mooring line, with the main geometric dimensions defined. In the picture, T_m is the force (module) applied by the mooring line to the platform, and $T_{m,h}$ and $T_{m,v}$ its components.

The geometry of a single mooring line is shown in Fig. 3.2. The line is attached to the platform by means of a fairlead and fixed to the seabed by an anchor. In the picture, L and L_s are respectively the total (constant) length and the length of the suspended portion of the line, while h_m and v_m are, respectively, the horizontal and vertical distance between the fairlead and the anchor in a generic configuration.

The force exerted by the line on the platform can be decomposed into two vectors, one on the horizontal $x-y$ plane and a vertical one,

whose modules ($T_{m,h}$ and $T_{m,v}$) can be expressed as a function of only h_m and v_m (that are directly related to the platform position) [146]:

$$T_{m,h} = \frac{w v_m}{2} \left[\left(\frac{L_s}{v_m} \right)^2 - 1 \right]; \quad T_{m,v} = w L_s \quad (3.12)$$

with $L_s = L - h_m + \frac{T_{m,h}}{w} \operatorname{arccosh} \left(1 + \frac{w v_m}{T_{m,h}} \right),$

where w is the line weight (buoyancy force included) per unit length.

The implicit set of Eqs. (3.12) applies when $h_m + v_m > L$, otherwise the suspended portion of the line has vertical alignment, horizontal tension is null ($T_{m,h} = 0$) and the vertical force equals the weight (minus the buoyancy) of the suspended part ($T_{m,v} = w v_m$).

Using these equations on the various mooring lines and computing the associated moments with respect to the platform center of mass, it is possible to express the load vector \mathbf{F}_M as a function of $\boldsymbol{\xi}$.

3.1.3 Kite model

In modeling Airborne Wind Energy Systems, the kite can be modeled with different degrees of accuracy depending on the required output of the analysis. The complexity of kite models available in literature ranges from simple analytical expressions to sophisticated multibody models. For example, in [7] the basic algebraic formula describing the theoretical power of a cable-free AWES is provided, in [169] a point mass model and a four point model are proposed, in [170] a sophisticated and computationally-demanding multibody model is described.

In the present work the kite equations are based on the well-known 4 DoF dynamic model presented in [138, 58]. The assumption of the frame of reference $x_k - y_k - z_k$, see Section 3.1, and the choice of spherical coordinate systems with polar angle on the wind axis allows to greatly simplify the equations and solve a faster-than-real-time and computationally efficient system.

Since tethers are assumed to be simple lines, the kite position and attitude is fully defined with the length of the cables L , the orientation angle ψ and the spherical angles θ and φ . A description of the coordinate system with rotations is as follows: starting with the cables along the x_k axis and the kite pointing upwards, the first

rotation has amplitude $-\psi$ around x_k , then $-\theta$ around y_k and finally $+\varphi$ around x_k again. Three examples of wind-polar coordinates are shown in Fig. 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Examples of wind-polar coordinates. Positive wind-polar coordinates (ψ, θ, φ) are indicated by the black arrows. Blue arrows show the kite cartesian reference frame. By definition, the wind window has the wind going towards the screen, in x direction.

The transformation from polar to cartesian position is therefore:

$$\mathbf{X}_k = \begin{pmatrix} x_k \\ y_k \\ z_k \end{pmatrix} = L \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta \\ -\sin \theta \sin \varphi \\ \sin \theta \cos \varphi \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.13)$$

The equations of motion of the kite are:

$$\dot{\psi} = g_k v_a \delta + \dot{\varphi} \cos \theta \quad (3.14)$$

$$\dot{\theta} = \frac{v_a}{L} \left(\cos \psi - \frac{\tan \theta}{E} \right) + \frac{v_{yaw}}{L} \tan \theta \quad (3.15)$$

$$\dot{\varphi} = -\frac{v_a \sin \psi}{L \sin \theta} \quad (3.16)$$

where the introduced elements assume the following meaning.

Steering response coefficient g_k is a constant that defines the steering response of the kite;

Steering control δ is the non-dimensional control input according to the Turn Rate Law [138];

**CHAPTER 3. DYNAMIC MODEL OF FLOATING OFFSHORE
AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY SYSTEMS**

Apparent wind speed v_a is given by the relation $v_a = v_w E \cos \theta + v_{yaw} E$ (in a realistic system the instantaneous value of this velocity should be measured by a dedicated on-board sensor);

Equivalent aerodynamic efficiency E takes account of all the relevant drag contribution (tether drag, wing drag and where applicable steering unit or fuselage drag);

Drift-away velocity v_{yaw} is the velocity of the kite along the yaw axis aligned towards the floating platform, given by the combination of the drum control input and the motion of the platform.

When the kite is linked to a fixed ground station, as in many AWE prototypes, the component of the kite velocity in the direction of the cables, v_{yaw} , can be assumed to come only from the drum control input on the reeling velocity, $v_{yaw} = -\dot{L}$ [58].

However, if the ground station is a floating platform, the ground ends of the cables of the kite are moved. This may lead to a temporary increase or decrease in the relative wind field at the kite and therefore in the tether tension, depending on the kite position in the wind window and on the direction of motion of the floating platform with respect to the kite position. For example, in case the cables are pulled against the wind, the kite velocity increases and so does the tether force. Likewise, if the platform moves towards the absolute wind direction, the tether tension will decrease. Conversely, a small platform oscillation perpendicular to the cables direction will not generate any effect at the kite. Therefore a kinematic law is needed to couple the airborne system to the floating platform to take into account these effects. In this work, the kinematic link is modeled as:

$$v_{yaw} = - \left(\dot{L} + \dot{\mathbf{C}} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{X}_k}{\|\mathbf{X}_k\|} \right) \quad (3.17)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{R}_Z \mathbf{R}_Y \mathbf{R}_X \mathbf{C}_p \quad (3.18)$$

where \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{C}_p represent the coordinates of the point where the cables exit from the platform (see Fig. 3.2), expressed in the fixed reference system ($x - y - z$) and in the platform reference system ($x_p - y_p - z_p$), respectively. \mathbf{R}_X , \mathbf{R}_Y and \mathbf{R}_Z are the rotation matrices around the x, y and z axis for the transformation from the platform ref. system to the fixed ref. system (see Fig. 3.1). \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{X}_k contain

the coordinates of the platform and of the kite defined in sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.3, respectively.

In case the platform does not move, the velocity of point C is zero and the coupling equation (3.17) goes back to the case of fixed ground station ($v_{yaw} = -\dot{L}$).

The kite affects the platform motion thanks to the kite aerodynamic loads that generate forces and moments on the platform through the tether.

$$\mathbf{F}_k = \frac{1}{2} \rho_a V_a^2 A_k \sqrt{C_L^2 + C_D^2} \quad (3.19)$$

where ρ_a is the air density, A_k is the kite aerodynamic area, C_L and C_D are the lift and drag coefficients, respectively.

Even though the lift and drag coefficients change with the angle of attack and other effects, in this analysis C_L and C_D are considered constant, assuming the presence of an inner control loop that keeps the angle of attack in a small range as reported in literature [8, 36, 120]. Stall effects are therefore not captured by this model.

3.2 Case study

In this section a case study is presented in order to provide an understanding on what kind of analysis can be conducted using the presented models. Specifically, a pumping kite system and its controller are implemented and integrated with a light-weight slack-moored floating platform model. The proposed analysis highlights the effects of the moving/floating platform on the AWES system and viceversa.

A cylindrical barge with large diameter and short draft is considered, which is assumed to be moored with a single slack mooring line (i.e., the platform can perform large displacements on the water plane). These conditions are considered highly disadvantageous in traditional offshore wind, as both the barge-like platform and slack mooring contribute to large displacements of the generator. Nevertheless, the results of this analysis show that the floating AWES can preserve stability and good power output in spite of the unfavorable layout, thus providing first positive evidences on the feasibility of offshore AWES systems based on light-weight floating foundations.

3.2.1 Simulator

The analysis of the case study has been carried out with a dynamic simulator for floating AWESs, which is based on the models presented in Section 3.1. The simulator has been developed in a Matlab-Simulink environment and can be adapted to different AWES architectures with custom layouts of the floating platform, mooring lines and flying kite.

Every time the routine is called, before starting the time-domain simulation, the implicit Eqs. (3.12) are solved for the input selection of the system parameters in order to map the force response of the mooring lines as a function of the fairlead position. Then, the simulator calls Simulink routines to solve the dynamic motion of the floating platform (Eq. (3.1)) and of the flying kite (Eqs. (3.14), (3.15) and (3.16)) that are coupled according to Eqs. 3.17 and 3.18 using the control strategy described in Section 3.2.3.

The modeled physical phenomena are all statically and dynamically stable as there are no negative stiffness and damping coefficients. The simulator showed no numerical stability issues for the range of the parameters set that has been employed. A thorough analysis of the numerical stability would be an interesting topic but it would be out of the scope of this work. The integration of the aforementioned equations is performed with a fixed step explicit solver (ode3 Bogacki-Shampine) with a 0.1 s step size.

A set of three dimensional views showing the animations produced by the simulator for the different subsystems is shown in Fig. 3.4. The source code of the simulator and a sample video is available at [11].

Figure 3.4: 3D view of the simulation environment. The subsystems of a simple offshore AWES are shown: kite, platform and mooring line.

3.2.2 Platform and mooring

For the sake of clarity, a simplified layout is assumed, which consists in a homogeneous axisymmetric platform moored with a single line (Fig. 3.4). Realistic architectures for offshore AWESs are likely to be more complex (e.g., having multiple mooring lines to keep the platform in place and non-trivial shapes and distribution of ballast masses and buoyant volumes to enhance stability). The platform is assumed to be a cylindrical barge-like buoy as in Fig. 3.2, with the features reported in Table 3.1. The inertia and damping of the mooring lines are neglected in this case study.

Platform data	Value	Unit
Diameter	10	m
Draft d	1.2	m
Height l	1.8	m
Density ρ_p	670	kg/m ³
Nominal displacement M	94.7	ton
Viscous drag coefficient C_h	1	
Viscous drag coefficient C_v	1	
Mooring line data		
Length L	350	m
Line linear weight w	373	N/m
Anchor position x	-301.2	m
Anchor position y	0	m
Anchor position z	-49.7	m
Fairlead position x, y	0	m
Anchor position z	-0.9	m
Water data		
Water density ρ_w	1025	kg/m ³
Water depth h	50	m

Table 3.1: Floating platform, mooring line and water data.

In the hypothesis of cylindrical platform with homogeneous density, ρ_p , the inertia matrix \mathbf{M} and the hydrostatic buoyancy matrix \mathbf{G} can be found analytically, with the relations in Table 3.2. Hydrodynamic parameters introduced in Section 3.1.1 are obtained with the BEM solver ANSYS AQWA. Platform drag coefficients (C_i in Eq. (3.7)) are all taken equal to one, in order to reasonably estimate the drag loads order of magnitude.

Inertia Matrix

$$M_{11} = M_{22} = M_{33} = m = \frac{\pi}{4}\rho_p l D^2$$

$$M_{44} = M_{55} = \frac{m}{4} \left(\frac{l^2}{3} + \frac{D^2}{4} \right) \quad , \quad M_{66} = \frac{1}{8} m D^2$$

Hydrostatic Stiffness Matrix

$$G_{11} = G_{22} = G_{66} = 0 \quad , \quad G_{ij} = 0 \quad \text{for } i \neq j$$

$$G_{44} = G_{55} = \frac{\pi}{64}\rho_w g D^4 - \frac{\pi}{4}\rho_w g d D^2 d_B + m g d_G$$

Table 3.2: Inertia matrix and hydrostatic stiffness matrix elements for the case of cylindrical homogeneous platform. Here, $d_B=0.6$ m is the depth of the barge center of buoyancy and $d_G=0.3$ m is the depth of the center of gravity below the still water level, in the equilibrium configuration.

In the present layout, it is assumed that the winch on which the tether is wound and the mooring line fairlead are aligned with the platform centroid along the platform z_p axis direction. The anchor is positioned along the x axis in a way that, in the reference configuration ($\boldsymbol{\xi} = \mathbf{0}$), the suspended length of the line (L_s) is vertical and equal to the vertical distance between the fairlead and the seabed, as shown in Fig. 3.1.

Although the hydrodynamic model proposed in Section 3.1.1 comes from a linearization, and is usually valid only for small displacements of the platform, in the case in exam it rigorously holds even for large displacements in x and y direction (not in z direction). Indeed, given the form of hydrodynamic parameters (in particular, hydrostatic stiffness) for this case (Table 3.2), none of the loads in Eq. (3.1) explicitly depends on x and y , except for \mathbf{f}_M and \mathbf{f}_K . In the computation of these two loads general non-linear formulations are used, which apply even for large x and y displacements as well.

For the choosen layout of mooring-barge-tether system and the assumption of small displacements, the platform dynamics is entirely described by 5 DoFs, as no moment can be generated on the z di-

rection, thus the platform yaw rotation, θ_z , is considered identically null.

3.2.3 Kite and controller

Among the many different type of controllers that have been proposed in literature [171, 36, 172, 54, 173, 45], we choose for this case study the simple control strategy illustrated in [138], including improvements proposed in [33].

This controller is based on a simple PID tracking and an algorithm based on four attraction points that makes it possible to reliably implement "side-down" figure-of-eight loops.

With reference to the coordinate system defined in Section 3.1.3, it is possible to define the heading, γ , as:

$$\gamma = \arctan\left(\frac{-\dot{\varphi} \sin \theta}{\dot{\theta}}\right) \quad (3.20)$$

The reference heading, γ_0 , is computed as

$$\gamma_0 = \arctan\left(\frac{\varphi - \varphi_{0,i}}{\theta_{0,i} - \theta}\right) \quad (3.21)$$

where $\theta_{0,i}$ and $\varphi_{0,i}$ are the constant polar coordinates of the i -th attraction point, P_i , to which the kite is pointing at ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$).

The non-dimensional steering input of eq. 3.14 is given by a simple proportional control on the reference heading:

$$\delta = K_\gamma(\gamma_0 - \gamma) \quad (3.22)$$

The attraction point P_i is pre-assigned and is changed with the following switch-case algorithm:

```

Switch  $i$ 
Case  $i = 1$ 
    if  $\varphi \leq -\varphi_{th}$  then  $i = 2$ 
Case  $i = 2$ 
    if  $\theta \leq \theta_{th}$  then  $i = 3$ 
Case  $i = 3$ 
    if  $\varphi \geq \varphi_{th}$  then  $i = 4$ 
Case  $i = 4$ 
    if  $\theta \leq \theta_{th}$  then  $i = 1$ 
    
```


This control algorithm results in a side-down figure-of-eight motion. For example, with reference to Fig. 3.5, viewing the kite from the floating platform with the wind going towards the screen, starting the kite with initial coordinates $\psi_0 = 0$ deg, $\theta_0 = 45$ deg and $\varphi = 0$ deg and initial attraction point P_1 , the kite moves upwards and starts steering counterclockwise ($\delta > 0$) while heading to point 1. The φ coordinate becomes negative and keeps decreasing until the threshold $-\varphi_{th}$ is reached and the attraction point switches to point 2. The kite keeps steering counterclockwise to reach point 2 and lowers its θ coordinate. When θ is lower or equal than θ_{th} the attraction point becomes point number 3. The kite steers counterclockwise and starts moving towards greater θ and positive φ until $+\varphi_{th}$ is reached and the attraction point becomes point n. 4. The kite steers clockwise towards lower values of θ and when θ is lower or equal than θ_{th} the attraction point becomes point n. 1 and the cycle starts over.

Figure 3.5: The kite is controlled in to a 'side-down' figure-of-eight motion following the four attraction points marked with a red *. The wind window is shown with the wind going towards the screen.

Regarding the control of the reeling drums, different strategies are possible. For example, in [33] the kite is reeled-in after depowering maneuvers, in [137] an optimization of the reeling cycle for a pumping glider is performed and in [62] a detailed control algorithm for soft kites with reel-in at the edge of the wind window is described.

In this work, during reel-out the drum velocity is controlled with a simple proportional controller on the tether force $\dot{L} = K_F(F_k - F_{k0})$. When the maximum tether length is reached, the control mode is switched to reel-in mode and the kite is assumed to fly at constant velocity towards the ground station with zero tension. When the tether length is below the minimum threshold the drum controller is switched to reel-out mode again.

The complete kite data, employed for this case study, together with the control parameters are reported in Table 3.3.

Kite and wind data	Value	Unit
Aerodynamic efficiency E	3.9	
Turn rate law constant g_k	0.13	
Lift coefficient C_L	0.65	
Avg. polar angle θ	28	deg
Area A_k	200	m ²
Avg. Tether tension F_k	81	kN
Avg. reel-out mech. power	200	kW
Wind speed V_w	12	m/s
Air density ρ_a	1.225	kg/m ³
Point C coord. \mathbf{C}_p	(0, 0, 1)	m
Control parameters		
Attraction point coord. $\varphi_{0,1}$	-20	deg
Attraction point coord. $\theta_{0,1}$	50	deg
Attraction point coord. $\varphi_{0,2}$	-30	deg
Attraction point coord. $\theta_{0,2}$	15	deg
Attraction point coord. $\varphi_{0,3}$	20	deg
Attraction point coord. $\theta_{0,3}$	50	deg
Attraction point coord. $\varphi_{0,4}$	30	deg
Attraction point coord. $\theta_{0,4}$	15	deg
Heading proportional gain K_γ	0.4	rad ⁻¹
Force proportional gain K_F	5e-4	(m/s)/N
Polar threshold θ_{th}	50	deg
Longitudinal threshold φ_{th}	± 15	deg
Min. tether length	400	m
Max. tether length	800	m
Reel-in speed	2.3	m/s
Force set point F_{k0}	76	kN

Table 3.3: Kite, wind and control data.

3.2.4 Simulation results

In order to provide a comparative study, three scenarios have been considered and are presented in this section. Specifically, the same AWES system have been imagined to be installed: (1) onshore (with fixed ground station), (2) on a floating offshore platform in a calm

sea (without waves) and (3) floating offshore platform in presence of intermediate intensity irregular sea waves. In the last case, wave excitation (equations 3.8 and 3.9) is computed assuming a propagation direction along the x axis and a Pierson-Moscowitz distribution [163, 164] to describe the wave spectrum:

$$S_{\omega}(\omega) = 262.9H_s^2T_e^{-4}\omega^{-5} \exp(-1054T_e^{-4}\omega^{-4}), \quad (3.23)$$

where H_s and T_e are statistical wave parameters known as 'significant wave height' and 'energy period', and they were assumed to equal $H_s=4$ m, $T_e=10$ s.

Results from simulations are reported in Figs. 3.6 and 3.7 that show the time series of the power output and the platform displacements in the three scenarios, respectively.

In Fig. 3.6 the power is zero during reel-in phases (marked in gray on the plot) due to the assumption of null tether tension, although in practice some power is required to reel-in the cables. Comparing the three scenarios, it is clear that when the AWES is on the floating platform, the power output is quite irregular. i.e. the reeling controller needs to compensate for the platform motion in order to follow the set point of tether tension, thereby generating large oscillations of the instantaneous power around the mean value.

As shown in Fig. 3.7, due to the peculiar layout with single mooring line, the platform undergoes large displacements on the horizontal plane (in x and y direction) in correspondence of both the switching phases between reel-out / reel-in and the periodic lobes of the figure-of-eight path. In particular, the platform oscillates above two different equilibrium positions during reel-out and reel-in phases. In the first case, the mean equilibrium position is set by the force balance among hydrodynamic loads, mooring traction and kite mean tether tension; as the tether tension goes to zero (reel-in), the platform moves in x direction toward the reference equilibrium position due to the restoring mooring force.

Notice also that, for both the scenarios with floating AWES (with and without waves), the power (Fig. 3.6) becomes negative at the beginning of reel-out cycles, that is, the generator is required to spend power even though the controller is set on reel-out mode. This effect, which is due to the large velocity of the platform in the direction of the tether length, is important and may introduce further complexity in the controller design.

Finally, further considerations can be outlined:

- Heave (z) and pitch (R_y) displacements of the platform in presence of waves are relevantly larger than in calm sea.
- In presence of waves, the hydrodynamic Eq. (3.8) is not rigorously valid immediately after the switching between reel-in and reel-out (i.e. when velocity in x and y direction is large). In these cases, wave frequency should be corrected accounting for the relative velocity between wave and platform.
- Although the considered kite is quite large (with a power in the order of hundreds of kilowatts) and the barge relatively light (the weight is approximately 10 times the mean tether pulling force), the platform does not lose stability, even in presence of relatively tall waves. This is an encouraging result, which demonstrates that offshore AWESs may be deployed with simpler and lighter structures than traditional offshore wind turbines.
- The simulation of the kite retraction phase was done assuming zero tension on the tether. The force during reel-in can be theoretically brought to a near-zero magnitude with a proper flight of a glider [137] and can be practically reduced to roughly one fourth of the reel-out force with a canopy kite [174]. The assumption of zero reel-in force leads to a simple and effective simulation of the transient phase between reel-in and reel-out (see Figs. 3.6 and 3.7), though it could be improved by e.g. choosing more accurate values of the tether force and the reel-in velocity or by taking into account different reel-in strategies.

Figure 3.6: Available mechanical power at the generator. Reel-in phases are highlighted in gray.

Figure 3.7: Displacements and rotations of the platform: results of the simulated case study. Reel-in phases are highlighted in gray.

3.3 Discussion

In this section, a general discussion is provided about technological and engineering issues which cannot be directly observed from the proposed simulator results. Design and operational aspects are discussed on the basis of existing knowledge coming from the offshore wind turbines sector. Types of platforms, moorings and very preliminary roadmap towards full-scale devices deployment are outlined.

For conventional horizontal-axis wind turbines, it has been suggested [161, 175] that in water deeper than 50 m bottom-fixed support structures are not economically feasible, thus the necessity of floating platform-based solutions arises. The installation of wind turbines on floating platforms presents a number of criticalities related to stability and critical loads due to the large aerodynamic forces applied at large height above the water surface, which are responsible for large pitch overturning moments [176]. Therefore, offshore wind platforms and moorings are generally designed to minimize the wind/wave induced displacements as well as free oscillations [177]. Tethered AWE generators have the intrinsic advantage of generating moderate over-

turning moments on the platform, thus, it is expectable that design requirements for floating AWE platform may be less stringent than for traditional turbines.

Beside the barge architecture presented in Section 3.2 a variety of platform typologies could be considered. Examples of possible configuration are reported in Fig. 3.8 on the basis of envisaged architectures in the wind-offshore sector [177, 175].

The spar buoy (Fig. 3.8(a)) is a platform with deep draft and it is stabilized by lowering the center of mass below the center of buoyancy with a properly sized ballast. This kind of platform features low vertical wave induced forces, thus undergoing small heave displacements. Due to the small cross section area, its motion is prevalently in roll and pitch [176].

Barge platforms (Fig. 3.8(b)) present large water plane surface (which allows to achieve stability) and relatively shallow draft. According to Roddier et al. [176], this kind of platform is marginally investigated in traditional offshore wind due to its significant angular motions. As shown by the case study in Section 3.2, in offshore AWE such angular displacements might be smaller (thanks to the moderate kite-induced moments on the floater), but still relevant. A solution is hypothesized in Fig. 3.8(b) right, where a ring-shaped barge is sketched, which has inertia and buoyant volume located by the platform outer perimeter. The barge central part consists of a lightweight structure (holding the generator), whose structural resistance is possible thanks to the relatively reduced loads generated by the AWE generator. This layout appears to provide a better pitch stability and reduced angular displacements.

Semisubmersible platforms (Fig. 3.8(c)) combine the restoring effects of the two previous types [175]. They are constituted by ballasted pontoons providing buoyancy to the structure, with relatively low wave excitation loads due to the moderate water plane area.

Figure 3.8: Schematic drawing of four main types of floating platform for offshore wind: (a) Spar buoy, (b) Barge platforms, (c) Semisubmersible platform, (d) Tension leg platform.

These three platform concepts usually employ catenary lines (like those modeled in Section 3.1.2) or taut lines as moorings. Catenary moorings generate a restoring force which is principally due to the line weight, they are slack and approach the sea bed with horizontal tangent. Taut legs arrive at sea bed tense with a certain angle; the main contribution to restoring forces is the line elasticity. Taut moorings have smaller positioning radius, thus requiring a reduced occupied sea bed portion, but they must stand larger tension and their anchor point must resist both horizontal and vertical forces [178].

A different type of floating platform is the so-called Tension Leg Platform (TLP), (Fig. 3.8(d)), in which the support tank basement is fully submerged and its excess buoyancy keeps the mooring lines tense and vertically aligned. This architecture minimizes platform displacements, but it is highly costly and presents a number of issues related to mooring installation and lines tension variation as water level changes (due to tidal or incoming waves) [176].

The choice of the platform and mooring type relies on different types of requirement and must be supported by making reference to coupled aero-hydrodynamic models. The key factors for the choice are environmental variables such as water depth (e.g., TLPs and taut moored platforms become advantageous with respect to catenary moored systems as water depth increases [179]), stability, crit-

ical loads, displacements. The evaluation of the last two aspects, in particular, is strongly related to the interaction of the floating platform with incoming waves. When the platform resonates (in one of its oscillation modes) with the incoming waves, wave induced loads and/or displacements are maximized. Evaluation of wave spectra and recurring wave energy periods in the installation site is a preliminary step towards the design of platforms with natural frequency outside the range of typical wave frequencies [177]. Moreover, a number of design expedients can be included in order to damp or minimize wave excitation on floating platforms. E.g., pontoons of semisubmersible platforms are usually equipped with horizontal plates at the bottom end, with the aim of increasing the added mass (thus reducing the natural frequency, shifting it away from waves pulsation) and generating viscous damping [176].

Furthermore, it must be remarked that other technical aspects should be kept into account to design and analyze floating AWE plants, i.e.:

- Operating loads and fatigue assessment. This aspect is less crucial than in traditional offshore wind, in which the most critical component is the wind turbine structure itself. In floating AWE, this type of analysis should only be addressed to floating basement and mooring lines.
- Cut-off meteorological conditions. The cut-off wind condition (beyond which a safety landing is necessary) have to be chosen in the light of the platform dynamics. A set of combined wind-wave-current cut-off states for the generator should be defined.
- Extreme loads and survivability. Platform design must guarantee survivability in presence of extreme waves/currents. The modeling methodology proposed in this work is suitable for average operating conditions only (and in presence of small platform displacements). Extreme sea analysis requires different tools, e.g., finite-volume CFD solvers or pool tests of scaled prototypes.
- Non-linear hydrodynamic effects. The relevance of other hydrodynamic effects should be preliminarily assessed with appropriate tools. E.g., Vortex-Induced Vibration (VIV) due to sea currents has to be examined, as it is potentially damaging at frequencies close to the natural frequency of the structure [168].

Moreover, second-order drift hydrodynamic forces can be included in the time domain model of Eq. (3.1), which may cause the platform to oscillate about an offset position with respect to the nominal equilibrium [161].

- Installation and operation. Transportation and anchoring of the platform as well as in-site installation of the tethered generator have to be standardized and automatized. Moreover, take-off and landing phases of the flying generator, which are complex operations still representing a challenge for on-shore AWE [8], have to be further improved and adapted to offshore conditions.
- Farms of devices. Similarly to other offshore renewable energy technologies, it is expected that offshore AWE generators become more convenient when installed in farms where operation and maintenance can be more efficient and fixed costs such as electrical connections can be shared among multiple devices [180]. If farms are considered, different layouts can be conceived (e.g., shared platforms and moorings may be employed for different AWESs) and more sophisticated models, keeping into account the aero-hydrodynamic interaction among different devices, should be employed.

Given the high uncertainty related to floating AWESs modeling and design, the above mentioned engineering issues, and the large capital costs involved, it is expectable that a viable roadmap towards implementation of full-scale offshore AWESs should include a series of incremental scale-up prototyping steps, following the methodology of the other offshore renewable energy systems (namely, wave, tidal, offshore wind generators) [176, 180].

After a first phase of concept definition, small-scale tests (e.g., wave tank tests on scaled prototypes of floating platform) are required prior to undertake offshore installation. Such tests are useful to adjust and update previously established numerical models, correct the design choices and assess the device response in operating and extreme load conditions. Final scale-up steps may include sea-tests, monitoring and grid connection of nearly-full-scale (e.g., 1:5) prototypes first, and on full-scale devices finally.

3.4 Conclusions

In this chapter, the potential of offshore AWESs is investigated and numerical models are presented for preliminary modeling and design of floating platforms housing AWESs.

Offshore sites are very promising for wind energy application, as they feature large available airspace and non-turbulent thin wind boundary layers. Installing AWESs offshore, in particular, may open the way to the development of high-altitude wind technology by preventing NIMBY effects that AWESs may induce on the general public. Nevertheless, the implementation of offshore wind generators is a costly and complex operation, which requires a number of progressive steps preceding the installation of a full-scale fully-functional device.

The first step towards deployment is preliminary numerical modeling aimed at understanding the interaction among the different subsystems (platform, wind generator, mooring system) and roughly designing the various parts and the controller. This chapter presents numerical models specifically tailored to this purpose. Existing models for the different subsystems have been collected from literature, adapted, extended and coupled. In particular, a multi-DoF hydrodynamic model for floating platforms is presented, which relies on potential-flow and linear waves theory, a quasi-static model for catenary moorings has been detailed, and a 4-DoF model for kite-type AWESs has been assumed. With respect to other sophisticated numerical tools, which solve fluid continuum equations using a local approach and a domain discretization, this set of models allows faster-than-real-time calculations and is thus preferable at a first stage of analysis.

A Matlab-Simulink simulator that relies on the above mentioned models has been released [11]. An illustrative case study is discussed, which makes reference to a cylindrical barge platform with a single mooring line.

The presented simulator provides a one-of-a-kind numerical platform on which different layouts of floating AWESs can be tested and designed, prior to undergo progressive scale-up prototyping steps towards the installation of full-scale offshore AWESs.

Chapter 4

Assessment of high altitude dual wind energy drone generators

As introduced in Chapter 1, in the upper region of the atmospheric layers, winds are more powerful, steadier and more persistent than at lower altitudes, where conventional wind turbines usually operate [13]. At several thousand meters above sea level, jet streams currents can reach power densities as high as 15 kW/m^2 (i. e. 50-100 more power than typical values at ground level) with typical availability of more than 30 %. Early studies in AWE were focusing on high altitudes, at several thousand meters above ground level [28]. However, in spite of several research efforts, present Wind Energy Drones (WEDs) are limited to several hundred meters [120, 37, 123]. The reason for this, which is better explained in section 4.1, can be identified in the problem imposed by the aerodynamic drag of the cables [181]. The gain in power provided by the strength of winds at high altitude is not enough to compensate the loss in power through cables drag that increases with their length. Several concepts have therefore been proposed and patented to overcome this limitations and achieve near-zero cable drag [131, 134].

This chapter presents the first detailed assessment of a system based on a dual WED architecture in which the two drones, with on-board generators, are connected to the ground with Y shaped

tethering; a concept that was first envisioned in patent [131] in 1976 and has been later investigated by several authors [181, 132, 182, 133]. Systems of more than two drones (multi WEDs systems) are also possible, however this chapter focuses on dual drone systems.

While previous studies mainly focused on modelling and control issues, this chapter aims at providing a first detailed evaluation of the power capabilities of a dual-WED system. Specifically, a model that combines essential aerodynamic, electrical and mechanical aspects is developed to derive a simplified power curve. This model takes into account important real-world constraints such as the mass of drones and tethers, plus structural and electrical constraints of the cables and hovering constraints.

A series of case studies is implemented on the basis of a site-specific wind data at different scales/altitudes, foreseeing a power output from a few hundred kW to several MW, with 30% capacity factor.

The contents of this chapter are organised as follows. Section 4.1 explains the dual wind drone concept and the working principle of the dual WED system, Section 4.2 presents the mathematical model that is employed to evaluate the performances of the system and Section 4.3 provides some numerical examples based on real wind data. The numerical solver of the equations is described in appendix C of this thesis.

4.1 Jet stream altitude wind drone system

Before explaining the WED concept that is proposed and analysed in the following sections, it is useful to recall the working principle of the single Fly-Gen wind drone, i. e. the concept investigated by Google-Makani and others [120, 7].

As explained in Chapter 1, in a single Fly-Gen WED, electric energy is produced on board of the aircraft during its flight and it is transmitted to the ground through a special rope which integrates electric cables. The Fly-Gen plane takes off pointing upwards, driven by the propellers thrust. This take-off mode is similar to that of a quadcopter and the on-board rotors are used as thrusters. During take-off the rope reels out from the ground station. The reel out direction is mainly downwind. Once the rope has been unwound, the

single WED changes flight mode becoming a tethered airplane. In this second flight mode a circular crosswind flight path is powered by the wind itself and the on-board rotors are used as generators to extract power from the wind. During this phase the cable length is fixed. An animation of the working principle for a single Fly-Gen drone is available in [91].

For a given absolute wind speed V_w , with air density ρ , angle of altitude β , lift and drag coefficients of the drone C_L and C_D referred to a drone wing area A , cable diameter d and length l , drag coefficient of the cable C_{\perp} , the nominal power that can be extracted by a single wind drone can be computed with the well known formula as in [8]:

$$P_{nom} = \frac{1}{2}\rho (V_w \cos \beta)^3 \frac{4}{27} \left(\frac{C_L}{C_D + \frac{dC_{\perp}}{4A}} \right)^2 C_L A$$

It is very important to notice that the power output reduction due to cable drag, $(dC_{\perp})/(4A)$, increases with the cable length dramatically. In the attempt of choosing coefficients and dimension of practical interest, it is easy to observe that it is difficult to design a system for extreme high altitudes. Actually, the gain obtained in reaching the powerful high altitude winds by increasing the cable length will soon result in a net loss due to dissipation in cable drag. This is why the optimal altitude for a single Fly-Gen wind drone is usually set at relatively low altitudes of a few hundred meters. This issue is currently limiting the real competitive advantage of WEDs and translates into a relatively minor improvement with respect to conventional wind turbines.

For the above mentioned reasons in this work we further develop the analysis of a solution to overcome this physical limit that was originally proposed by [131] and later investigated in [181, 132, 182, 133, 16].

This concept consists in (at least) two crosswind drones that share a common part of their cables (see Fig. 4.1 right). One main longer cable connects the ground station to a split point where the two cables (hereafter called *dancing cables*) that reach each drone are attached.

The drones are controlled in a way to approximately follow the same circular trajectory maintaining diametrically opposed positions. Such circular trajectory is chosen in a way to minimize the absolute velocity of the split point.

If this working condition is achieved, the longer-shared cable is not moving and does not generate any drag, and aerodynamic losses are only generated by the two shorter cables. This solution may allow to considerably increase the length of the cables (i. e. the altitude) while keeping the aerodynamic losses substantially constant thereby achieving a major gain in the power output because of the stronger high-altitude winds.

Figure 4.1: A dual wind drone system and other wind energy technologies. In this schematic drawing, a dual drone system (right) extracts power at high altitude, converts it into electricity thanks to on-board wind turbines and sends it to the ground through light-weight electrical cables. A single wind drone (Google-Makani style) and a conventional wind turbine are also depicted.

Because of its complexity, it was hard to envision a real technological viability for this system when it was first sketched back in 1976 [131]. Only recently, because of modern enabling technologies, several studies were conducted about this concept. In [132] a nominal power output of 6 MW is envisioned with a double Fly-Gen drone system of 100 m², in [182] a dual airfoil system is modelled together with a rotational take-off system and in [181] the momentum balance of the airflow for a dual drone system is investigated.

The present work focuses on assessing the power output of a WED system including real-world constraints such as the weight of the cables, the dissipated heat due to joule effect in the electrical conduc-

CHAPTER 4. ASSESSMENT OF HIGH ALTITUDE DUAL
WIND ENERGY DRONE GENERATORS

tors, and their resulting temperature rise. Specifically, two different cable layouts are therefore proposed in Fig. 4.2. The first layout assumes a coaxial cable having the structural and electrical part on the same axis. This coaxial layout is simpler but requires a low electrical resistance in order not to heat up the structural cables. A second layout proposes the electrical conductors outside the structural cables in order to allow higher temperatures of the electrical cables thereby increasing the Joule losses but at the same time reducing the weight of the cables.

Figure 4.2: Schematics of the cable arrangement for dual WEDs. Proportions are distorted for the sake of clarity. Two different layouts are shown. 1) The left configuration features a coaxial cable with integrated structural and electrical functions i. e. the cable is made of structural wires, to resist the traction forces of the airborne system, coupled with conductive aluminum wires, to transfer the power from the airborne generators to the ground. 2) Right: a more complex arrangement has the electrical cables that run in parallel to the structural cable.

4.2 Model

This section introduces the mathematical model that makes it possible to assess the *nominal* power output of the dual WED system presented in section 4.1. The nominal power output will be then used in Section 4.3 to provide simplified and conservative power curves of dual drone systems of several sizes.

4.2.1 Model hypotheses

The split point of the long common cable is assumed to be kept fixed by appropriately controlling the two drones. Each drone is assumed to fly in steady state crosswind flight and at constant altitude, i. e. the radius of the trajectory of the WEDs is much smaller than the length of the common cable.

Section 4.2.2 describes the basic geometrical relations employed to describe the system. The lengths of the longer shared cable and the two dancing cables are computed from the nominal altitude and elevation angle assuming straight cables (i.e. neglecting the cable sag) by means of a simple trigonometric equation. Each dancing cable is assumed to be subjected to a triangular relative wind distribution while the fixed common cable is assumed to be subjected only to a site-specific absolute wind shear distribution that is computed in Section 4.2.3 assuming low tether sag.

Section 4.2.4 recalls known models for estimating the steady-state nominal power output [120, 7] and also adds a 2D mechanical equilibrium (Fig. 4.3) in order to take into account also the effect of drone mass and of the distributed cable drag due the absolute wind velocity. The mass of the two drones is assumed to be lumped to a single point at nominal flight altitude. The distributed cable drag force is conservatively assumed to be applied at the nominal flight altitude.

The structural cable diameter is related to the drone lift by considering the nominal breaking strength and a safety coefficient as in Section 4.2.5.

Considering that the cables are very long, Section 4.2.6 takes into account the dissipated power by Joule effect and the resulting temperature of the cables surface. The power cables are therefore assumed to be an ohmic circuit coupled with a constant convective heat transfer model through a cylindrical surface.

The cables represent the most important mass-payload of the

drones. Even though a small tether sag is assumed to be negligible when computing the cable length and the distributed cable drag, such a small tether sag has an effect in the 2D mechanical equilibrium (Fig. 4.3), especially at larger scale. Thus the tether sag angle at the nominal altitude is computed by approximating the cable shape as a parabola as described in Section 4.2.7.

Finally the electrical power output is computed in Section 4.2.8.

4.2.2 Geometrical relations

This subsection is dedicated to illustrate the geometric parameters and relations. Specifically, the distance between the ground station and the center of the circular trajectory of the two drones, l_{fd} , is directly computed from the nominal flight altitude, H , and the elevation angle, β , with a basic geometrical relation (see Fig. 4.3).

$$l_{fd} = \frac{H}{\sin \beta} \quad (4.1)$$

Under the assumption of low tether sag, the distance l_{fd} is a good approximation for the length of fixed and dancing cable, defined as the sum of the length of the shared fixed cable, l_f , plus the length of one dancing cable, l_d , projected along the fixed cable direction through the half-angle between dancing cables, γ ,

$$l_f = l_{fd} - l_d \cos \gamma \quad (4.2)$$

The two-way length of the electrical cables, l_e , is twice the length of the fixed cable and two dancing cables (see Fig. 4.2). All electrical tethers are conservatively assumed to have constant section.

$$l_e = 2(l_f + 2l_d) \quad (4.3)$$

4.2.3 Distributed drag on fixed cable

The horizontal drag force generated by the absolute wind along the fixed cable, F_{hd} , is non negligible and can be approximated as:

$$F_{hd} = \int_0^H \frac{1}{2} \rho(h) V_w(h)^2 C_{\perp} (2d_{pc} + 2d_{ec}) dh \quad (4.4)$$

where $\rho(h)$ is the air density as a function of altitude; $V_w(h)$ is the absolute wind speed as a function of the variable altitude h ; C_{\perp} is the perpendicular drag coefficient of the round cable; d_{pc} is the diameter of each polymeric cable; and d_{ec} is the diameter of each electrical cable.

4.2.4 Crosswind Fly-Gen flight and drone mass

The operating wind speed (equal to the cut-in wind speed), V_{ci} , is projected considering three angles. Not only the elevation angle, β , as done in previous literature [119, 8], but also the angle induced by the cable mass, θ_c , and the angle induced by the drone mass, θ_d , that will be explained later. The projected cut-in wind speed, V_{cip} , is therefore:

$$V_{cip} = V_{ci} \cos(\beta + \theta_c + \theta_d) \quad (4.5)$$

The equivalent diameter of the dancing cable, d_{eqd} , is computed as the sum of the diameter of the polymeric cable, d_{pc} , and the diameter of the two electrical cables, $2d_{ec}$. This simple sum is valid in case the two conductive cables are outside the polymeric cable (Fig. 4.2-right), and it is conservative with respect to the coaxial case (Fig. 4.2-left).

$$d_{eqd} = d_{pc} + 2d_{ec} \quad (4.6)$$

The equivalent aerodynamic efficiency of each drone, E_{eq} , is computed as in [118]:

$$E_{eq} = \frac{C_L}{C_D + \frac{d_{eqd} C_{\perp} l_d}{4A_d}} \quad (4.7)$$

where C_L and C_D are the lift and drag coefficients of the wing, respectively, A_d is the wing surface and C_{\perp} is the perpendicular drag coefficient of each dancing cable.

The power output for the two drones, P_2 , is computed with known models [7, 8] also taking into account the momentum conservation

efficiency¹, η_m , and the efficiency of the electric turbines η_t .

$$P_2 = 2 \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho_H V_{cip}^3 \frac{4}{27} E_{eq}^2 C_L A_d \eta_m \eta_t \right) \quad (4.8)$$

where ρ_H is the air density at the flight altitude, H .

The flight speed of each drone, V_d , is computed as in [7]:

$$V_d = \frac{2}{3} V_{cip} E_{eq} \quad (4.9)$$

and the lift force generated by each drone, L , is:

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \rho_H V_d^2 C_L A_d \quad (4.10)$$

As shown in Fig. 4.3, the equivalent lift force, L_2 , generated by the two drones together is:

$$L_2 = 2L \cos(\gamma) \quad (4.11)$$

The equivalent lift is used to compute the horizontal and vertical force balance (Eqs. 4.12 and 4.13, respectively) also including the tension in the fixed cable, F_f , the mass of the two drones, $2m_d$ and the distributed drag on fixed cable F_{hd} . Notice that with a moment balance at the ground station, F_{hd} should be included in Eq. 4.12 with a discount factor between 1/2 and 1. A conservative factor of 1 is chosen. In this steady state model, it is assumed that the roll angle of each drone is increased by θ_c and θ_d so that the lift force points more upwards and balances the downward gravity components as shown in Fig. 4.3.

$$L_2 \cos(\beta + \theta_c + \theta_d) + F_{hd} = F_f \cos(\beta + \theta_c) \quad (4.12)$$

$$L_2 \sin(\beta + \theta_c + \theta_d) = 2m_d g + F_f \sin(\beta + \theta_c) \quad (4.13)$$

¹ η_m takes into account the momentum conservation applied to Fly-Gen airborne wind turbines. Theoretically, it is possible to have η_m approaching 1 in case the onboard rotors area is much bigger than the wing planform area, as explained in details in [120], in paragraph 28.2.5, where η_m is called η or also $1 - a$. For practical real world dimensions, this value is also shown to be very high.

Figure 4.3: Force balance at drones. The lift forces and the gravity forces of the two drones are summed up and considered as acting on a single point. The figure shows the lumped force equilibrium at this single point. The cable shape (together with the angle θ_c) is given by the linear mass of the cable and its tension F_f . The gravity force acting on the two drones is compensated by the angle θ_d . Note that in this balance the two drones are assumed to be in steady state flight, flying perpendicular to the screen and that the angle θ_d aims at representing the influence on the roll angle for both drones.

4.2.5 Structural equations of dancing cables

The tension in each dancing cable, F_d , is assumed to be equal to the lift force generated by the drone:

$$F_d = L \quad (4.14)$$

A basic structural cable model takes account of the area of each polymeric dancing cable, A_{pc} , the breaking strength, σ_{pc} and the safety factor, η_{pc}

$$A_{pc} = \frac{F_d \eta_{pc}}{\sigma_{pc}} \quad (4.15)$$

The polymeric dancing cable cross-section is circular

$$d_{pc} = \sqrt{\frac{4}{\pi} A_{pc}} \quad (4.16)$$

4.2.6 Electrical equations

The electrical current in the circuit, I , is related to the generated power and the voltage of the on-board turbines, V_t

$$I = \frac{P_2}{V_t} \quad (4.17)$$

A basic thermal model relates the dissipated power per unit length, P_{dl} , to the temperature difference between the surface of the electrical cables and the environment, ΔT , and to the diameter of the electrical conductor, d_{ec} , through the convective thermal coefficient h_{air} . ΔT is assumed constant throughout the whole length of the cable.

$$d_{ec} = \frac{P_{dl}}{\Delta T \pi h_{air}} \quad (4.18)$$

The relation between the total dissipated power, P_d , and the dissipated power per unit length is straightforward

$$P_{dl} = P_d / l_e \quad (4.19)$$

The total dissipated power is generated by Joule effect and depends on the electrical resistance of the cable, R_{ec}

$$P_d = R_{ec} I^2 \quad (4.20)$$

The electrical resistance of the cable is linked to the cable dimensions by means of the second Ohm's law:

$$R_{ec} = \frac{l_e \rho_{eAl}}{\frac{\pi}{4} d_{ec}^2} \quad (4.21)$$

where ρ_{eAl} is the resistivity of the conductor.

4.2.7 Fixed cable mass and shape

The linear mass of the fixed cable, m_{fl} , is the sum of the linear masses of two polymeric dancing cables and two electrical cables (see Fig. 4.2):

$$m_{fl} = 2A_{pc} \rho_{mpc} + 2 \frac{\pi}{4} d_{ec}^2 \rho_{mAl} \eta_{mAl} \quad (4.22)$$

ρ_{mpc} and ρ_{mAl} are the mass densities of the polymer and of the electrical conductor, respectively, and η_{mAl} is a safety coefficient that aims at taking into account the mass for additional insulation or coating fixtures.

In order to model the effect on the power output from the cable gravity force, the shape of the cable is approximated as a parabola that passes through the ground station and the center of the circular trajectory of the two drones. Using a parabola instead of a catenary curve is valid under the hypothesis of small tether sag, i. e. when θ_c is small. The parabola has equation $y = ax^2 + 2ax_1x$. Eq. 4.23 gives the coefficient a (that was derived in the gravity term of Eq. B.17) and Eq. 4.24 computes the coefficient x_1 geometrically.

$$a = \frac{m_{fl} g}{2F_f} \quad (4.23)$$

$$x_1 = \frac{\tan \beta}{2a} - \frac{l_{fd} \cos \beta}{2} \quad (4.24)$$

The geometrical derivative of the parabola at the flight mid point allows to compute the tether sag angle:

$$\theta_c = \arctan(2a(l_{fd} \cos \beta + x_1)) - \beta \quad (4.25)$$

4.2.8 Power output

The electrical power output is straightforward:

$$P_{out} = P_2 - P_d \quad (4.26)$$

The next section shows how this model can be used to derive the power curve of a dual drone generator by means of a several numerical case studies.

4.3 Power curves of a dual wind drone system

This section presents several examples of dual WED systems. After estimating the nominal power output with the model presented in Section 4.2, the conservative power curves are presented by means of the following additional hypotheses:

- the nominal wind speed is directly computed from the statistical wind distribution at the nominal flight altitude given a chosen Capacity Factor (CF). The nominal wind speed is the CF^{th} percentile of the distribution.
- the system is assumed to work only when the absolute wind speed is higher or equal to its nominal wind speed, i. e. the nominal wind speed is conservatively assumed equal to the cut-in wind speed. The system is assumed to be switched off when the wind speed is lower.
- the plant is assumed to work at the cut-in/nominal wind speed also when the wind speed is greater than the cut-in/nominal wind speed. In this case, the plant would work below its theoretical optimum and the excess power is assumed to be managed by means of spoilers or other control factors that are neglected in this analysis.

- the cut-off wind speed is neglected.

The resulting power curve is thus simplified into a step function and it only has an on/off threshold at the cut-in/nominal wind speed (see red lines in Fig. 4.5).

The model presented in Section 4.2 is applied to five different case studies having different sizes and flight altitudes (see table 4.2). The full list of input parameters is shown in Tables 4.1 and 4.2 and the results are presented in Table 4.3 and in Fig. 4.5.

In all the considered case studies, the WED systems are assumed to operate in Saudi Arabia, the nearest region to Europe with large availability of jet streams currents [183]. The wind data are taken from radiosonde measurements at King Fahad Airport (see Fig. 4.4).

Plant input		
Capacity factor	CF	30 %
Flight altitude	H	see table 4.2
Wing area of each drone	A_d	see table 4.2
Elevation angle	β	20 deg
Half-angle between dancing cables	γ	45 deg
Length of each dancing cable	l_d	300 m
Aerodynamic input		
Lift coefficient of drone	C_L	1.5 ()
Drag coefficient of drone	C_D	0.15 ()
Drag coefficient of each dancing cable	C_{\perp}	1 ()
Momentum conservation efficiency	η_m	0.97 ()
Polymeric cables		
Structural safety factor of polymeric cable	η_{pc}	1.25 ()
Breaking strength of polymeric cable	σ_{pc}	1500 N/mm ²
Mechanical input		
Mass of each drone	m_d	see table 4.2
Mass density of polymeric cable (UHMWPE)	ρ_{mpc}	997 kg/m ³

**CHAPTER 4. ASSESSMENT OF HIGH ALTITUDE DUAL
WIND ENERGY DRONE GENERATORS**

Mass density of electric cable (Aluminum)	ρ_{mAl}	2700 kg/m ³
Mass safety factor of electric cables (insulation)	η_{mAl}	1.3 ()
Electrical input		
Efficiency of the electric turbine	η_t	0.85 ()
Nominal voltage difference at turbines	V_t	35000 V
Electrical resistivity (Aluminum)	ρ_{eAl}	3e-8 Ω m
Convective heat exchange coefficient	h_{air}	6 W/(m ² K)
Temperature difference (electrical cable vs air)	ΔT	300 °C

Table 4.1: **Input parameters.** A parameter is chosen to be an input when it is either: a design choice, a constraint, a variable to be optimized in the future, or a variable that can be linked to other phenomena by nesting it into an additional iterative loop.

Input data, case n.	1	2	3	4	5
Wing area of each drone A_d (m ²)	20	50	50	80	124
Flight altitude H (m)	250	500	2000	5000	10000
Mass of each drone m_d (kg)	500	2000	2000	5000	12000

Table 4.2: **Input parameters for different case studies.** Five case studies are investigated from a smaller (case n. 1) to a larger generator (case n. 5).

Output data, case n.	1	2	3	4	5
Wind data @ King Fahad Airport, SA					
Air density at altitude ρ_H (kg/m ³)	1.15	1.12	0.98	0.73	0.41
Cut-in wind speed at altitude (30 % CF) $V_{ci}(m/s)$	8.1	8.5	10	19.8	42.1

CHAPTER 4. ASSESSMENT OF HIGH ALTITUDE DUAL
WIND ENERGY DRONE GENERATORS

Plant output						
Power output of the plant	P_{out} (MW)	0.14	0.27	0.36	3.2	14.87
Power coefficient	C_P (%)	39.5	44.3	16.8	6.3	2.3
Cut-in wind speed at altitude (projected)	V_{cip} (m/s)	7	6.6	7.9	16.5	31.6
Length of fixed and dancing cable	l_{fd} (m)	731	1462	5848	14619	29238
Length of fixed cable	l_f (m)	717	1448	5812	14506	29026
Diameter of dancing cable (equivalent)	d_{eqd} (mm)	7	11	12	30	59
Flight speed of each drone	V_d (m/s)	45.9	43.4	51.8	99.6	170
Equivalent aerodynamic efficiency of each drone	E_{eq} ()	9.9	9.9	9.8	9.1	8.1
Mechanical output						
Diameter of each polymeric dancing cable	d_{pc} (mm)	6	9	10	21	34
Cross section of each polymeric dancing cable	A_{pc} (mm ²)	30	66	82	363	916
Linear mass of fixed cable	ρ_f (kg/m)	0.06	0.14	0.17	0.83	2.71
Lift generated by each drone	L (kN)	36	79	98	435	1099

**CHAPTER 4. ASSESSMENT OF HIGH ALTITUDE DUAL
WIND ENERGY DRONE GENERATORS**

Tension in fixed cable	F_f (kN)	47	93	121	584	1539
Equivalent lift generated by the two drones	L_2 (kN)	51	112	139	616	1555
Angle induced by cables mass	θ_c (deg)	0.2	0.5	1.9	4.7	11
Angle induced by drone mass	θ_d (deg)	10.3	19.1	15.5	9.1	10.4
Cable parabolic parameter	a (e-6 m ⁻¹)	6.4	7.2	6.8	7	8.6
Cable parabolic parameter	x_1 (e+4 m)	2.8	2.5	2.4	1.9	0.7
Distributed drag to fixed cable tension	F_{hd}/F_f (%)	0.1	0.3	1.5	3.3	9.9
Electrical output						
Length of electrical cables (2 way)	l_e (m)	1514	2976	11825	29652	59252
Power generated by the two drones (gross)	P_2 (MW)	0.14	0.29	0.43	3.94	19.1
Dissipated power in cables (Joule effect)	P_d (MW)	0	0.01	0.07	0.74	4.23
Dissipated power in cables (Joule effect) (linear)	P_{dl} (W/m)	2.7	4.3	5.7	24.9	71.4
Diameter of each electrical cable	d_{ec} (mm)	0.5	0.8	1	4.4	12.6

CHAPTER 4. ASSESSMENT OF HIGH ALTITUDE DUAL
WIND ENERGY DRONE GENERATORS

Electrical resistance of cables	R_{ec} (Ω)	256.6	193.2	449.2	58.4	14.2
Electrical current through cables	I (A)	4	8.2	12.2	112.5	545.8

Table 4.3: **Output parameters for different case studies.** Five case studies are investigated from a smaller (case n. 1) to a larger generator (case n. 5).

4.3.1 Power coefficient of the high altitude wind drone system

An important parameter that is used to describe the technical performance of a conventional wind turbine is the ratio between the nominal power output and the available wind power $\frac{1}{2}\rho V_w^3 A_r$ through the rotor surface A_r , this number is the so called coefficient of power, C_P . It is important to remember that the maximum theoretical C_P for a conventional wind turbine is the so called Betz's limit and it is equal to $\frac{16}{27}$.

Also, the Betz's limit (as we know it) does not apply to wind drones, especially at large scale, mainly because the hypothesis of mono-dimensional flow does not hold true with respect to the annulus [8, 120, 181]. For example in this assessment, the power coefficient has reasonable values at smaller scale but it is very small at larger scale, if compared to e.g. a value of $C_P = 45\%$ for a conventional wind turbine, (see Table 4.3). The smaller values are due to the large area of the annulus that is swept by the drones. However it is worth noticing that this low efficiency is not relevant during techno-economical optimizations and it is not a weakness of large scale wind drones. If the cost of the wind drone generator is low and the output is large, having this low efficiency has to be regarded as a strength, in that it demonstrates that the margins for power optimization are large.

4.4 Future works

Possible future investigations may include: a dynamic model of a multi WED system, a more realistic power curve that has a cut-in

CHAPTER 4. ASSESSMENT OF HIGH ALTITUDE DUAL WIND ENERGY DRONE GENERATORS

Figure 4.4: Wind Power Density as a function of altitude in Saudi Arabia. The chart shows the value of the wind power density (on the x axis) that is exceeded 30% of the time at different altitudes (on the y axis). The wind carries 15.5 kW/m^2 at 10250 m, 51 times more than at low altitude. The data are taken from 432 radiosonde measurements of the wind speed as function of altitude at King Fahd Airport in Saudi Arabia throughout 2015 [184]. The jet streams carry similar power densities in many other countries, especially United States (north east), Canada (north east), Egypt, China (north east), Korea, Japan, South Africa, Argentina, Chile, Australia (south).

Figure 4.5: Power curves for the five case studies. The cable layout and the power curves for the considered WED systems are shown. The top left figure shows the cable layout of the five case studies together. The cable sag effect becomes more important as the WED size and altitude increase. Each wind drone system is assumed to work following a simplified power curve (red line) that has a cut-in wind speed that depends on the desired flight altitude. The wind statistical occurrence at the chosen altitude is represented by the blue bars.

wind speed lower than the nominal wind speed, this will certainly increase the foreseen power output; a techno-economical optimization of the dual WED with a genetic algorithm; an optimization of the number of flying drones would also be interesting, as it is reasonable to expect that more than two drones can produce more energy at a lower cost by sharing a common cable; different take-off and landing platforms and their control strategies might be investigated, e.g. ground rings for horizontal take-off of tethered drones or a multi-perch system for vertical take-off, or convertiplane-like drones, or a dual drone that can become one single drone or re-detach to increase the power output or maximize stability, a faired rope for the dual drone system; moreover, means to achieve the required fast circular motion including additional lifting surfaces on the drones or other cable layouts are also an interesting topic, e.g. additional fixed or moving surfaces at an angle with respect to the wing, or a movable cable attachment point; finally, means to achieve the helicopter-like pitch variation of the drones during the rotary motion could be investigated.

For example, a possible take-off method inspired to the discipline of control line flight [185] is shown in Fig. 4.6. In this representation two drones are connected by an horizontal cable at their starboard wing tip so that the mid point of the connection line is in the center of the take-off ring. (Fig. 4.6 top). The midpoint of the connection line is assumed to be connected to the main cable through a rotational joint. The main cable is connected vertically to the ground station (represented by a cube). The drones accelerate on the circular runway until take-off speed is achieved. Having detached from the ground, the drones are free to go up until the desired length of the main cable is reached (Fig. 4.6 bottom-left). Once that the desired length is reached, the drones (that keep rotating) are controlled in order to rotate the main cable towards the wind direction (Fig. 4.6 bottom-right). After that the slope of the main cable is set, the main cable stands still, the rotation of the drones is sustained by auto-rotation thanks to the wind, and the motors (that do not require power any longer) are used as generators.

Figure 4.6: Take-off ring. Two wind drones are linked by a cable at their starboard wing-tip. They accelerate along a circular landing strip using the power from the motors until take-off (top). After take-off, the two drones lift the main cable to the desired altitude (bottom-left). At the desired altitude, the main rope is oriented towards the wind while the two drones keep rotating (bottom-right) and finally the generation phase can start, i. e. the main cable is kept fixed and the drones continue to rotate thanks to wind power while using their motors as generators.

4.5 Conclusions

In this chapter, the power production of a dual WED system has been assessed by means of a set of simple algebraic equations. All the most relevant physical phenomena and constraints have been considered and the computations are based on real high altitude wind data.

Being not limited by the cable aerodynamic drag, the dual wind drone system might be the first Airborne Wind Energy concept that increases the power production with increasing altitude, thus potentially allowing to reach the huge power of jet streams.

Five case studies of wind drone systems having different size and flight altitude have also been analysed and their respective power curves have been presented. The nominal power output for the considered case studies range from hundreds of kW to several MW with a capacity factor of 30%.

Finally a take off ring for horizontal take-off of a dual WED system is presented for the first time.

*CHAPTER 4. ASSESSMENT OF HIGH ALTITUDE DUAL
WIND ENERGY DRONE GENERATORS*

Chapter 5

Automatic ‘control-line flight’ for high altitude wind energy drones

In chapter 4 a dual drone system potentially able to extract power at very high altitudes has been introduced. Thanks to the hypothesis of axi-symmetrical flight, a single drone can be used to model an axi-symmetric dual drone system at take-off and landing. In this chapter we describe a test campaign on a single wind drone flying round the pole in an axi-symmetric configuration, a preliminary step towards the completion of dual drone system. Full autonomous take-off and landing capabilities of the wind drone have been demonstrated by means of a test bench built in TU Delft, The Netherlands, and schematically shown in Fig. 5.1.

Among existing literature in Airborne Wind Energy, it is worth mentioning [186], where a concept for rotary take-off and landing of a single glider plane has been investigated. A rotational rigid arm introduces energy into a suspended tethered drone by pulling the rope that is connected to its fuselage. Also, among other literature unrelated to renewable energy, in [187] a system of multiple quadrotors flying round the pole is investigated.

The major differences of this work from the existing Airborne Wind Energy literature are that 1) the ground station is mechanically passive, i. e. it does not introduce energy into the system, and

2) the tether is not connected directly to the fuselage but it passes through the wing tip, following the example of the so called ‘control-line’ flight, also known as ‘u-control’ or ‘round the pole’ flight (see Fig. 5.1-bottom). During take-off and landing the drone is powered by on-board propellers while the ground station measures the tether tension and the two angular positions (elevation and azimuth). The measurements are then sent in real-time to a ground laptop for measurement and control purposes.

Figure 5.1: CAD model of the test setup. A single drone system is used to investigate an axi-symmetric dual drone system at take-off.

Moreover it is important to notice that, in an attempt of prototyping a multi drone system, crashing a multi drone system would increase significantly the overall prototyping time and cost. A great risk of crash comes from the potential failure of any subsystem of

each single drone that composes the assembly. For this reason it is reasonable to expect that testing and tuning each single drone, before assembling the multi drone system, will help reducing the overall risk and the prototyping time and cost. Therefore the single-drone arrangement shown in Fig. 5.1-bottom can be used to test and tune each drone before assembling and taking-off a multi-drone system.

In the present work, the take-off and landing phases of an axisymmetric wind drone were fully automated. Thanks to this result, it is easier to foresee that a multi-drone system will also take-off and land autonomously. Further research activities are therefore encouraged in this direction, with the final goal of prototyping a multi-drone system for jet stream wind power generation that will be able to provide more power at a lower cost.

This chapter is structured as follows: first, Section 5.1 introduces the mathematical model for a single axisymmetric drone tethered to a ground station, then the test setup is described in details in Section 5.2. The results of the autonomous flight tests are presented in Section 5.3.

5.1 Dynamic model of take off and landing of a single drone

The drone is modelled as a point mass with aerodynamic properties that is rigidly connected to the centre of rotation through an inextensible straight tether with constant length. As shown in Fig. 5.2, two coordinate systems are defined, the absolute coordinate system (x, y, z) that is fixed to the ground in the centre of rotation, and the drone coordinate system (roll, pitch, yaw) that is fixed onto the quarter chord point of the wing of the drone so that the roll axis points forward, the yaw axis points starboard, and the yaw axis points down of the drone.

Notice that, since the tether passes through the wingtip and has a tension which is an order of magnitude higher than the mass of the plane, the roll behaviour is stiffened [188, 189] and the roll coordinate can be considered equal to the tether elevation θ . The same is true for the yaw coordinate which can be considered equal to the tether azimuth φ . In order to fully represent position and attitude, it is therefore necessary to consider only the pitch coordinate ψ , the tether elevation θ and azimuth φ .

5.1.1 Position

The position of the drone \mathbf{r} can be represented in spherical coordinates with angular elevation θ , azimuth φ and tether length r . The vertical axis is chosen as polar axis and the elevation coordinate θ increases downwards.

$$\mathbf{r} = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r \sin \theta \cos \varphi \\ r \sin \theta \sin \varphi \\ r \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 5.2: Coordinate system definition. The three degrees of freedom of the drone ψ , θ , φ and the Cartesian coordinates x , y , z are shown. The tether is shown as a black line. The roll, pitch, and yaw axis of the drone coordinate system are shown in red, green and blue, respectively. The reference iso-altitude line, $\theta = \theta_{ref}$, is indicated with a magenta horizontal circle. The magenta dashed line is tangent to the circle. Notice that the elevation coordinate increases downwards by definition. For example, in this picture the coordinates of the drone are $\theta = 35 \text{ deg}$, $\varphi = 60 \text{ deg}$, $\psi = 15 \text{ deg}$.

5.1.2 Attitude

It is possible to define the position and attitude of the drone with 3 Degrees of Freedom (D.o.F.). Following the example of [190], we define the Zero configuration with the tether lying on the polar axis and the roll axis pointing towards the y direction. The first rotation is defined around z with magnitude ψ , the second rotation is around y with magnitude θ , and the third rotation is again around z with magnitude φ . The rotation matrix \mathbf{R} that allows the transformation from the Zero configuration to any configuration defined by the 3 D.o.F. is therefore as follows:

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_z(+\varphi)\mathbf{R}_y(+\theta)\mathbf{R}_z(+\psi) \quad (5.2)$$

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi \cos \theta \cos \psi - \sin \varphi \sin \psi, & -\cos \varphi \cos \theta \sin \psi - \sin \varphi \cos \psi, & \cos \varphi \sin \theta \\ \sin \varphi \cos \theta \cos \psi + \cos \varphi \sin \psi, & -\sin \varphi \cos \theta \sin \psi + \cos \varphi \cos \psi, & \sin \varphi \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta \cos \psi, & \sin \theta \sin \psi, & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}$$

It is worth noticing that, by definition, the x , y , z coordinates of the roll pitch and yaw unit vectors in the Zero configuration are $(0, 1, 0)$, $(0, 0, 1)$, $(1, 0, 0)$, respectively. This means that the non-Zero x , y , z coordinates of the roll pitch and yaw unit vectors are the second, third and first column of the \mathbf{R} matrix, respectively.

5.1.3 Kinematics

Now that the coordinate system is defined, we can derive the kinematic relations between the absolute coordinates and the angular coordinates of the drones.

Setting constant tether length ($\dot{r} = 0$) and deriving Eq. 5.1 with respect to time, it is possible to write the velocity of the drone \mathbf{v} :

$$\mathbf{v} = r\dot{\theta}\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} + r\dot{\varphi}\sin\theta\hat{\boldsymbol{\varphi}} \quad (5.3)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\varphi}}$ are the normal unit vectors in θ and φ direction, respectively, expressed in the absolute reference system. These unit vectors, together with the third unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ in the tether direction, define a useful reference frame that can be related to the drone unit

vectors (\mathbf{e}_{roll} , \mathbf{e}_{pitch} , \mathbf{e}_{yaw}) by considering the definition of the pitch coordinate ψ ,

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{r}} &= \mathbf{e}_{pitch} \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} &= \mathbf{e}_{yaw} \cos \psi - \mathbf{e}_{roll} \sin \psi \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\varphi}} &= \mathbf{e}_{yaw} \sin \psi + \mathbf{e}_{roll} \cos \psi\end{aligned}\tag{5.4}$$

It is then possible to write the velocity relations by substituting Eq. 5.4 in Eq. 5.3, decomposing the resulting equations in the roll, pitch and yaw directions according to $\mathbf{v} = v_{roll}\mathbf{e}_{roll} + v_{pitch}\mathbf{e}_{pitch} + v_{yaw}\mathbf{e}_{yaw}$, and multiplying both sides of the equations relative to the roll and yaw components by a rotation matrix of magnitude ψ . The resulting relations in velocities are:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\theta} &= \frac{1}{r} (-v_{roll} \sin \psi + v_{yaw} \cos \psi) \\ \dot{\varphi} &= \frac{1}{r \sin \theta} (v_{roll} \cos \psi + v_{yaw} \sin \psi)\end{aligned}\tag{5.5}$$

By deriving twice Eq. 5.1, it is possible to write the acceleration of the drone \mathbf{a} :

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{a} &= (-r\dot{\theta}^2 - r\dot{\varphi}^2 \sin^2 \theta) \hat{\mathbf{r}} + \\ &\quad + (r\ddot{\theta} - r\dot{\varphi}^2 \sin \theta \cos \theta) \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} + \\ &\quad + (r\ddot{\varphi} \sin \theta + 2r\dot{\theta}\dot{\varphi} \cos \theta) \hat{\boldsymbol{\varphi}}\end{aligned}\tag{5.6}$$

Similarly to what already done with the velocities, we can write the acceleration relations by substituting Eq. 5.4 in Eq. 5.6, decomposing the resulting equations in the roll, pitch and yaw directions according to $\mathbf{a} = a_{roll}\mathbf{e}_{roll} + a_{pitch}\mathbf{e}_{pitch} + a_{yaw}\mathbf{e}_{yaw}$, and multiply both sides of the equations in the roll and yaw directions by a rotation matrix of magnitude ψ . The resulting relations in acceleration are:

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{\theta} &= \frac{1}{r} (-a_{roll} \sin \psi + a_{yaw} \cos \psi + r\dot{\varphi}^2 \cos \theta \sin \theta) \\ \ddot{\varphi} &= \frac{1}{r \sin \theta} (a_{roll} \cos \psi + a_{yaw} \sin \psi - 2r\dot{\theta}\dot{\varphi} \cos \theta)\end{aligned}\tag{5.7}$$

and the expression for the acceleration in pitch direction is:

$$a_{pitch} = (-r\dot{\theta}^2 - r\dot{\varphi}^2 \sin^2 \theta) \quad (5.8)$$

5.1.4 Force balance

The following forces are considered in the force balance: tether tension T , motor thrust F_m , lift L and drag D of the main wing, lift of the elevator L_e , and gravity force F_g . With reference to Fig. 5.3, the vector expressions in the drone reference system can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T} &= -T \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{pitch} \\ \mathbf{F}_m &= F_m \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{roll} \\ \mathbf{L} &= -L \cos \alpha \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{yaw} + L \sin \alpha \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{roll} \\ \mathbf{L}_e &= -L_e \cos \alpha_e \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{yaw} + L_e \sin \alpha_e \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{roll} \\ \mathbf{D} &= -D \sin \alpha \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{yaw} - D \cos \alpha \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{roll} \\ \mathbf{F}_g &= (mg \sin \theta \cos \psi) \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{yaw} - (mg \sin \theta \sin \psi) \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{roll} + \\ &\quad - (mg \cos \theta) \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{pitch} \end{aligned} \quad (5.9)$$

where α is the angle of attack, T , F_m , L , L_e , D , F_g are the magnitudes of the forces.

By writing the force balance in the drone axes, $F_{roll} = ma_{roll}$, $F_{pitch} = ma_{pitch}$, $F_{yaw} = ma_{yaw}$ and considering the expressions of Eqs. 5.8 and 5.9, the accelerations of the drone can be derived

$$\begin{aligned} a_{roll} &= \frac{1}{m} (F_m + L \sin \alpha - D \cos \alpha + L_e \sin \alpha_e - mg \sin \theta \sin \psi) \\ a_{yaw} &= \frac{1}{m} (-L \cos \alpha - D \sin \alpha - L_e \cos \alpha_e + mg \sin \theta \cos \psi) \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

and, from the force balance along the pitch axis, the tether force expression results in

$$T = m (r\dot{\theta}^2 + r\dot{\varphi}^2 \sin^2 \theta - g \cos \theta) \quad (5.11)$$

5.1.5 Relative wind velocity and angles of attack

With reference to Fig. 5.3, the magnitude of the relative speed at the main wing, v_a , and the angles of attack on the main wing, α , and on

Figure 5.3: Force balance at the wind drone. View along the tether direction. The balance lies on the θ - φ plane. The forces are shown in black. The roll and yaw axes of the drone reference system are shown in grey. The velocity triangles are shown in red.

the elevator, α_e , are computed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 v_a &= \sqrt{v_{roll}^2 + v_{yaw}^2} \\
 \alpha &= \arctan\left(\frac{v_{yaw}}{v_{roll}}\right) \\
 \alpha_e &= \arctan\left(\frac{v_{yaw} + l_{fe}\dot{\psi}}{v_{roll}}\right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.12}$$

notice that the airflow velocity at the elevator is assumed equal to the airflow velocity at the main wing for the sake of simplicity, while the angle of attack of the elevator is considered different to take into account the natural stabilization of the pitch motion.

5.1.6 Aerodynamic coefficients and forces

The aerodynamic lift coefficients of the main wing, C_L , and of the elevator, C_{Le} , are computed assuming inviscid flow ($Re \rightarrow \infty$), elliptical wings, symmetric airfoils, constant wing profiles and no wing

twist. The drag coefficient, C_D , is assumed constant.

$$C_L = C_{L0} + \frac{2\pi\alpha}{1 + 2/\mathcal{R}} \tag{5.13}$$

$$C_{Le} = \frac{2\pi\alpha_e}{1 + 2/\mathcal{R}_e}$$

Where the coefficient C_{L0} represents the angle of incidence and the trim of the main wing. \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{R}_e are the aspect ratios of the main wing and of the elevator, respectively. The magnitude of the aerodynamic forces are therefore

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \rho v_a^2 C_L A$$

$$D = \frac{1}{2} \rho v_a^2 C_D A \tag{5.14}$$

$$L_e = \frac{1}{2} \rho v_a^2 C_{Le} A_e$$

where ρ is the air density, A and A_e are the areas of the main wing and of the elevator, respectively.

5.1.7 Pitch motion dynamics

With reference to Fig. 5.3, the dynamics of the pitch D.o.F., ψ , are modelled taking into account the pitch moment of inertia of the aircraft around the tether attachment point, J , the moment on the aircraft generated by the elevator lift, M_e , and the stabilizing moment on the aircraft generated by the gravity force, M_g . The moment balance on the quarter cord of the main wing is

$$J\ddot{\psi} = +M_e + M_g$$

$$M_e = -l_{fe} L_e \cos \alpha_e \tag{5.15}$$

$$M_g = -mg d \sin \psi$$

where l_{fe} is the distance between the tether attachment point on the fuselage (quarter cord of the main wing) and the elevator aerodynamic centre (quarter cord of the elevator) and d is the distance

between the aerodynamic centre of the main wing and centre of gravity. Notice that the centre of gravity is below the aerodynamic centre and that it is assumed zero aerodynamic moment from the main wing.

5.1.8 Horizontal steady-state flight

In the simple case of steady-state flight at constant elevation angle, the dynamic equations reduce to this trivial set of four algebraic relations: two of them are steady state equilibrium conditions

$$\begin{aligned} D &= F_m \\ L &= mg \sin \theta \end{aligned} \tag{5.16}$$

and two of them are the definitions of the aerodynamic forces

$$\begin{aligned} D &= \frac{1}{2} \rho v_a^2 C_D A \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \rho v_a^2 C_L A \end{aligned} \tag{5.17}$$

These equations can be solved explicitly by knowing the motor thrust F_m , then finding in this order D , v_a , L , θ . It is interesting to notice that from Eqs. 5.16 and 5.17 the following relation can be obtained:

$$L = F_m \frac{C_L}{C_D}$$

and that, with the additional hypothesis of θ close to 90 deg,

$$\theta \approx \frac{F_m \frac{C_L}{C_D}}{mg}$$

5.1.9 Pitch stability

In the real flights, the drone tends to fly horizontally without pitch actuation. This intrinsic pitch stability is given in the dynamic model by the M_g component of Eq. 5.15. Setting to zero the offset d , or setting the centre of gravity above the aerodynamic center, immediately results in an unstable set of equations.

5.1.10 Altitude stability

Some important information about the altitude stability of control line flight can be easily understood from the horizontal steady-state case, i.e. when the drone is flying at a constant flight velocity. In particular the flight is stable in altitude when $\theta > 90 \text{ deg}$ (drone below the horizontal plane that passes through the ground attachment point of the tether) but it is unstable when $\theta < 90 \text{ deg}$ (drone above the ground station, towards the zenith). This can be explained by perturbing the vertical force equilibrium of the steady-state case (fourth equation in Eqs. 5.16). For example, if the drone is below the ground station, a displacement *down* (i. e. an increase in θ), decreases the $mg \sin \theta$ component while the lift L is constant. The vertical balance is then dominated by L that brings the drone *up*, thus keeping a stable altitude. Conversely, in case $\theta < 90 \text{ deg}$, a displacement *up* (i. e. a decrease in θ) generates an unstable behaviour due to, again, lower gravity and same lift that brings the drone further *up*.

A simple feedforward controller can be used if the elevation angle is below the ground station and this is well confirmed by experimental results. Moreover, we foresee that a feedback controller is mandatory in order to manoeuvre the drone in the upper region of its working space, however further test campaigns are needed to experimentally validate this statement.

5.1.11 Faster than real time integration

The dynamic equations can be integrated for control or simulation purposes by following this sample procedure. First the initial positions and the initial roll and yaw velocity are set, then the angles of attack and the aerodynamic forces are computed with Eqs. 5.12, 5.13 and 5.14. By knowing the motor thrust and the gravity force, the accelerations in the drone reference frame are computed with Eq. 5.10. Integrating those in time gives the velocities which can be in turn integrated to yield the ψ , θ , φ coordinates by means of Eq. 5.5.

5.2 Test setup

As introduced in Fig. 5.1, a rotary single-drone take-off system is a useful first step towards the experimental validation of a multiple-drone axi-symmetric take-off system.

CHAPTER 5. AUTOMATIC ‘CONTROL-LINE FLIGHT’ FOR
HIGH ALTITUDE WIND ENERGY DRONES

A detailed description of the single-drone test setup is summarized in Fig. 5.4. The setup is composed by a ground station and a rotating tethered drone having full automatic take-off and landing capabilities.

Figure 5.4: Schematics of the test setup.

The drone is a revised version of a control-line model plane, therefore it does not have roll and yaw actuation capabilities, and it features only one actuator for the pitch command. Nose-up is achieved when both the ailerons are moved downward and the elevator is moved upward at the same time. Conversely, nose-down is achieved by actuating the ailerons up and the elevator down. Besides the pitch actuator, a battery, an electric engine, a flight controller and a radio receiver and transmitter are also fitted on board the plane.

The ground station is shown in Fig. 5.5. It is composed by a rotor assembly (highlighted in blue) and a stator (not highlighted). The stator is a heavy fixture that allows a maximum tether force of 9.6 kg before tilting. The rotor passively follows the azimuth and elevation position of the drone. The whole rotor rotates in azimuth while the top mechanical link (highlighted with a green box) passively follows also the elevation angle of the drone. Thanks to two absolute magnetic encoders and a load cell, the ground station measures in real time the azimuth angle, the elevation angle and the tether tension. A rotating electronic assembly then performs the data acquisition and sends the measured data to a laptop computer via a wireless

Figure 5.5: Functional CAD model of the ground station.

connection.

The laptop is able to receive at the same time the data coming from the ground station and the data coming from the plane. A soft real time controller running on the laptop at 60 Hz sends the throttle and nose-up commands to a microcontroller through a serial interface. The microcontroller first converts the commands to a Pulse Position Modulation (PPM) signal and then sends them to a standard radio control for model planes. The radio control finally forwards the signal to the drone. If compared to a custom electronic design, feeding a PPM signal to a standard radio control allows a quick setup of a reliable wireless communication from the laptop to the drone, with the disadvantage of a longer actuation time.

A picture of the overall setup is shown in Fig. 5.6 and a list of technical details is available in Table 5.1.

5.3 Automatic flight results

A fully automatic ‘take off - fly - land’ sequence can be achieved by using the test setup introduced in Section 5.2. Figs. 5.7 and 5.8 show the time history of two consecutive sequences performed in laboratory environment (without wind) with a simple feed-forward controller (a video is available in [191]).

During the ‘take-off’ sequence, the throttle increases until a suitable take-off speed is reached, then the nose-up command is increased and the drone takes-off. During the ‘flight’ sequence a simple proportional feed-forward controller tracks three different altitudes by

Ground station	
Base mass	20 kg
Tilting tether pull	94 N
Safe operating pull	78 N
Load cell	Futek monoaxial FSH00107 with custom amplifier, accuracy ± 0.2 N
Encoders	Absolute magnetic Mouser AEAT6012-A06, accuracy ± 0.1 deg
Battery	Lipo 3000 mAh 3S 25C 11Volts
Acquisition board	Udoo Neo based on ARM Cortex-M4 200 MHz
Drone	
Wingspan	0.6 m
Total mass	0.74 kg
Max recorded flight speed	17.2 m/s (62 km/h)
Flight radius	2.8 m (centre of rotation to fuselage)
Tether	Dyneema braided, 0.5mm, max 225 N
Propeller	Xoar wooden, size 9x4"
Drone electronics	
Flight controller	Pixhawk
RC receiver	Spektrum AR610
ESC	Turnigy Multistar V2 OPTO 40 Amps
Motor	Turnigy Aerodrive 3530 24 Amps
Battery	Lipo 3000 mAh 3S 25C 11Volts
Servo	Corona 919MG, actuation time 0.06 sec
Controller	
Laptop controller	Simulink based
PPM converter	Udoo Neo based on ARM Cortex-M4 200 MHz
Radio transmitter	Spektrum DX6i

Table 5.1: Details of the test setup.

CHAPTER 5. AUTOMATIC ‘CONTROL-LINE FLIGHT’ FOR HIGH ALTITUDE WIND ENERGY DRONES

Figure 5.6: The automatic model ready to fly at the Cyber-Zoo facility of TU Delft.

controlling the throttle only. Finally, in the ‘landing’ sequence the drone is slowed down until it almost touches the ground, then a full nose-down command is given and the throttle is removed.

Considering the simple feed-forward controller, the overall sequence is remarkably repeatable. It is possible to tune the steady-state model presented in Section 5.1 in order to validate experimental data in steady-state conditions. Using C_L and C_D as calibration parameters, the results are shown in Table 5.2.

Steady state flight ($\theta_{ref} = 95$ deg)		
Flight speed, $r\dot{\varphi}$	12 m/s	measured
Flight altitude, θ	95 deg	simulated 94.7 deg, measured 95 deg ± 0.5 deg
Tether force, T	36 N	simulated 38 N, measured 36 N ± 1 N
Motor thrust, F_m	1.96 N	Measured at zero flight speed
Lift coefficient, C_L	0.92 ()	Estimated by matching the elevation angle
Drag coefficient, C_D	0.25 ()	Estimated by matching the flight speed

Table 5.2: Steady state flight, model validation.

Figure 5.7: Automatic flight. The charts show the measurements from two consecutive automatic 'take off - fly - land' sequences. The measured tether tension is shown (top), together with flight speed (middle) and the azimuth (bottom).

CHAPTER 5. AUTOMATIC ‘CONTROL-LINE FLIGHT’ FOR HIGH ALTITUDE WIND ENERGY DRONES

Figure 5.8: Automatic flight. The charts show the results from two consecutive automatic ‘take off - fly - land’ sequences. In each sequence, take off is performed first, then the drone tracks elevation angles θ of 95, 90.5 and 96.5 degrees and then the drone lands. The chart shows throttle command (top), nose-up command (middle) and elevation angle (bottom).

Motor thrust, F_m	
Throttle 45%	1.37 N
Throttle 50%	1.86 N
Throttle 55%	1.96 N
Throttle 70%	3.43 N
Throttle 100%	4.90 N

Table 5.3: Experimental motor thrust of the drone, measured at zero flight speed.

5.4 Conclusions

Recent literature suggests that the so called ‘dancing drone’ (or dual drone) concept might be the first system able to reach altitudes of several thousand meters where the jet streams carry extremely large power densities, more than 15.5 kW/m² for 30% of the time. Because of this, the dancing drone concept is potentially an interesting starting point to build an ultra low cost wind turbine.

In this chapter the take off and landing for the dancing drone concept has been investigated by means of a rotating drone in axisymmetrical configuration following the example of control line flight. A dynamic model has been developed, and the flight stability was discussed.

Full automatic take-off and landing capabilities were experimentally demonstrated and two sample ‘take off - fly - land’ sequences are reported. Given the flight stability and the repeatability of the sequences, the dual drone system is foreseen to have autonomous take-off and landing capabilities and further research in this direction is highly encouraged.

Conclusions and future work

At several thousand meters above sea level, jet streams currents can reach power densities as high as 15 kW/m^2 (i. e. from 50 to 100 times more powerful than at 100 m altitude) with typical availability of more than 30%. In the attempt to exploit this resource, in the last decade several companies and research organizations patented and developed diverse principles and technical solutions for the implementation of the so called Airborne Wind Energy Systems (AWESs). These systems appear exceptionally promising from the point of view of: 1) increased power production, because of the high power density and high capacity factors and 2) reduced structural mass (10 to 50 times lighter than conventional wind turbines), thanks to the tensile loading conditions.

On the downside, current AWESs require large airspace, they can raise safety issues, and might face Not In My Back-Yard (NIMBY) effect. For these reasons, deep-offshore floating AWESs may take advantage of both the lightweight design of AWESs and the huge availability of low-cost sites for the installation of floating structures. In this thesis the dynamics of an offshore floating AWES has been investigated with two models: the first couples the aircraft steady state crosswind model with one DoF hydrodynamics of a floating platform held in place by a catenary mooring line; the second couples a 4-DoF model for Ground-Gen AWESs with a multi-DoF hydrodynamic model for the floating platform with catenary mooring. The possibility of extracting combined wind-wave power has been investigated and an open source simulator has been released.

Possible future work, actually fundamental steps towards a com-

mercial scale floating generator, includes a thorough assessment of different kinds of floating platforms and mooring systems in a simulation environment, followed by a series of small scale implementations of small scale floating AWESs.

Another important factor that is currently limiting the potential of AWESs is represented by the cable aerodynamic drag. In order to reach higher altitudes a longer cable is of course needed. However the gain in power provided by the wind at higher altitude is not enough to compensate the loss in power, through the cable drag, that increases with the cable’s length. Several concepts have therefore been proposed and patented to overcome this limitations and achieve near-zero cable drag. One of these concepts is a system of drones tethered according to a special layout that theoretically allows to overcome the physical burden of the aerodynamic drag. Based on such a concept, a multi Wind Energy Drone (WED) system has been investigated. A set of simple algebraic equations has been used to assess the power production and the most relevant physical phenomena and constraints have been considered. The proposed analytical model shows that, being not limited by the cable aerodynamic drag, the jet stream altitude wind drone system might be the first Airborne Wind Energy concept that increases the power production with increasing altitude, thus allowing to reach the unprecedented power of jet streams. A power curve of a jet stream altitude wind drone system based on real wind data in Saudi Arabia is also shown. Comparing to the 1.5 MW of a wind turbine that has blade length equal to the wing-span of each drone, or to the 0.6 MW forecast of a single wind drone (Google-Makani concept), this study foresees a power production of 15 MW from a large scale jet-stream-altitude wind drone system with a capacity factor of 30%. In order to get one step closer to such a multi WED system, a novel take-off and landing method for a system of multiple WEDs has been investigated by means of a rotating drone in axi-symmetrical configuration, following the example of control line flight. A dynamic model has been developed, and the flight stability has been discussed. A small scale test setup has been built allowing to experimentally demonstrate full automatic take-off and landing capabilities. Two sample ‘take off - fly - land’ sequences are reported. Given the flight stability and the repeatability of the sequences, a multi WED system is foreseen to have autonomous take-off and landing capabilities and further research in this direction is highly encouraged.

CHAPTER 5. AUTOMATIC ‘CONTROL-LINE FLIGHT’ FOR
HIGH ALTITUDE WIND ENERGY DRONES

As regards multi WEDs systems, future work towards a small scale demonstrator can be divided in four parallel frameworks:

1. A *control subsystem*, composed of model planes with on-board batteries, should demonstrate the capability of taking-off/landing the multi WED system but, most importantly, it should demonstrate the capability of keeping the desired set-points in terms of inclination and tension of the main tether, at first in a laboratory environment, and then in real wind conditions.
2. An *on-board generation subsystem* that allows to generate power from the relative wind should be built following the examples of existing Fly-Gen AWESs;
3. An *electro-mechanical tethering system* should resist the structural loads while providing and receiving electricity between the ground station and the on-board generation subsystem. A custom-built small scale setup in a laboratory environment might allow a relatively fast development of this subsystem;
4. A *ground station assembly* should be built. It should be able to handle the cables and resist the structural loads, while safely transmitting the electrical power.

Finally, these four subsystems should be assembled together in order to create a fully-functional small scale prototype that should be used to demonstrate power production at different altitudes and should be used to measure the power productivity of the multi WED system. Measuring the power output, together with the wind conditions and other relevant information, plays a fundamental role in the overall technology development process in that it allows data-driven forecasts about the productivity at larger scale and higher altitude by means of validated power curves.

*CHAPTER 5. AUTOMATIC 'CONTROL-LINE FLIGHT' FOR
HIGH ALTITUDE WIND ENERGY DRONES*

Appendix A

How to use the open source multi d.o.f floating offshore AWE simulator

This chapter explains how to use the simulation tool based on the model described in chapter 3 with a step by step guide. The source code of the simulator and a sample video is available at [11].

A.1 Step by step guide

The simulation is divided into five phases as shown in Fig. A.1. Given a buoy geometry, a first hydrodynamic preprocessing is performed where the hydrodynamic coefficients are found (see Section A.2), an input script is called where all the useful data is defined, then a time-domain integrator processes the input generating the output, and finally the results are shown thanks to a postprocessing script (see Section A.6).

[]

*APPENDIX A. HOW TO USE THE OPEN SOURCE
MULTI D.O.F FLOATING OFFSHORE AWE SIMULATOR*

Figure A.1: Main simulator script The simulation tool runs first the input file, then launches the Simulink time domain integration and finally shows the results.

A.2 Hydrodynamic preprocessing

Every time the geometry is changed, a manual phase of hydrodynamic preprocessing is needed to compute the hydrodynamic coefficients of the floating platform. The hydrodynamic preprocessing is not needed if the platform geometry is not changed because it is valid for different sea state conditions, mooring and kite data. The hydrodynamic preprocessing is in turn composed by three phases, first the hydrodynamic coefficients are computed with a commercial BEM software such as WAMIT, NEMOH or AQWA (Fig. A.2), then a state space model identification is performed in order to build a dynamic system that has the proper response with a wide-spectrum wave input, (Fig. A.3) finally, the original system and the identified system response is checked (Fig. A.4).

Once this is done, a faster than real time simulation tool is available for first design iterations.

Figure A.2: Computation of the hydrodynamic coefficients A commercial BEM solver is used to compute the hydrodynamic coefficients at different frequencies.

A.3 Input simulation options

The simulation file `MAIN_simulator.m` allows to choose the following options.

- `plotplot.animation_on` switches on/off the animation pane (Fig. A.5) when set to 1 or 0, respectively.
- `plotplot.verbose_plot_on` switches on/off the detail plots (Fig. A.6).

APPENDIX A. HOW TO USE THE OPEN SOURCE
MULTI D.O.F FLOATING OFFSHORE AWE SIMULATOR

Figure A.3: State space identification. The state space identification is performed.

Figure A.4: Validation of the resulting reduced model. The reduced model is validated.

- `kite_force_on` decouples the kite and the platform so that the kite is affected by the platform motion but the platform dynamics are not affected by the kite force. This option is useful to investigate how the kite affects the floating platform.
- `waves_on` switches on and off the waves. This option allows to choose between calm sea and sea with waves.
- `platform_displacement_on` switches on and off the platform motion regardless of the forces that are applied to the platform. This option is useful to investigate how the floating platform motion affects the kite dynamics.

A.4 Input platform and mooring data

In the file `AWEC_input.m` the following parameters related to the floating platform can be chosen:

- `h` is the water depth in m. Only values higher than 20 m are acceptable because the hydrodynamics of the platform are computed in deep water conditions,
- `geom.pc` is the 3d vector expressing the cable output point position in platform coordinates.
- `ss.type` sets the sea state type. 0 indicates monochromatic regular waves and 1 indicates polychromatic irregular waves;
- `T` is the wave period for regular waves or the energy period (T_e) for irregular waves;
- `H` is the wave height for regular waves or the significant wave height (H_s) for irregular waves;
- `Lm` is the length of the mooring line in m;
- `x_plat_initial` is the initial x coordinate (m);
- `y_plat_initial` is the initial y coordinate (m);

The script `load_platform.m` loads the following geometry data and BEM results:

- `D` (m) barge diameter;

- l (m) total height (draft plus emerged part);
- d (m) nominal draft;
- W (rad/s) vector of angular frequencies;
- $GAMMA$ matrix, the rows correspond to different frequencies, and columns are the wave excitation loads per unit wave amplitude. $GAMMA(:,1:3)$ is in (N/m), $GAMMA(:,4:6)$ is in (Nm/m);
- $PHASE.g$ are the corresponding frequency-dependent phase angles (rad) of the wave excitation loads on the different DoFs;
- $MINF$ is the infinite-frequency added-mass matrix;
- $Arad$, $Brad$, $Crad$, $Drad$ are state-space matrices for radiation loads.

A.5 Input kite data

In the file `AWEC.input.m` the following parameters can be chosen.

- `data.Vw` sets the wind speed in m/s ;
- `data.E` sets the equivalent aerodynamic efficiency (non dimensional);
- `data.rho_a` sets the air density in kg/m^3 ;
- `data.Ak` sets the area of the kite in m^2 ;
- `data.CL` sets the lift coefficient of the kite (non dimensional);
- `data.gk` sets the proportional factor of the turn rate law [138] in rad/m ;
- `psi0` sets the initial ψ coordinate in rad ;
- `theta0` sets the initial θ coordinate in rad ;
- `fi0` = sets the initial φ coordinate in rad ;
- `L0` = sets the initial flying cable length in m ;
- `contr.kPg` sets the gamma proportional control gain [33];

- `contr.initial_att_p` sets the initial attraction point of the switching control algorithm. It can be either 1, 2, 3 or 4.
- `contr.fi` is a vector containing the φ coordinates of the four attraction points in *rad*.
- `contr.theta` is a vector containing the θ coordinates of the four attraction points in *rad*.
- `contr.fi.th` is a vector containing the thresholds of the φ coordinate for the switching condition expressed in *rad* ;
- `contr.theta.th` is a vector containing the thresholds of the θ coordinate for the switching condition expressed in *rad*;
- `contr.type` sets the reel-out control strategy: 1 indicates force control while 2 indicates velocity control;
- `contr.Vr0` sets the reel-out speed (expressed in *m/s*) in case `contr.type` is equal to 2.
- `contr.Fk0` sets the force set-point (expressed in *N*) in case the variable `contr.type` is equal to 1.
- `contr.kPf` is the kite force proportional gain and is used only if `contr.type` is equal to 1.
- `contr.Vr_in` sets the reel-in speed in *m/s*.
- `contr.L_min` sets the reel-in to reel-out threshold in the cable length;
- `contr.L_max` sets the reel-out to reel-in threshold in the cable length.

A.6 Simulation results

To get the results it is sufficient to run the file `MAIN_simulator.m` from the Matlab environment. The animation pane shown in Fig. A.5 will pop up together with the plots of the results (Fig. A.6).

The animation pane (Fig. A.5) shows three figures. The top left figure shows a close view of the motion of floating platform. In this figure also a small part of the mooring line and of the flying tether

APPENDIX A. HOW TO USE THE OPEN SOURCE MULTI D.O.F FLOATING OFFSHORE AWE SIMULATOR

Figure A.5: Animation of the Offshore AWES Simulator. The animation pop up is composed by a set of 3 subplots, showing the floating platform view (top left), the aerial kite view (top right) and the underwater mooring line view (bottom left).

are shown. The top right figure shows a far aerial view of the kite and flying tether. The bottom left figure shows a far submarine view of the mooring line.

Finally the postprocessor shows the main simulation results by means of a set of plots (see Fig. A.6):

- Plot n. 1 shows the time history of the platform displacements,
- Plot n. 2 shows the time history of the platform rotations,
- Plot n. 3 shows the top view of the x - y platform trajectory,
- Plot n. 4 shows the kite trajectory as viewed looking towards the wind direction,
- Plot n. 5 shows the time history of the tether length,
- Plot n. 6 shows the non dimensional steering input to the kite,
- Plot n. 7 shows the time history of the tether force,

APPENDIX A. HOW TO USE THE OPEN SOURCE
MULTI D.O.F FLOATING OFFSHORE AWE SIMULATOR

Figure A.6: Output plots of the Offshore AWES Simulator. A set of 9 plots is shown. 1) Platform displacements; 2) Platform rotations; 3) Platform trajectory - top view; 4) Kite trajectory - view towards the wind direction; 5) Tether length; 6) Non dimensional steering input; 7) Tether force; 8) Coupled motion; 9) Mechanical power output.

*APPENDIX A. HOW TO USE THE OPEN SOURCE
MULTI D.O.F FLOATING OFFSHORE AWE SIMULATOR*

- Plot n. 8 represents the coupled motion according to the definition given in Eq. 3.17,
- Plot n. 9 shows the time history of the mechanical power output.

Appendix B

Cables for Airborne Wind Energy

As introduced in Chapter 1, the tethering system represents a major challenge in the development of Airborne Wind Energy Systems. There are several reasons for this. The tether has a large aerodynamic drag and therefore has a major effect on the overall aerodynamic performance of the AWES and also on the aerodynamic design of the aircraft. The tether has to withstand important structural loads and in some cases it has to carry electricity for on-board actuation or power transmission. The tether wear is likely to be an important design factor in many large scale designs. Finally a tether is not straightforward to handle automatically. As for the material, common choices for AWESs tether are UHMWPE (known commercially as Dyneema) or Kevlar.

This appendix describes a model to predict the shape of a tether in crosswind flight. Important shape parameters such as the angle with respect to the aircraft are derived.

B.1 Cable sag 2D steady state model

This section briefly shows the results of the application of a simple 2D model for computing the kite tether sag under steady state aerodynamic loading [124].

The model computes analytically the tether shape by assuming

constant tension along the tether and a relative wind velocity that varies linearly along the length as shown in Fig. B.1.

Figure B.1: Triangular relative wind Simplest hypothesis on wind distribution.

B.1.1 Differential steady state model at constant tension

Assuming constant tether length and no inertia forces along the tether as shown in Fig. B.2, it is possible to derive the analytical equation for the tether sag. The aerodynamic force is assumed perpendicular to the undeformed tether shape and the deflection is assumed small. The undeformed tether lies on the x axis.

Figure B.2: Differential model Steady state 2D tether model.

In this section the 2D steady state tether model is analyzed in the following cases:

- Without gravity, constant air density, ρ

- Without gravity, variable air density
- With gravity, constant air density

B.1.2 Without gravity, constant ρ

With reference to Fig. B.2, the vertical equilibrium equation of the infinitesimal element can be written as

$$T \sin \left(\left. \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right|_{x+dx} \right) - T \sin \left(\left. \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right|_x \right) + dF_{aer} = 0 \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Where T is the tether tension and dF_{aer} is the aerodynamic force acting on the infinitesimal piece of tether. Assuming small tether sag, y , and small sag derivative, $\partial y/\partial x$, the equation can be further simplified to the first order and becomes:

$$T \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2} dx = -dF_{aer} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Considering

$$dF_{aer} = -\frac{1}{2} \rho V_R(x)^2 C_{dc} d \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$V_R(x) = V_k \frac{x}{r} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

where $V_R(x)$ is the relative wind velocity acting along the tether, C_{dc} is the tether perpendicular drag coefficient, d is the tether diameter, V_k is the kite velocity and r is the tether length, the equation becomes:

$$T \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{2} \rho V_k^2 \frac{x^2}{r^2} C_{dc} d \quad (\text{B.5})$$

The integration of equation B.5 along the tether length, with boundary conditions $y(0) = y(r) = 0$, yields:

$$y(x) = \frac{1}{2} \rho V_k^2 C_{dc} d \frac{1}{T} \frac{(x^4 - r^3 x)}{12r^2} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Equation B.6 represents the tether shape. Notice that, because of the assumption of small tether sag, the overall tether length is not strictly preserved.

The angle between the undeformed tether shape and the deformed shape at the kite-tether joint can be computed

$$\omega = \arctan \left(\left. \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \right|_r \right) = \arctan \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho V_k^2 C_{dc} d \frac{3r}{12T} \right) \quad (\text{B.7})$$

and the maximum displacement can also be obtained

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$x_{max} = r \sqrt[3]{\frac{1}{4}} \approx 0.63r \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$y_{max} = \frac{1}{2} \rho V_k^2 C_{dc} d \frac{r^2}{16T} \sqrt[3]{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

This means that the maximum displacement is located at 63 % of the tether length, regardless of all the other variables.

B.1.3 Without gravity, variable ρ

In case variable air density along the tether is taken into account, equation B.5 becomes:

$$T \frac{\partial^2 y_\rho}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{2} \rho(x) V_k^2 C_{dc} d \frac{x^2}{r^2} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Equation B.11 can be easily integrated numerically or can be written in an analytical form by defining

$$\rho(x) = \rho + \Delta\rho(x, \beta) \quad (\text{B.12})$$

$$k = \frac{1}{2} V_k^2 C_{dc} d \frac{1}{r^2 T} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

where β is the elevation angle at which the kite flies. The integral of equation B.11 is

$$y_\rho(x) = y(x) + \Delta y_\rho(x) = \frac{1}{12} k \rho x^4 + k \iint \Delta\rho(x, \beta) x^2 dx^2 \quad (\text{B.14})$$

plus the boundary conditions $y_\rho(0) = 0$ and $y_\rho(r) = 0$.

It is possible to define the error in the maximum displacement obtained by considering a variable air density (taking into account the altitude) with respect to the case in which air density is considered constant.

$$err_\rho = \frac{\Delta y_\rho(x)}{y(x)} \Big|_{x=x_{max}} = \frac{[\iint \Delta\rho(x, \beta)x^2 dx^2] \Big|_{x=x_{max}}}{\frac{1}{12}x_{max}^4 \rho} \quad (B.15)$$

From equation B.15 it is interesting to notice that the error err_ρ depends only on r , ρ and β .

B.1.4 With gravity, constant ρ

In case the gravity force is added to the aerodynamic force in the differential model, equation B.5 becomes:

$$T \frac{\partial^2 y_g}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{2} \rho V_k^2 C_{dc} d \frac{x^2}{r^2} + gm_l \quad (B.16)$$

where m_l is the mass per unit length of tether.

The integral of equation B.16 represents the tether shape and is

$$y_g(x) = y(x) + \Delta y_g(x) = \frac{1}{2} \rho V_k^2 C_{dc} d \frac{1}{T} \frac{(x^4 - r^3 x)}{12r^2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{gm_l}{T} (x^2 - rx) \quad (B.17)$$

It is possible to define the error in the maximum displacement obtained by considering the gravity effect with respect to the case in which gravity force is neglected.

$$err_g = \frac{\Delta y_g(x)}{y(x)} \Big|_{x=x_{max}} = \frac{16 gm_l \left(\sqrt[3]{\frac{1}{4}} - 1 \right)}{\rho V_k^2 C_{dc} d} \quad (B.18)$$

B.1.5 Numerical results

For the case of a kite flying crosswind in the conditions defined in Tab. B.1, the results are shown in Figs. B.3 and B.4.

The angle ω at the kite-tether joint (which is zero when the tether is a straight line) is:

- $\omega = 11.08$ deg (analytical value - without gravity, constant ρ)
- $\omega = 10.67$ deg (numerical value - without gravity, variable ρ)
- $\omega = 11.77$ deg (analytical value - with gravity, constant ρ)

Simulation data	
Air density	$\rho = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$
Kite velocity	$V_k = 80 \text{ m/s}$
Cable diameter	$d = 0.020 \text{ m}$
Cable drag coefficient	$C_{dc} = 1$
Tension in the rope	$T = 100000 \text{ N}$
Cable length	$r = 1000 \text{ m}$
Elevation angle	$\beta = 30 \text{ deg}$

Table B.1: 2D tether model data

Figure B.3: Cable sag Cable sag of a kite tether. The world coordinates, x_w and y_w , have the same scale

Figure B.4: Cable sag Cable sag shown in the tether reference system, x and y . Deformation is emphasized.

The difference of the maximum displacement obtained with variable air density (from International Standard Atmospheres (ISAs) table) with respect to the maximum displacement obtained with constant air density is $err_{\rho} = 3.19\%$.

The difference of the maximum displacement obtained with gravity with respect to the maximum displacement obtained without gravity (with constant air density in both cases) is $err_g = -9.83\%$.

B.2 Partitioned tether fairing

As explained in section 1.6, tether aerodynamic drag represents an important physical limit in the development of AWESs, therefore this section describes a novel tether concept aimed at overcoming the tether drag issue.

B.2.1 Concept

Cable fairing is a well known technique that allows to reduce the tether drag and is used in a wide variety of applications, especially underwater [192, 193, 194]. Cable fairing has the potential to reduce

substantially aerodynamic drag while solving the stability issues of streamlined cross-sections. A summary of the potential advantages that can be achieved thanks to tether fairing are shown in Fig. B.5.

Figure B.5: Potential reduction in tether drag The drag coefficients, C_d , computed with reference to the section thickness are shown. Cable fairing may lead to a 15-25 folds decrease in tether drag thus increasing substantially (possibly by a factor of two or three [123]) the power output of a crosswind AWE generator.

The proposed solution is shown in Fig. B.6 and a mock-up is represented in Fig. B.7. Several independent faired sections are free to rotate around the inner tether and their position is ensured by the use of rings that are fixed to the tether. Some backlash will allow the tether to align with the wind direction with minimal aerodynamic force. This concept is similar to other submarine concepts [193].

Figure B.6: Partitioned fairing The partitioned fairing concept exploits known technology applying it to the AWE field.

Figure B.7: Mock-up of the partitioned fairing concept. A 9 mm ropes passes through the fairing section: a streamlined NACA0020 symmetrical profile.

B.2.2 Experimental procedure

The experimental procedure described in this section aims at investigating the large scale behavior of faired tethers for AWE systems through small scale measurements as shown in Fig. B.8. Each independent faired subsection can be modeled with a multi D.o.F. system, for example two coordinates in the plane of the relative airflow and a third coordinate representing the rotation of the section about the tether axis, and the model coefficients can be measured experimentally at small scale. The full scale behavior can then be rigorously simulated.

Figure B.8: Experimental procedure for aerodynamic tether measurements. Thanks to small scale measurements it is possible to simulate the dynamics of large scale systems.

Figure B.9: Modeling fairing dynamics for AWESs Cable fairing is modeled with a multi D.o.F. aeroelastic system and the coefficients are measured experimentally.

This kind of test can be performed with different facilities, e.g. a wind tunnel campaign or by means of a laboratory car. This latter case, being relatively inexpensive, is here explored in more detail.

Such a laboratory car should be equipped with load cells for multi-axial force measurements and an high speed camera to measure the time history of the tether degrees of freedom by means of computer vision algorithms (see Figs. B.10 and B.11). Differential measurements with a reference tether are an important validation tool. It is easy to show that inertial loads of the moving vehicle are not an issue.

Figure B.10: Experimental setup for partitioned low-drag tether concept A specially equipped laboratory car is used for data acquisition.

The fixtures on the laboratory car must be positioned at a significant distance from the car roof in order to make the fairing work in a reasonably undisturbed flow. A sample analysis of such a flow is shown in Fig. B.12. A slightly disturbed flow is visible at a distance of 1 m from the roof at low speed (around 60 km/h). Further

Figure B.11: Experimental setup details Load cells for multiaxial differential measurements are shown together with an high speed camera. Markers along the tether could also be used to effectively measure the tether position with computer vision techniques.

CFD investigation is needed to asses the minimum vehicle velocity at which the test can be considered in undisturbed flow in the real setup.

Figure B.12: Simplified vision analysis of the airflow around a sport car and family car. At low speed the flow at 1 meter height is slightly compressed. Base pictures from [195, 196].

Appendix C

Fast solver based on non-linear iterative nested loops

Non-linear systems are difficult to solve in that no specific methodology guarantees a solution and multiple solutions are generally possible. However, a solution method for the non-linear system presented in section 5.1 is found to be as follows: first the cut-in wind speed of the plant is computed by a pre-processor, then an iterative procedure solves the non linear equations, and finally a post-processor performs some double checks to avoid errors in the implementations. It is important to notice that this particular solution method depends on the set of variables that are assumed to be inputs and the set of variables that are assumed to be unknown (outputs). The full list of input and output parameters is shown in Tables 4.1 and 4.3.

C.1 Pre-processing wind data analysis

A pre-processor is used to compute the operating wind speed depending on the specific site data. More specifically, the pre-processing routine has the following inputs:

- The desired capacity factor of the plant, CF
- The working altitude of the drones, H

- The statistical wind data in the chosen site in the reference period

and the pre-processor outputs are:

- The operational/cut-in wind speed, V_{ci} (computed as the CF^{th} percentile of the wind speed statistical distribution at the operating altitude, H)
- The average air density at the operating altitude, ρ_H
- The wind speed and air density distributions at different altitudes, $V_w(h)$ and $\rho(h)$

The wind statistics are extracted from the radiosonde database in [184] and the average air density is computed with the ideal gas law $\rho_H = p_H / (287.05 T_H)$, where p_H and T_H are the average pressure and temperature at the operational altitude in the reference period expressed in Pa and °K respectively.

C.2 Solver processing

After that the operational/cut-in wind speed and the air density are computed by the pre-processor, the system of 26 equations in 26 unknowns introduced in Section 5.1 is solved with a recursive iterative procedure. The equations are arranged into four nested iterative loops as shown in Fig. C.1. Numerical stability and convergence in a wide range of input data are achieved by having the inner core to solve the well known AWE algebraic models used for first assessments and then adding external loops for each physical phenomenon that needs to be analyzed.

With reference to Fig. C.1, first, Equations 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 are solved to compute the geometrical parameters, then an initial guess is made for the following three variables: θ_c , d_{ec} , d_{pc} . Then Eq. 4.4 is solved, and the fourth guess θ_d is made. Subsequently, the core Equations 4.5, 4.6, 4.7, 4.8, 4.9, 4.10, 4.11, 4.12, 4.13 are iterated in the inner loop until the fourth guessed variable θ_d converges. Then the cable structural Eqs. 4.14, 4.15, 4.16, together with the whole inner loop and the drag equation Eq. 4.4, are iterated in the second-to-inner loop until the third variable d_{pc} also converges. Note that for each single iteration pass of the second-to-inner loop, the inner loop

is solved with several iteration passes. Now that both the fourth and the third variable θ_d and d_{pc} converged, the electrical equations in the third-to-inner loop, Eqs. 4.17, 4.18, 4.19, 4.20, 4.21 are iterated together with the second-to-inner loop until the second guessed variable, d_{ec} , converges. Similarly to the previous loop, for each iteration pass of the third-to-inner loop, the second-to-inner loop is solved several times. After that, the outer loop solves the cable gravity equations 4.22, 4.23, 4.24, 4.25 until also the first guessed variable, θ_c , converges. After that all variables converged, the power output is finally computed with Eq. 4.26.

Despite this numerical intensive structure, the solver is extremely fast and converges usually in a few seconds up to less than 0.5 seconds in a standard laptop, thus allowing to build optimization algorithms on top of it.

C.3 Post-processing and hovering constraint

The postprocessor displays the output and runs some redundant checks to issue automatic warnings to prevent human errors when writing the code and to verify that all the hypotheses hold true.

Besides that, the post-processor checks that the required mass of the electrical turbines/motor is compatible with the drone mass and displays the minimum rotor area that is required for vertical take-off (not using the horizontal ring of Fig. 4.6) up to 1000 m altitude, assuming 6 rotors per drone. This hovering viability check is performed by computing a reasonable rotor area with a first approximation physical model as follows:

$$m_{sm} = \frac{P_2}{12P_{toW}}$$

where m_{sm} is the mass of a single rotor and P_{toW} is the Power-to-Weight ratio of the motors.

The Hovering Specific Electric Consumption H_{SEC} is the ratio between the required electrical power for vertical take-off and the lifted mass

$$H_{SEC} = \frac{P_2}{2(m_d + m_c + 6m_{sm})}$$

APPENDIX C. FAST SOLVER BASED ON NON-LINEAR
ITERATIVE NESTED LOOPS

Figure C.1: **Solver routine.** The solver is composed by 4 nested iteration loops. The inner loop is the most important and models the crosswind flight. Every outer loop models an additional phenomenon. Despite his numerical intensive structure, the solver is extremely fast.

APPENDIX C. FAST SOLVER BASED ON NON-LINEAR
ITERATIVE NESTED LOOPS

where $m_{c\ 1000} = 1000\ m_{fl}$ is the mass of 1000 m of cables assumed to be carried by each drone.

The hovering specific electric consumption is linked to the rotor area of each rotor, A_{sr} , by the physical relation

$$A_{sr} = \eta_{hov} \frac{P_2}{12 \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho_g \left(\frac{2H_{SEC}}{g} \right)^3 \right)}$$

where ρ_g is the air density at ground level (1.22 kg/m³), g is the gravity constant, and η_{hov} is a lumped coefficient assumed to be equal to 10 to roughly match real data from convertiplanes and large helicopters that have rotor diameters around 10 m and H_{SEC} around 200 W/kg at take-off.

*APPENDIX C. FAST SOLVER BASED ON NON-LINEAR
ITERATIVE NESTED LOOPS*

Appendix D

Technical drawings of the wind drone experimental setup

This appendix contains the executive technical drawings that were used in the experimental setup described in Chapter 5.

APPENDIX D. TECHNICAL DRAWINGS OF THE WIND
DRONE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

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 DRONE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Rotor - top mount - theta arm part 1

APPENDIX D. TECHNICAL DRAWINGS OF THE WIND
DRONE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Rotor - top mount - theta arm part 2
(only differences from part 1 are shown)

APPENDIX D. TECHNICAL DRAWINGS OF THE WIND
DRONE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

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DRONE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

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